

**SUSTAINABLE RAINWATER HARVESTING SYSTEM IN LAE
CITY, A MODEL FOR PAPUA NEW GUINEA**

Carl Anthony Smith

**A Thesis submitted in fulfilment of the requirement for the degree of
Master of Philosophy (Civil Engineering)**

**Department of Civil Engineering
Papua New Guinea University of Technology**

January, 2016

STATEMENT OF ORIGINALITY

I, Carl Smith declare that the research project entitled sustainable rainwater harvesting systems (SRHS) in Lae city: a model for Papua New Guinea on fulfilment of the requirements for the award of Masters of Philosophy degree in Civil Engineering at the Papua New Guinea University of Technology is original work based on the following five objectives:

1. Review existing global, national and local rainwater harvesting and its policy, and propose a policy framework in its absence or where policy strategies are weak and does not address effectively for sustainable rainwater harvesting that will support the needs of the communities.
2. Examine the rainfall availability in Lae for sustainability of supply.
3. Assessment of the study area topography where the SHRS model would be feasible.
4. Provide a design model of a sustainable rainwater harvesting system (SRSH) as an alternative water supply infrastructure that is not mechanical/electrically driven in harvesting rainwater.
 - a. Catchment area
 - b. Rainwater Collection Tank
 - c. Utilities
 - d. Network Distribution
5. Develop a scaled prototype for modeling and simulation of SRHS, for potential replication throughout the country.

To the best of my knowledge the content of this research project has not been submitted to any other University for the award of a degree or diploma, the approach has not encountered any textbook or published paper in the field and as such it is original research effort.

MEng. (by Research) Student: Carl Smith

Date: September 5, 2016

Signature:

ABSTRACT

The Sustainable Rainwater Harvesting System (SRHS) is a strategy to harvest rainwater and use the resource sustainably to support the need for water supply in the Papua New Guinea University of Technology (PNG). Lae City is the Garden City of PNG attributed to its significant rainfall. The vast resource of rainfall, at the moment is not fully harnessed, to support the need for water supply to the population today and the future. The methodology to a SRHS covers four phases. Phase 1 covers the assessment of parameters about rainwater harvestings: such as regulations, catchment location including its topography, and rainfall availability. Phase II, deals with Design of the SRHS facility that is non-energy intensive. Phase III discusses how to maintain and managed a SRHS. Phase IV- is the prototype of the facility. A prototype is a scaled visual presentation of the project study. It will also serve as a basis for funding proposal presentations. The study found that the feasibility of the project requires an attributed characteristic of a rainforest to harness rainwater supply as accounted for by the hydrologic cycle. The location chosen is adjacent to the Rainforest Habitat on the Papua New Guinea University of Technology campus. The facility will also support on providing groundwater surcharged. The study provides a framework that will support sustainable rainwater harvesting in the country based on SRHS model. The project will serve as a model to a sustainable rainwater harvesting systems as a viable alternative in harnessing natural resource (water) of the country.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

I wish to thank Dr. Mirzi Betasolo for her selfless guidance in the completion of this research. She introduced me to many new concepts in Civil Engineering and has educated me on several computer software used in this research and taught me how to analyse technical engineering ideas and applying them to real life situations. She coordinated me throughout this work and provided constant reinforcement all the way.

I wish also to extend deepest gratitude to Mr. Chris Kobal Head of the Civil Engineering Department and Mr. Josiah Novulu Deputy Head of the department who both made it their point of duty to help me to fit in the new environment both academically and socially. Thanks to all the lecturers who have advised me on various aspects of the research, but especially to Mr. William Pikire who went personally to various departments to gather data for this research, I must also mentioned by name Ms. Julie- Anna Banduru who went to the weather bureau several times in Port Moresby, while on holidays to gather weather data for this research. The author of this study is indeed very grateful to Ms. Lydia Tasi who have helped, so that this paper could be completed with such clarity, thanks for her patience to ably assist the author through the very tedious aspect of fine tuning the mechanics of the paper and help to format this document. The admin staffs in the department have been very kind, supportive and effective in their effort to assist to put this research together. Dr. Harry Sakulas and Mr. Peter Clark made invaluable contribution to this research by providing verifiable information on the rainforest habitat on UNITECH campus, as they were instrumental in the initial implementation and operation of the idea. Many thanks for their contribution as the rainforest habitat provides the corner stone of the philosophy of reserved vegetation for rainfall inducement and continuous water supply for sustainable rainwater harvesting system.

Thanks to my family in Jamaica especially my wife Lisa who has sacrificed greatly to see me through this research. To my other colleagues and associates who have been timely in their support even from that distance. I must make mention of Mr. Sylvio Tracy who has remotely from that distance assisted to complete working drawings on time and accurately, many thanks to you.

TABLE OF CONTENT

ABSTRACT	ii
ACKNOWLEDGMENT	iii
TABLE OF CONTENT	iv
LIST OF FIGURES	viii
ACRONYMS	x
CHAPTER 1	1
1. INTRODUCTION	1
1.1 Problem Statement	3
1.2 Hypothesis and Null Hypothesis.....	3
1.3 Research Objectives	4
1.4 Materials and Methods.....	4
1.5 Conceptual Framework	6
1.5.1 Phase I – Data Collection.....	7
1.5.2 Phase II – Design of SRHS	10
1.5.3 Phase III – Maintenance and management.....	10
1.5.4 Phase IV –SRHS Prototype.....	11
1.6 Proposed Study Sites.....	12
CHAPTER 2	17
2. LITERATURE REVIEW	17
2.1 Global Perspective	17
2.1.1 World Bank.....	18
2.1.2 Rainwater Harvesting Capacity Centres	18
2.1.3 Water Harvesting in the Caribbean.....	21
2.1.3.1 Community Rainwater Harvesting Systems in Jamaica	22
2.1.3.2 Barbados experience	23
2.1.3.2.1 Rainfall Data – Barbados Case	24
2.1.3.3 Bermuda experience.....	25
2.1.4 Global examples transferable to Papua New Guinea (PNG)	27
2.2 Local Perspective	28
2.2.1 Brief background to Water PNG.....	29
2.2.1.1 Water PNG establishment and mandate.....	30
2.2.1.2 Water Use Regulations in PNG	32

2.2.1.3 Water PNG Roles.....	32
2.3 Rainwater Harvesting and Climate Change in PNG	35
2.4 Ground water recharged potential of rainwater in Lae City.....	40
2.5 Rainfall in Papua New Guinea (PNG)	40
2.5.1 Rainfall in Lae City.....	41
2.5.2 Reserve Vegetation for sustainable rainwater supply in Lae City	41
2.5.3 Sustainable Rainwater Harvesting and the Hydrologic Cycle	44
2.5.3.1 Hydrologic Cycle	44
2.6 Principle of a sustainable rainwater harvesting system design model	46
2.6.1 Basic Design model of a sustainable rainwater harvesting system.....	48
2.6.1.1 Rainfall.....	48
2.6.1.2 Catchment Area.....	49
2.6.1.3 Conveyance System- Filter/Separation.....	49
2.6.1.4 Storage tanks	49
2.6.1.5 Sizing Storage Tank.....	51
2.6.1.6 Filtering.....	51
2.6.1.7 Disinfecting.....	52
2.6.1.8 Treatment	52
2.6.1.9 Distribution	53
2.7 SRSB Prototype	57
2.7.1 Structures of the SRHS Components	57
CHAPTER 3.....	59
3. METHODOLOGY AND MATERIALS.....	59
3.1 Introduction.....	59
3.2 Social Assessment.....	59
3.3 Reconnaissance	60
3.3.1 Site Coordinates	61
3.3.2 SRHS Site Plan	61
3.4 Rainfall Assessment.....	61
3.4.1 Benefiting population.....	62
3.4.1.1 Excess water from SRHS for groundwater recharged	62
3.5 UNITECH Rainforest Habitat (RFH)	63
3.6 A SRHS Model Assembling	73
3.6.1 SRHS Model Construction Process	74
3.6.2 Concepts.....	74
3.6.3 Evaluation	74

CHAPTER 4.....	76
RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.....	76
4.1 Introduction.....	76
4.2 Policy Review	76
4.2.1 Proposed framework for sustainable rainwater harvesting systems in Lae City: a model for Papua New Guinea.....	79
4.2.1.1 The conceptual framework for operation and management of SRHS	80
4.2.1.1.1 Community action group/steering committee for SRHS	82
4.2.1.1.1.1 Land Tenure	82
4.2.1.1.1.2 Global and Regional support, capacity building and funding	83
4.2.1.1.1.3 Regional	84
4.2.1.1.1.4 National Government	84
4.2.1.1.1.5 Local Government Support.....	85
4.2.1.1.1.6 Water Sector in Papua New Guinea.....	86
4.2.1.1.1.7 Environment Management.....	87
4.2.1.1.1.8 Watershed Management.....	88
4.3 Framework content	89
4.4 Background	89
4.4.2 Signs.....	93
4.4.3 Inspections	94
4.4.4 Public Awareness.....	94
4.4.5 Framework evaluation.....	94
4.4.6 Rain data management.....	95
4.4.7 Rain data management proposal SRHS	95
4.4.8 Water quality and quantity	96
4.4.9 Framework for SRHS drinking water management adopted from the World Health Organization guidelines for drinking-water quality volume 1 recommendation 2008.	98
4.4.10 Distribution Management	100
4.4.11 Site consideration for SRHS water distribution	101
Site Mapping, Setting Ground Profile and Pegging Out SRHS Site.....	102
4.4.12 Strategic framework for implementation of SRHS benefitting communities	105
4.4.13 Schedule maintenance.....	116
4.5 Computation of water catchment	117
4.6 Rainfall analysis for Lae City and UNITECH Campus	117
4.7 Analysis of demand and storage design	119
4.8 Rainfall projection	122

4.9 Water Availability.....	123
4.10 Water Demand	123
4.11 Required Storage.....	124
4.12 Elements of the SRHS prototype	127
4.12.1 SRHS storage tank	129
4.12.2 Tank location for SRHS.....	132
4.12.3 Tank materials for SRHS	132
4.12.4 Slow Sand Filtration.....	135
4.12.6 Range of Application of Slow Sand Filters According to Raw Water Quality.....	136
4.12.7 Utilities Room.....	137
4.12.8 Elevation profile.....	139
4.12.9 Site selection	140
4.12.10 Chlorine.....	142
4.13 Prototype.....	144
4.13.1 Prototype Design Features	145
4.13.2 Aesthetics.....	146
4.13.3 Construction and Commissioning SRHS.....	147
4.13.4 Cost of SRHS Prototype	148
4.13.5 The SRSR Model.....	148
Chapter 5.....	152
CONCLUSION.....	152
Chapter 6.....	154
RECOMMENDATION AND FUTURE RESEARCH	154
Chapter 7.....	156
BIBLIOGRAPHY.....	156
8. APPENDICES	161
Map of Proposed SRHS in Lae City- Papua New Guinea.....	162
Appendix C: Gravity Flow Calculations.....	181

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1.1 Conceptual framework SRHS.....	8
Figure 1.2 Study Area of SRHS (with inset photos).....	15
Figure 2.1 1990 to 2012 Mean 22 years monthly rainfall for Papua New Guinea.....	37
Figure 2.2 Map of mean rainfall in Lae	42
Figure 2.3 How water is collected and evaporated from vegetation canopy.....	43
Figure 2.4 The cycle of transpiration.....	43
Figure 2.5 Many different processes that leads to the movement and phase changes in water.....	45
Figure 2.6 Process diagram of a drinking water sustainable rainwater harvesting system.....	47
Figure 2.7 Cross sectional view of the basic design of a community standpipe unit.....	56
Figure 3.1 eXplorist 510 GPS.....	62
Figure 3.2 Percolation pit for groundwater recharged.....	63
Figure 3.3 Site layout plan of the habitat.....	72
Figure 3.4 Vegetation and biodiversity of the rainforest habit.....	73
Figure 4.1 A Policy Conceptual Framework for operation and management for SRHS.....	80
Figure 4.2 Rainwater harvesting contraption at a settlement in Lae (Madang Compound).....	83
Figure 4.3 SRHS site identification report.....	102
Figure 4.4 Identification pegs fixed in position.....	103
Figure 4.5. SRHS Site Topography.....	104
Figure 4.6: Typical Topographic map of Papua New Guinea University of Technology.....	105
Figure 4.7 Average precipitations graphically calculated using Samsamwater – Climate tool on Papua New Guinea University of Technology Lae.....	118
Figure 4.8 Graph showing Papua New Guinea University of Technology campus water consumption pattern.....	119
Figure 4.9 Papua New Guinea University of Technology Lae, location on the rainfall data map.....	120
Figure 4.10 Monthly rainfalls for an average year calculated using Samsamwater – Rainwater harvesting tool for Papua New Guinea University of technology campus Lae.....	122
Figure 4.11 Water availability and water demand throughout the year calculated using Samsamwater – Rainwater harvesting tool for Papua New Guinea University of Technology Campus Lae.....	123
Figure 4.12 Water levels throughout the year in proposed storage reservoir calculated using Samsamwater – Rainwater harvesting tool for Papua New Guinea University of Technology Lae.....	124
Figure 4.13 Elevation profile from proposed storage reservoir to water tower.....	126
Figure 4.14 Plan view of sustainable rain water harvesting system.....	130

Figure 4.15 Section of the sustainable rainwater harvesting concrete storage and catchment surface.....	131
Figure 4.16 Plan view of SRHS storage tank.....	133
Figure 4.17 Section through storage tank.....	134
Figure 4.18 Section through slow sand filter.....	137
Figure 4.19 Plan view of utilities room.....	138
Figure 4.20 Left elevation of utilities room.....	139
Figure 4.21 Elevation profiles of the SRHS showing composite view catchment, storage and utilities room.....	141
Figure 4.22 Calcium Hypochlorite Tablet Feed System.....	143
Figure 4.23 Prototype with basic aesthetic layout.....	144
Figure 4.24 Process diagram for SRHS.....	145
Figure 4.25 Plan View of SRHS model.....	149
Figure 4.26 Right elevation SRHS model.....	150
Figure 4.27 Sustainable Rainwater Harvesting Process Model.....	150
Figure 4.28 Sustainable Rainwater Harvesting Process Model.....	151

LIST OF TABLES

Table 4.1 Global Rainwater Harvesting Policy Review.....	78
Table 4.2 Local Rainwater Harvesting Policy Review.....	79
Table 4.3 Coordinates of the four selected SRHS boundary stations.....	101
Table 4.4 Average precipitations (in mm or liters per m²) for the location Papua New Guinea University of Technology campus Lae.....	118
Table 4.5 Design parameters for SRHS.....	121
Table 4.6 Runoff coefficient for various catchment types.....	122
Table 4.7 Water quality parameters.....	136

ACRONYMS

A	Area of catchment
CGIAR	Consultative Group of International Agriculture Research
Cr	Run off coefficient
ESL	Environment Solution Limited
GPS	Global Positioning System
GHARP	Greater Horn of Africa Rainwater Partnership
IFTA	Insect Farming and Trading Agency
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
IRHA	International Rainwater Harvesting Alliance
IWRM	Integrated Water Resources Management
km ²	Square kilometre
L	Litres
m ²	Square meter
m ³	Cubic meter
MDG	Millennium Development Goal
mg	Milligram
MGD	Million Gallons Per Day
mm	Millimetre
MUS	Multiple Use Water
mwc	Mean Water Column
mWG	Mean Water Gage
NGO	Non-Government Organization
NTU	Nephelometric Turbidity Unit
NWSS	National Water Supply and Sewerage
pH	Potential Hydrogen
PNG	Papua New Guinea
Q	Quantity of rainfall
R	Average rainfall
Re	Reynolds number

RHCCs	Rainwater Harvesting Capacity Centres
RWH	Rainwater Harvesting
SEARNET	Southern and Eastern Africa Rainwater Network
SIDS	Small Islands and Developing State
SRC	Scientific Research Councils
SRHS	Sustainable Rainwater Harvesting System
UNEP-DHI	United Nation Environment Program
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
UNICEF	United Nation Children Emergency Fund
UNITECH	University of Technology
WHO	World Health Organization
WRA	Water Resource Authority
Ws	Water Supply
γ	Friction Factor
3D	Three Dimensions
%	Percent

CHAPTER 1

1. INTRODUCTION

Papua New Guinea (PNG) is the largest country in the Pacific region both by geography and population. It has been estimated to have two third of the population of Pacific Region. It has an estimate of 6.9 to 7 million people which approximately 87% live in rural areas, where access to water and sanitation has been on the decline. Report from Guardian.com (2009) shows that 40% of the population in PNG has sustainable access to improved drinking water, and with sustainable access to improve sanitation range about 45% of the population (Rogers, 2009). According to report of World Bank, PNG is not on track to meet either the millennium goal or its own national development targets of 70% access to water by the year 2030 and 100% access by the year 2050(WorldBank, 2013). From the Progress on Sanitation and Drinking Water 2013 Update WHO UNICEF data on water and sanitation shows that the country is at 19% access to Sanitation and Drinking Water with only 13% access in the rural area. PNG has fallen behind all its neighbours in providing significant access to water and sanitation despite positive economic growth(Unicef, 2014).

PNG has a climate characterized by high temperatures and humidity throughout the year due to the North West Monsoon season from December to March while the South West Monsoon season from May to October. The temperatures are not extreme and in most areas, apart from the high altitudes, have a daily mean temperature of 27°C with little variation. The humidity in the lowland areas varies around 80 percent due to varied topography and location(Climate, 2015). In the mainland a mean annual rainfall ranges from less than 2,000 mm along the coast to more than 8,000 mm in some mountain areas while the island groups to the north and the northeast receive an average rainfall between 3,000 and 7,000 mm/year on areas lying southwest of Fly River. The west of Lae in the Markham valley receives less than 2,000 mm of rain per year(Encyclopedia, 2015). The Port Moresby (National Capital) coastal area receives the least rain with less than 1,000mm/year due to an average monthly temperature that ranges from 26°C (79 degrees Fahrenheit) to 28°C (82 degrees Fahrenheit) throughout the year(FAO, 2015).

PNG has 21 provinces, a National Capital District and its second largest city, Lae City, with coordinates: 6°44'S 147°0'E is known as the Garden City and is the capital of Morobe Province(Encyclopedia, 2012). The average rainfall of Lae City, the garden city, per

year amounts to 3,447 mm measured from the years 2000 to 2012. It is also estimated that the same range of rainfall has continued beyond 2012 to date with minor changes in average rainfall due to climate change. Large volume of rainfall is necessary for sustainable rainwater harvesting as continuous supply depends solely on consistent and frequent rainfall. The city of Lae experiences an average of 20 days of rainfall each month, consistently from January to December. This is thought to be a reliable environment to explore the implementation of strategies for a Sustainable Rainwater Harvesting System (SRHS) in the city of Lae as a model for Papua New Guinea's alternative source of water supply. This will provide an answer to the fourth directive principle of Papua New Guinea's national constitution which is to conserve its natural resources – water resource, by using them to ensure a collective benefit and be replenished for the benefit of future generations (Jim, 2008).

Rain water harvesting within Papua New Guinea communities including Lae city already exists in a smaller scale. As you traverse the streets of Lae small units of rainwater harvesting apparatus from roof gutters to tanks can be observed that catch limited amounts of rainwater for household use (Conservancy, 2015). With the pressing issue on climate change a SRHS can support depleting resources and utilizing what could be a catastrophic event- flood during heavy rains. According to climate experts due to climate change a country experiencing wet season will experience severe scenarios in the future (Morelock, 2015). Rapid drastic changes in weather also affects the temperature and precipitation which have in some cases caused illness and promoted the flooding of bridges, roadways and dams in PNG are attributed by global warming. The country may also be at risk of outbreaks of many diseases such as gastroenteritis, polio, cholera, in the absence of proper facilities for water harvesting. The country's future development is dependent on sustainable water infrastructure and alternate water support systems.

Water PNG is a water provider of the country which over 100 million litres of treated water each day to the residents of the following townships: 1) Alotau, 2) Bereina, 3) Daru, 4) Finschhafen, 5) Kavieng, 6) Kimbe, 7) Kokopo, 8) Kwikila, 9) Kundiawa, 10) Lae, 11) Lorengau, 12) Madang, 13) Maprik, 14) Mt hagen, 15) Mutzing, 16) Popondetta, 17) Rabaul, 18) Wabag and 19) Wewak. Most of the water required to meet each of the mentioned township demands is drawn from the local river, spring and groundwater catchments. In Lae city alone, supply of treated water to Lae and surrounding areas by Water PNG exceeds 30.0 ML each day making it the biggest of Water PNG operation in Papua New Guinea with over

12,000 potential customers. Most of water required to meet Lae City`s demand is bore water drawn from the seven(7) bores located at Taraka (along the perimeter boundary of the Papua New Guinea University of Technology along Independence Drive of Lae(Water, 2015).

The concept behind this research is not to invent new catchment styles but to introduce methodologies and strategies that can harness greater volume of rainwater and distribute it formally and effectively in a self-sustaining way without the use of energy resource or with mechanical operation. The particular focus will be on a suitable community in Lae, where an applicable scaled prototype can be developed and implemented as a pilot project, in the area that will demonstrate the potential of SRHS for replication throughout the country. Therefore, the proposal for a robust sustainable rainwater harvesting network which will benefit the country. This is because the use of fuel that drives surface water distribution system that comes from rivers and groundwater, will contribute to CO₂ emission. This will increase global warming which makes the country more vulnerable to drastic events as a result of climate change. The country`s industrial hub will need to be persuaded to embrace alternatives to decrease pollution and increase alternative quality water supply sources.

1.1 Problem Statement

Rainwater harvesting in Papua New Guinea exist on small scales, however, with the potential effect of climate change, the change in rainfall pattern and the increase uncertainty, it poses a threat to the current rainwater harvesting methods and its sustainability. No documentation has been found on previous studies done on sustainable rainwater harvesting systems in Papua New Guinea.

1.2 Hypothesis and Null Hypothesis

Hypothesis: Based on the rainfall pattern and volume in PNG sustainable rainwater harvesting is a viable alternative to support on shortfall in existing water supply and any potential for water scarcity that may arise.

Null Hypothesis: The rainfall pattern and volume in PNG is not an indication that sustainable rainwater harvesting is a viable alternative to support on shortfall in existing water supply and any potential for water scarcity that may arise.

1.3 Research Objectives

The following objectives give clear outlines of the working principles for implementation of the SRHS and will give strategic direction to the flow of the study.

1. Review existing global, national and local rainwater harvesting and associated policies, and strategies for sustainable rainwater harvesting that will support the needs of the communities
2. Examine the rainfall availability in Lae for sustainability of supply.
3. Assessment of the study area topography where the SHRS model would be feasible.
4. Provide a design model of a sustainable rainwater harvesting system (SRSH) as an alternative water supply infrastructure that is not mechanical/electrically driven in harvesting rainwater.
 - i. Catchment area
 - ii. Rainwater Collection Tank
 - iii. Utilities
 - iv. Network Distribution
5. Develop a scaled prototype for modeling and simulation of SRHS, for potential replication throughout the country.

The term ‘rainwater harvesting’ is usually taken to mean the immediate collection of rainwater running off surfaces upon which it has fallen directly. This definition excludes runoff from land watersheds into streams, rivers, lakes, etc. This project is concerned primarily with the provision of clean drinking water; therefore, the rainwater harvesting proposal mainly seeks to explore rainwater collected from, catchments.(WaterAid, 2013).

1.4 Materials and Methods

The methods used in answering the objectives are both descriptive research and qualitative research. This study of Sustainable Rainwater Harvesting Systems (SRHS) in Lae city: a model for Papua New Guinea is used as a research strategy in order to determine how rainwater can be harvested in a sustainable way for the benefit of water scarce community. In qualifying the descriptive component of the research, it captures the study area that is located on the Papua New Guinea University of Technology (UNITECH), this area is west bound along independence drive in Lae and is access via the furthest entrance gate to UNITECH

in the same direction. On entering through the gate to the right is the rainforest habitat and turning right on to a narrow strip of road adjacent to the habitat leads to the area known as the garden which can be visualized on the UNITECH map (Figure 1.2) later in the study. The rainforest habitat along with the garden area will pivot the study as the main area of the project to locate the catchment area, collection tank, utilities room and distribution point, while the rainforest habitat will simulate the vegetation reserve that will represent a forest canopy that will induce rainfall through transpiration in the water cycle. The community that will benefit from the water captured will be represented by UNITECH campus community, which will see the infusion of captured water within the existing network.

The approach will encompass the sequence of design, data collection procedures and define approaches to data analysis. In that the intention of this study is based on the core research query stated above. Nonetheless there are some proposals to this problem : (a) rainwater harvesting is naturally sustainable as rainfall is the principal source of fresh water for potable uses; (b) rainwater harvesting can support a water-scarce community to get access to clean water; (c) rainwater harvesting requires efficient and clear guidance and operational principles to measure quality and quantity of water; (d) water agencies within government in water-scarce areas will need to implement rainwater harvesting through framework guidelines so that they can control water quality and assure its full potential as an alternative water source, especially in areas deprived of modern water infrastructure; and (e) rainwater harvesting is economically sustainable and practically viable when you examine the simplicity of rainwater harvesting technology in comparison to the cost of harnessing water from other conventional and less environmentally friendly water sources, such as groundwater and surface water sources.

Against that background there are some technical sustainability boundaries linked to the specific and accurate measurements of average precipitation within Lae City that will support water availability throughout the year based on demand and to maintain supply at an optimum levels. The primary concern is to investigate various data collection processes and use analytical tools to accurately supply relevant data. Hence, two main software were employed: Samsamwater-Climate tool and Samsamwater-Rainwater harvesting tool, these software using internet connection and satellite interface produces accurate real time rainfall data and projected analysis. These data are translated in a way to determine water availability

in the specific community, supply levels and storage levels projection. In addition to the projected collection of rainwater for distribution, there will be occasions of greater intensity of rainfall that will show excess water supply, in this proposal the idea is that excess water is to be channelled to replenish depleting groundwater levels in Lae City and when the system is propagated throughout Papua New Guinea the same principles will apply. This study does not go in depth on rainwater harvesting for groundwater replenishment but give an insight on its potential and encourages the practice as a sound environment practice and hope that subsequent studies will look at this area more in depth in the future.

To support the effort of this study and confirm the prospect of sustainable rainwater harvesting systems (SRHS) in Lae City: a model for Papua New Guinea data was collected from other studies including various books, working papers, official and unofficial government documents and studies, various media, surveys and international conference papers and interviews with locals. The writer of this paper had toured some parts of Papua New Guinea and had met with various community personnel to get a feel of persons attitude towards the concept of rainwater harvesting and the possibility for acceptance, and to obtain feedback as to how willing were community members and groups were to get involved in the planning and implementation phases of SRHS. Though these tours were not formally geared with predetermined questionnaires, the interviews and queries were carefully noted to enhance this study. In all the discussions with various community members there were acknowledgement of the great need for proper water supply, and the attitude shows willingness to participate in the process by most residents. It should be noted that the information collected on these tours is not statistically sound, and could not be formally included as data in this study. The materials capture were snapshots to build substance for this report.

1.5 Conceptual Framework

In its broadest sense the conceptual framework is the plan or the guiding principles for the development of the concept Sustainable Rainwater Harvesting system (SRHS) in Lae City: a model for Papua New Guinea. The conceptual framework is developed into four phases: phase one covers data collection processes; phase two covers the design phase of the concept; phase three maintenance and management of the SRHS and phase four is the prototype. Through these four concepts a workable plan will be developed with the potential

to ensure sustainability in rainwater harvesting. This will be discussed in more detail in the following chapters. Sustainable rainwater harvesting is a wide subject with many different connotations of definition, but within the context of the SRHS the meaning is as follows: the collection and storage of rainwater for human use in a manner that preserves and protects the environment and for the preservation of the natural resource (rainwater) for continuous supply now and in the future. Therefore, the conceptual framework serves as guide in accomplishing this research is shown in **(Figure 1.1)** and discussed below.

The conceptual framework is classified in four different phases to show the general structure and the connection sequence of the phases. The phases are as follows: Phase I- data collection, Phase II- Design of SRHS, Phase III- Maintenance and management of SRHS and Phase IV- SRHS Prototype.

1.5.1 Phase I – Data Collection

This phase is primarily concerned with the demand for water within the target group, how rainwater harvesting can address that demand and formalize the use of rainwater to the benefit of the population. Also, the implications of introducing alternative water support system on the local community and the industrial community in line with viable reserve vegetation in Lae City. Rainwater harvesting depends heavily on reserve vegetation areas to encourage precipitation. This kind of vegetation reserve will require local awareness of the need to preserve and managed as a part of the cycle to produce rainwater continuously. Therefore, the strategies employed in the implementation of a SRHS must address these concerns in the way policy frameworks are structured to guide the processes involved, so that the integration of vegetation with the design framework is valuable. The policies must also protect the viability of the existing Water PNG as that body is the primary water supply arm. Water PNG will require support from rainwater harvesting system, to have a wider reach to groups that are currently not served by the formal water structures.

Figure 1.1 Conceptual framework SRHS

On reconnaissance, another area within the SRHS framework that is involved in this phase is the topography of the site, this study will establish parameters in the classification of the site's landscape as this will be necessary to maintain the reduction or the elimination of the use of mechanical operations and greater reliability on gravity distribution. The topography will be done in conjunction with an in depth site investigation to ensure the integrity of the site, such that it can support major water structures without being impacted by ground movements or any other structural forces. The rainwater harvesting zones will require policies that will mandate a scientific approach to the collection of rainwater and the preservation of its support mechanism. In that, rainfall data will be required to be maintained and updated to gauge decisions relating to distribution and the regulation of supply when necessary and influence the design parameters.

Generally phase one covers four primary concept (see Figure 1.1), within the framework: Social assessment which deals specifically with the collection of population data to ascertain the accurate demand for water supply in the area. The other subtopic under social assessment speaks to the impact on the major water provider in Papua New Guinea (Water PNG), this assessment will look at the quantity of water supplied and see whether the community can be adequately supplied by Water PNG or it would benefit from additional water supplied within the context of the SRHS. Also, to determine if the additional water from SRHS would improve the production efficiency and by extension the efficiency of water supplied to the customer. The effective supply of water will require a standard framework within which to operate, therefore, the idea of a policy framework will account for that, as a part of the initial assessment for the SRHS.

In carrying out a social assessment for a SRHS a reconnaissance captures the technical data for the proposed location, such as topography, land measurement, so that GIS and GPS mapping method would be employed to carry out the data collection process. Rainfall assessment is the focal aspect of the SRHS to understand the historical and current data to ensure that when a SRHS is implemented it can be sustainable. The data processing for a SRHS required to be collated and sequence in clear and interpretable information for ease and simplicity in implementation.

1.5.2 Phase II – Design of SRHS

This is the SRHS design phase that will involve four areas: The catchment area, catchment tank, catchment utilities and the network distribution. The basic design of the catchment area is an open area, purpose built with a hard and impervious surface. The catchment area will be deliberately size based on the rainfall data measurement capacity to support the needed quantity of water. The quantity of water demand by the population will be determined by the water demand survey, through interaction with the community and formal data collection process and data analysis procedures, which will be carried out. The storage tank will also be sized based on the demand and the predetermined period of distribution. Since the catchment area will have to be inevitably an open area to the element, it will be susceptible to droppings from flying animals such as birds, other airborne pathogens and airborne impurities. Therefore, the water collected will require treatment to bring it to potable state. Hence, the purpose of the utilities area in the design is to facilitate and secure sanitizing equipment, distribution regulation and operational appurtenances. The distribution network will be modelled based on the data collected from user community topography and pipeline travel profile. Likewise, based on the overall project implementation and water distribution the next phase is conceived.

1.5.3 Phase III – Maintenance and management

This phase deals with the maintenance and management of the SRHS, which will primarily be set out and dealt with extensively in the policy framework. Potable water manufacturing plants are required by international and local policies to be of a predefined hygienic condition at all times and rainwater harvesting plant for potable water is no different. A maintenance and management structure will form part of SRHS operation. This maintenance and management apparatus will encapsulate the whole SRHS. Operations from the maintenance and security of the vegetation reserve areas so that vegetation in the area is not destroyed for individual purposes, the catchment area will also be required to be sealed and polished on a schedule basis, the catchment tank will require cleaning over lengthier schedule, it will overtime accumulate sediments that will reduce the capacity of the tank and compromise water quality. The utilities room will include mechanical devices such as valves, pipes, chlorine chamber and taps that will require more rigid attention and maintenance. The distribution network will also require similar maintenance and management intervention,

more frequently as it will involve expenditure to respond to the required maintenance of valve, pipes and meters that will invariably go bad overtime.

1.5.4 Phase IV –SRHS Prototype

SRHS prototype (Figure 4.23) shows the scaled 3D graphic model, to demonstrate and simulate the actual infrastructure in smaller version. It is necessary to get a general perspective as to how the system will work and how it will basically function overtime. Besides, the prototype will form the basis for funding proposals presentation. The study culminates with the development of a model of a rainwater harvesting system that represent a scaled 3D view of the proposed system, this model is a rectangular shaped structure showing salient features to harvest rainwater. These includes a catchment surface, an inlet canal, a filter compartment, circulation ports within the water process section, storage tank, distribution outlet, tank overflow and cleanout outlet. A feature of this model that might be unique is the rain simulation tray which is also rectangular and is fixed atop the catchment surface and is completed with a water support contraption that releases water using a controlled valve to produce different gauges of rainfall. As a model it required to be constructed from a material that offers ease of manufacture, light weight to permit portability and to be able to bring out as much intricate details as possible, to the furtherance of greater clarity of how the system work. The type of material used to construct the prototype are Poly methyl methacrylate (PMMA) also known as acrylic or acrylic glass as well as by trade names plexiglass, acrylite, lucite and perspex among many others. It is a transparent thermoplastic often used in sheet form as a lightweight or shatter resistant alternative to glass (Encyclopedia, 2016b). Aluminum frames were used to formulate a support into which the system was fixed for structural support. Aluminum is a lightweight, silvery-white metallic element that is ductile and is found chiefly in bauxite, and is a good conductor of electricity. It is the most abundant metal in the earth's crust and is used to make a wide variety of products from can to airplane components (Encyclopedia, 2016a).

1.6 Proposed Study Sites

When selecting the site for sustainable rainwater harvesting system there are some primary considerations in alignment with vegetation reservation for continuity of the hydrologic cycle as follows.

- Rainfall potential by assessment of reserve vegetation, and if it can managed to induce precipitation that will lead to rainfall.
- Supports the demand of the proposed community
- Rainfall capacity supply assessment based on empirical rainfall data
- Topography assessment to ensure that the site is easily accessible and has the necessary clearance to locate the components of a rainwater harvesting system;
- The willingness of the community to facilitate the implementation of such system.
- The potential for full community involvement of all aspects of the process in the long run.

The site selected for this study is the Papua New Guinea University of Technology (UNITECH) campus. It is located 8 km outside Lae City, along Independence Drive in the Morobe Province of Papua New Guinea. The campus occupies a land area of 200 hectares. On this land space also houses the student and staff accommodation. It also has 13 teaching departments and 3 affiliated colleges. The University has a student population of 3000 and a staff population of more than 700 staff members. All of whom are accommodated full time with all amenities provided including campus water supply.

The 200 hectares of land on which the University sits, is situated in a relatively suburban setting, with plenty of green area. In order to provide a comprehensive demonstration of how the SRHS will be supported with adequate and continuous water supply, the rainforest habitat in this setting will simulate the forest reserve that will encourage precipitation. Thus, the proposed site is located next to the forest habitat and alongside the pumping stations of Water PNG. The excess water from the SRHS will support a proposal for ground water recharge to avert groundwater depletion in the near future, as groundwater of 30 ML is pumped every day by water PNG to support the need for water supply in Lae City.

The site location is shown below (**Figure 1.2**), with inserted images to provide more visuals of the location and to convey information of how important the project, Sustainable

Rainwater Harvesting System (SRHS) will support the current environment and the impact it is facing now and in the future. This arrangement will demonstrate how important it is to maintain a balance, to optimize the performance of the hydrologic cycle and provide a continuous pattern of rainfall through evaporation, transpiration, condensation and precipitation.

Figure 1.2 Study Area of SRHS (with inset photos)

1.7 Research Timeline and limitation of the study

The research timeline is two (2) years but the effort of the author of this study was to complete ahead of the schedule time due to other unrelated circumstances that might affect the outcome of the research in the long run. One of the greatest hindrances to doing research on rainfall in Papua New Guinea is getting data from the relevant agencies on the ground. Even if the data is forthcoming verifying the accuracy of the data is another area of serious concern. However, this is not a new phenomenon in Papua New Guinea, as is highlighted by the following: Climatic information, particularly rainfall records are important to many aspects related to water supply and agriculture, such as the assessment of crop performance. While the rainfall recording network in PNG expanded to 330 operating stations by 1970 the total number of stations since has declined. Furthermore, rainfall data also show signs that the quality of records are deteriorating. The earlier records reveal certain incorrect recording techniques reflected in missing data, such as the "Monday effect", where the rainfall of whole weekends would be recorded as a single daily fall on Monday. However, in an analysis of recent rainfall data from six neighbouring stations in the Northern Province the authors, Spooner and McAlpine have noticed further sources of errors which can be explained by the lack of acquaintance with the recording techniques(Spooner and McAlpine, 1986).

As a result the idea of finding alternate data sources underscores the approach of this research, in that to meet the objectives using the internet and climate software was crucial to the effort despite the slow pace of internet development in this part of the world. Having accessed key data online was crucial to the completion of the data collection could be accomplished in scheduled time.

The concept of sustainable rainwater harvesting in Papua New Guinea as a developing country, is a welcoming option, especially with the reality of climate change which threatens the future viability of existing water sources. While there is not an immediate shortage of water sources in PNG, the primary modes of water supply are very expensive and are not far reaching enough to a vast segment of the society. This study "Sustainable Rainwater Harvesting in Lae City, a model for Papua New Guinea", in a timely manner, seeks to explore juxtaposing rainwater harvesting to the current water sources and proposed sustainable rainwater harvesting as a viable and cost effective alternative. Rainwater harvesting is one of the most encouraging choice for providing fresh water in the face of

growing water inadequacy and rising water charges along with mounting demand. Therefore the idea of this study is to propose a model sustainable rainwater harvesting system with a framework of coherent guiding principles that will engender the replication of this system throughout PNG. The thrust of this study is to set the framework in all aspects to limit modifications, except where site investigation dictates that the terrain conditions is prohibitive or the rainfall profile is below the threshold for the establishment of a rainwater harvesting system. The timeline allocated to comprehensively achieve the objectives of this study is on schedule.

CHAPTER 2

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter examines the global perspective of sustainable rainwater harvest as an alternative water resource. A general evaluation of the global water supply system is needed in order to understand the advancement and progress of universal approach to rainwater harvesting, in different countries with almost similar characteristics as Papua New Guinea (PNG), as well as rainwater harvesting practices from a local perspective. Along with the various strategies to build on the traditional approach to rainwater harvesting and make it more efficient by proposing additional plans to allow national government to develop new and contemporary policy guidelines on rainwater harvesting to ensure its sustainability.

2.1 Global Perspective

In spite of increasing support for sustainable rainwater harvesting globally by public agencies, environmental organizations and well-defined industry guidelines; the researchers Fricano and Grass (2014), found a strikingly limited number of municipalities with formal sustainable rainwater harvesting programs and policies. The research looks at the different strategic approach to rainwater harvesting in PNG and realized that there is a grave lack of research and sound guideline to rainwater harvesting in the country. As such, this lack of direction contributes to a myriad of environmental ills and other serious community issues like health problems from poor and inadequate water storage, and hygienic problems among others. The approach is adhoc and mirrors traditional and customary styles by using rusting gutters to runoff in small uncovered containers which is not sustainable. The unsustainability of traditional method is underlined in the fact that rainfall patterns have evolve significantly and so the approach has to be holistic to encapsulate the whole gamut of sustainability, which includes capturing rainwater resource plus caring for the environment so that adequate amount of water is available and some can be preserve for future generation. This can only be achieved through careful research, financial and technical linkages with global entities involve in the support and practice of sustainable rainwater harvesting.

2.1.1`World Bank

The World Bank includes in its global mandate for developing countries, every objective to reduce poverty by supporting the efforts of countries to promote equitable, efficient, and sustainable development. This involve support for the provision of potable water and sanitation facilities, flood control, and water for productive activities in an economically viable, environmentally sustainable, and socially equitable manner. The new approach is designed to help countries achieve these objectives more effectively while sustaining the water environment and the World Bank will support member governments to that end. The World Bank will give priority to countries where water is scarce or where the problems of water allocation, service efficiency, or environmental degradation are serious. In these countries, through its economic and sector work, lending, and participation in international initiatives, the World Bank will promote policy reforms, institutional adaptation and capacity building, environmental protection and restoration, and when requested, cooperation in the management of international water sources. Because of the crucial interdependencies between water and other sectors, the World Bank will incorporate water resource policy and management issues in its country policy dialogues and in the formulation of country assistance strategies where water issues are considered to be most significant.(Prentice, 1998). In PNG the capacity to implement a rainwater harvesting system requires capacity building like most small islands and developing states. Therefore, establishing linkages with the World Bank, whose thrust is to facilitate financial and technical support would benefit PNG, to develop a sustainable rainwater harvesting sector, which is the idea being promoted by this study.

2.1.2 Rainwater Harvesting Capacity Centres

RAIN Foundation encourages governments to establish and support an institutional framework for Rain Water Harvesting (RWH). In order to increase the awareness and adoption of RWH by public as well as private actors, RAIN Foundation and its partners establish Rainwater Harvesting Capacity Centres (RHCCs) in each country under the RAIN Foundation programme, overseeing project implementation, but also coordinating promotion and lobby activities at a national level. One of the aims is the inclusion and recognition of RWH in national water policies. The centres involve and bring together key players within the sector through workshops and more day-to-day consultations about RWH policies, water

source mapping, water quality testing and the like. For programme implementation, RAIN Foundation and the RHCCs identify priority intervention areas at a national level and contract NGO's already working within these regions. The RHCC's and RAIN Foundation train these partnering NGO's in RWH, monitor and evaluate project implementation.

The centres also play a central role in learning and knowledge exchange, systematizing best practices and experiences. User manuals have been developed in English and French, as well as rainwater quality guidelines. Most NGO's have been able to achieve ambitious construction targets despite the remoteness of most of the sites. In-country capacity development has increased the number of trained and experienced NGO's, technicians, masons and trainers in the RWH technology, as well as community-based water committees and households in management of the RWH systems. Extension workers support households and water committees to manage water distribution and payment schemes, and to maintain water quality and hygiene (Nijhof et al., 2010). PNG can benefit from external intervention from these agencies both financially and in capacity building for the implementation of a sustainable rainwater harvesting systems throughout the country. The suggestion is that the PNG government does not have to implement this proposal alone, it has the option of soliciting support from NGO's and supporting groups that are willing to help small Island and developing States in these undertakings.

In an effort to develop an integrated, structured and efficient sustainable rainwater harvesting system in PNG as an alternative water technology, this study has examined several literatures globally that support a well-organized approach to sustainable rain water harvesting systems in countries with similar precipitation characteristics to PNG. Under the heading policies and challenges, the clear implication of Article 26 of the Plan of Implementation of the World Summit for Sustainable Development in 2002 was that Integrated Water Resources Management (IWRM), based on the four Dublin Principles, was seen at the international level as the framework within which countries should seek to organize and manage their water sectors, and the rainwater harvesting sector is a developing sector globally and similar intervention is required, (GWP, 2014). Part of the appeal is that IWRM stresses cross-sector integration not only as a support to development, but as a process and framework that is sensitive to country-specific geographic, historical, cultural, social, and economic conditions, in developing rainwater harvesting implementation strategies. The impetus to embark on a process of integration is rooted in a recognition that existing water

governance arrangements within countries are weak and not capable of addressing the water challenges that they are facing. These challenges include water scarcity, deteriorating water quality, the impact of extreme events, and the provision and maintenance of water services (GWP, 2014). Critical issues identified include supply-driven management, weak or non-existent policy framework, fragmented and subsector approaches to water management, lack of information, inadequate technical competencies, and low levels of investment in the water sector (GWP, 2014). The challenges faced by other countries as highlighted in the report are similar to those in PNG and require the same kind of intervention with coherent policy guidelines. This idea is part of the effort of this research to initiate the concept so that a skeletal can be structured as a framework for future policy development on sustainable rainwater harvesting in the country. The consequences of an adhoc rainwater harvesting practice is that poor management of existing water sources are impeding economic and social development and that these deficiencies are most acute in developing countries. (Cashman *et al.*, 2010).

The converse is that good water sector management makes an important contribution to the goals of sustainable water security, poverty reduction, improved public health, and environmental sustainability. It provides infrastructure that underpins economic development (Jønch-Clausen, 2004). The implication is that IWRM is a political process in which societal, developmental, and ideological factors have to be reconciled, and one that will involve the resolution of conflicts of interests in the water sources at many different levels (Jønch-Clausen, 2004). Implementations are built on three pillars: an enabling environment to sustainable rainwater harvesting policies, strategies, and legislation; an institutional framework that allows the enabling environment to be operationalized; and the establishment of management instruments that allow institutions to do their job and achieved the goal of sustainable development, which at its core is water security that is paralleled with environmentally sound method of harnessing water, using a renewable resources that cannot be depleted and the only source that fit that criterion is sustainable rainwater harvesting (GWP, 2014). Papua New Guinea is not a water scarce society as is confirmed in other references in the study. However, the society has not evolved with environmental changes which is affecting rainfall pattern globally. Consequently, with this lack of adaptation the country runs the risk of a collapse of its water sources if it is severely impacted by changes in rainfall pattern. The study therefore, is concerned with the examination of how involved government is in the water resources management because water resources

management underpins economic development and other societal issues such as health. It must be pointed out that for sustainability of the natural resource, government must be integrated in the process in a significant way to influence the lives of people and touch the life of the most vulnerable, the poor.

In most areas, population is increasing rapidly and the issue of supplying adequate water to meet societal needs and to ensure equity in access to water is one of the most urgent and significant challenges faced by decision-makers. With respect to the physical alternatives to fulfil sustainable management of freshwater, there are two solutions: (a) finding alternate or additional water resources using conventional centralized approaches; or (b) better utilizing the limited amount of water resources available in a more efficient way. To date, much attention has been given to the first option and only limited attention has been given to optimizing water management systems. Among the various alternative technologies to augment freshwater resources, rainwater harvesting and utilization is a decentralized, environmentally sound solution, which can avoid many environmental problems often caused in conventional large-scale projects using centralized approaches. However, some countries have sought to harmonize their water resources with scenario. Like Jamaica which is in the developing phase to employ sustainable rainwater harvesting strategies to augment its water supply quantity. Barbados also has a well-established policy driven rainwater harvesting strategy in place. Bermuda has a long history of rainwater harvesting as the pillar on which their water sector was established(Latham, 1987).

2.1.3 Water Harvesting in the Caribbean

According to the Water Resource Authority Jamaica, Jamaica has a tropical climate with average temperature ranges from 26°C in February to 30°C in August. (WRA, 2011). It is a Caribbean nation with climate and precipitation that, threatens the water resources due to climate change, and rainwater harvesting is a possible response. The island experiences tropical storms and hurricanes frequently during the July to November season. Precipitation can vary both seasonally and spatially. The average annual precipitation from 1881 to 2007 was 1,871 mm. The Blue Mountain area receives over 5,080 mm of annual rain, while the capital city of Kingston receives less than 762 mm. The dry season runs from December through April and coincides with the season of cold fronts(ESL, 2009).According to Marilyn (2012), there are three rainfall-area characterizations in Jamaica: (1) heavy rainfall area (northeast section, Cockpit country (contiguous rainforest in Trelawny), parts of the parishes

of Hanover and Westmoreland), (2) moderate rainfall area (north coast from Port Maria to Negril Point and the central regions of the island), and (3) low rainfall area (south coast between Bull Bay—on the southeast coast in St. Andrew—and Black River, as well as the north coast between Discovery Bay and Montego Bay)

2.1.3.1 Community Rainwater Harvesting Systems in Jamaica

Against that background, community rainwater Harvesting Systems collect rainwater from large concrete or metal catchment area on hillside to catch rainwater and transfer it to a large storage through pipes by letting it flow downhill into the storage tank. Some limitations of community rainwater harvesting systems in Jamaica are that communities are dependent on the amount and frequency of rainfall for their water supply. This is to some extent, unpredictable and many times communities have insufficient water to meet their needs. The communal nature of this system makes regulating water consumption difficult due to the absence of community accountability for the amount of water that each member draws from the system. Other measures to minimize the water supply shortage due to insufficient rainfall are: (1) Communities can increase the size of the catchment area and increase the amount of rainwater harvested, (2) to ensure sufficient amount of water are stored during times of rainfall to meet the community needs during drought by increasing the capacity of the storage tank, (3) to make sure that the rainwater harvesting system can supply sufficient water even on irregular weather patterns by supplementing rainwater harvested with water delivered by truck, and (4) Communities ensure that water is sufficient by establishing mechanisms to ensure that members of the community pay for the quantities of water they consume so as to ensure responsibility and conservation of resources and are billed based on quantity.

This study is similar to the use of concrete or metal catchment run by gravity. However, this study will recommend an arrangement that will not be managed by the community alone. But, an integrated structure between the community and stakeholders and the City administration, as resources regulators, for sustainability, including: ensuring the enforcement of policies that will protect the environment. These guarantee continuous harvesting of rainwater in the area despite the changing of the climate. The Jamaican government currently allocates 0.1% of its total budget to water resources(ESL, 2009).

The UNITECH campus is not the ideal place to bring out in a very practical way some of the lessons intended by this research, because the campus is a captive group and some of

the ills within an unregulated community are not seen. Nonetheless the salient point from this research can be gleaned from the application of sustainable rainwater harvesting on the UNITECH compound and the intention is that some level of tweaking will be applicable to the peripherals but the fundamental tenets will remain constant through the application of rainwater harvesting throughout PNG. Sustainable rainwater harvesting in this study is proposed as supplemental water to conventional water systems and by using UNITECH as the study model the suggestions are to use rainwater harvesting to supplement existing sources to the benefit of the institution by reducing cost and consumption quantity. So that like the Jamaican scenario the proposal is for UNITECH to allocate a percentage of its budget to harvest rainwater as support to existing water and manage it through its current operation, and this scenario can be reflected if rainwater harvesting becomes a part of the PNG water landscape.

2.1.3.2 Barbados experience

In Barbados, the fifteenth most water scarce nation in the world, water availability is directly influenced by rainfall (80% of which is lost via runoff and evapotranspiration); rainfall is also expected to decline due to climate change, and saline intrusion of wells is anticipated to increase due to sea-level rise and low rainfall (Emmanuel and Spence, 2009). Seawater desalination using renewable energy has been recommended for some small Island State and may be critical to survival when combined with other adaptation methods such as RWH. The attributes of the Barbados scenario in relation to this research is that no matter the level water scarcity in a country or region sustainable rainwater harvesting is the most viable alternative to support conventional water sources. Though the situation in PNG is not as crucial at this time the potential for extreme water scarcity is looming based on the pattern of climate change as pointed out in earlier discussions.

Barbados, an island of 430 km² located at 13°10' N and 59°30' W is the most easterly of the Caribbean islands; with a population of approximately 277,000 it is one of the most densely populated countries in the world. It is recognized that Barbados is a water scarce country and that committed work is necessary to ensure the sustainable management of this resource. Equitable allocation and ongoing monitoring of the fresh water resources of Barbados are necessary to ensure its optimal utilization, conservation and protection (Barbados, 2000).

One of the main approaches in Barbados to address this issue of water scarcity is the utilization of sustainable rainwater harvesting using different means to achieve this. A policy framework with specific, clear and coherent principles was developed. But rain data validation was also necessary to start the process.

2.1.3.2.1 Rainfall Data – Barbados Case

The real challenge to the implementation of a sustainable rain water harvesting solution is the determination of the amount of storage required during the wet season so as to meet the demand for water during the annual low rainfall period (dry season) of approximately five months. It is therefore, necessary to have reliable rainfall data over a period of at least 25 to 30 years to support a prediction model. Thanks to a network of approximately 50 rain gauges located on sugar cane farms. Barbados has some 150 years of rainfall data based on twice daily readings by dedicated farmers at 6.00am and 6.00pm. This data was analysed to provide average monthly precipitation levels; used in predictive models that perform a monthly water balance for various rainfalls scenarios. Therefore, an understanding of the pattern of rainfall in Barbados was the guiding light that pivoted the various mode of rainwater harvesting that is employed, to mitigate any major impact from water scarcity(Hutchinson, 2010).Examples of the relevant and specific guidelines to rainwater and fresh water resource management policies in Barbados are:

- Obtaining and analyzing information and maintaining up-to-date records of the total available fresh water resources of Barbados
- Establishment of a system whereby data related to water resources including rainfall collection, extraction, rainfall levels etc., is collected, collated and stored effectively. This information should then contribute to the development of future water use and management policies and programs.
- Phasing out of the importation and use of devices that do not comply with international water conservation standards.
- Conducting public education and awareness building programs to inform about the importance of employing water conservation practices in daily life.
- Continued support for the policy requiring new dwellings of a particular size to construct rain water catchment and storage tanks, including the possible revision of the policy to include existing dwellings and new dwellings of smaller sizes.

- Establishment and implementation of appropriate pricing and financial concessions to encourage the above and other water conservation policies, and to render these policies economically attractive.
- Rationalization of competing demands for water use in order to arrange them in an appropriate list bearing in mind the limited supplies available.
- Maintaining human, financial and technical commitments towards ensuring a firm foundation for managing water use in a sustainable manner as well as for devising methods for augmenting the fresh water supply appropriately such as sustainable rainwater harvesting;
- Development, implementation and enforcement of comprehensive and appropriate sustainable rainwater harvesting and water resources management regulations and legislation.
- Conducting research into the effects of the climate change phenomena including the specific effects on fresh water resources and the influence of expected rainfall reduction and increased evapo-transpiration due to temperature rise. This research will include an exploration of the most appropriate procedures to prepare for climate change and mitigate its adverse effects.
- Enhancing public awareness and educational campaigns to inform about the necessity and benefits of reducing water use.
- Conducting a cross-sectoral examination of policies which impact on sustainable rainwater harvesting and other fresh water resources in Barbados including, in particular, policies for human survival and sustainability of the economy

2.1.3.3 Bermuda experience

The island of Bermuda is located 917 km east of the North American coast. The island is 30 km long, with a width ranging from 1.5 to 3 km. The total area is 53.1 km². Bermuda is known for using roof tops and large catchments for practically all its potable water use, in all approximately 2.7 meters are caught annually, use began as far back as 1628. The sizes of tanks and systems construction are prescribed by law and a continuous program of discussion about quantity and quality of water, maintenance of sustainable water supply and future demands are maintained (Latham, 1987).

Like Barbados, Bermuda has a well-developed policy framework for sustainable rainwater harvesting with its long history of dependence on rainwater for practically all its potable water needs. In Bermuda the development rainwater harvesting is well documented throughout the ages so that the establishment of strong framework for rainwater harvesting was not difficult. Some documentation show systems being develop by various groups in the early days of development of the country. Rainwater was also collected from artificial catchments created by removing hillside soil and sealing rock surface with mortar. Water from large artificial catchments provided significant quantities of water, e.g., an estimated 13.6 million L/yr. from a catchment developed by the British military installation, and 45.5 million L/yr. from a catchment serving a major hotel (Thomas, 1980).

Roof water systems with adequate storage were not systematically encouraged until the 20th century. Prior to the adaptation of a strong policy framework for rainwater harvesting and the current public health regulation in 1951, storage capacities of 1,400 to 22000L were common (previous public health regulation required up to 6,800 liters per occupant, although 13,000 liters per occupant were recommended), compared with typical storage today of 68,000 liters (UNEP International Environmental Technology Centre -Osaka/Shiga, 2001)

The rainwater harvesting program in Bermuda was established under strict policy guidelines and regulations for the protection of individual house hold from the collection and storage of poor quality water that will harm their health and these regulations were absolutely necessary to ensure that optimum public health is sustained at all times. In developing a Rainwater Harvesting System in Papua New Guinea requires no less carefulness, whereby a policy framework and fair enforceable regulations for the protection of individual households from water borne disease and the public from the outbreak of epidemic from poorly regulated water harvesting and storage.

The elevation of most of the land mass is less than 30 m above sea level, rising to a maximum of less than 100 m. The average annual rainfall is 1,470 mm. A unique feature of Bermuda roofs is the wedge-shaped limestone “glides” which have been laid to form sloping gutters, diverting rainwater into vertical leaders and then into storage tanks. Most systems use rainwater storage tanks under buildings to supply piped indoor water. Storage tanks have reinforced concrete floors and roofs, and the walls are constructed of mortar-filled concrete blocks with an interior mortar application approximately 1.5 cm thick. Rainwater utilization systems in Bermuda are regulated by a Public Health Act which requires that catchments be

whitewashed by white latex paint; the paint must be free from metals that might leach into water supplies. Owners must also keep catchments, tanks, gutters, pipes, vents, and screens in good repair. Roofs are commonly repainted every two to three years and storage tanks must be cleaned at least once every six year (Waller, 1982).

The ideas gleaned from these countries with similar rainfall and other characteristics as Papua New Guinea will be utilize in this study as a base point in dovetailing features with local perspective to consolidate a viable approach to the implementation, management and operation of alternative water resources. While Papua New Guinea is an Island state like the countries mentioned the development process in PNG is at different stage from those countries so that adaptation of rainwater harvesting with regulation will not catch on as quickly hence it behoves the country to start now. A lot more effort will have to be placed on public education, cultural matters, land issues and a better framework for policy enforcement though there are structural dissimilarities this study is promoting the various sequence that must be followed to make sustainable rainwater harvesting in Papua New Guinea achievable in the shortest possible time give the changeable nature of climate change that will at some point affect the conventional water sources on which the country now depends.

2.1.4 Global examples transferable to Papua New Guinea (PNG)

The global concept is similar to the effort of this study in that it is well established that the rainwater harvesting practices in PNG are unsustainable in its current status and the framework developed through this study will create that pathway to sustainable rainwater harvesting system in PNG. The idea of having a policy framework to guide the implementation of sustainable rainwater harvesting is not a new model globally. But this model of a policy driven SRHS has not been tried in PNG and though it has been done successfully in Barbados and Bermuda which are Island states much smaller in size but have similar characteristics to PNG. The historical background, the culture, social scenarios, and environmental issues might vary in some ways. However, there are lessons learnt from these countries' utilization of sustainable rainwater harvesting technologies for a number of years and these technologies are transferable to the PNG settings.

2.2 Local Perspective

As a result, any set of coherent principles set out to guide sustainable rainwater harvesting will integrate the management of the various component of the water cycle regime, throughout the country. In this sense, it is crucial to preserve the environment in which a Sustainable rainwater harvesting system SRHS will be established. The fact is that, the environmental awareness as a nation has not permeated the society which has consequences that leave PNG with a myriad of environmental concerns including: the loss of the nation's forests and global warming which in parts are effects from elsewhere, but primarily due to bad environmental practices by humans. With only 801 cu km of renewable water resources, global warming and the resulting rise in sea level are a threat to Papua New Guinea's coastal vegetation and water supply mainly (Encyclopedia, 2015).

The connection between potable water demand and environmental responsibilities as a nation is important to recognize in the broader context of sustainable water management. To this end, local government and the water sector groups are faced with an anticipated carbon reduction task and they will be required over the coming decades, to manage potable water demand and encourage good environmental practices. The conventional water supply mechanism which seems to be the quickest and easiest way to address water demand puts unnecessary strain on the balance within the ecosystem. Sustainable rainwater harvesting represents the opposite and is an integrated water management approach. However, to limit contributions to climate change and continuous rainwater supply, it is paramount to protect and conserve the natural vegetation infrastructure that induces rainfall.

The Department of Environment and Conservation in Papua New Guinea, noted that maintenance of the qualitative and quantitative values of the natural water resources, of Papua New Guinea as a key element in the sustainable development of the country's resources. They are a natural asset that supports life of the population and the economy of the region. Thus, protecting and conserving the existing water quality and quantity is one of the major thrust, which is a critical aspects for the sustainable development of the country and for ultimately improving the quality of life for the people of Papua New Guineans. However, due to pressing issues on climate change, this water resource is under threat, and will require strong policy to ensure that the protection and conservation of this resource is managed in an effective, efficient and in a sustainable manner. The PNG Government's overall Development Policies for sustainable water support is under increasing pressure from the

large number of resource development projects that are being implemented throughout the country (Environment, 2009).

The unique geography of the many islands in the Pacific Ocean exposes them to the potential for water scarcity and water related natural hazards compounded by the effects of climate change and variability, including sea level rise. Papua New Guinea (PNG) is among the Pacific island countries that are struggling to build the capacity to address many challenges, such as developing coherent policy frameworks and integrated approaches to managing scarce freshwater resources. Other weakness within the PNG Scenario is the rapid increase in population, the slow pace of infrastructure and the fragmentation of community development. This setup among other cultural, land and social issues present a unique situation that involves a distinctive approach to the development of a policy framework on sustainable rainwater harvesting in configuration to the PNG environment. Thus, the framework is being developed in this study consultation with the local communities in Lae PNG which is the key to primary investigation and information gleaning which can ultimately be dovetailed with experiences in Jamaica Barbados and Bermuda among others to formulate a cogent framework for PNG, on sustainable rainwater harvesting. The character of this framework is its infiniteness and hence, the framework being develop by this study is the foundation for future and continuous revision on sustainable rainwater harvesting in PNG. This is so because the environment in which we harvest rainwater is very dynamic due to climate change and the evolution of human conduct towards the environment (UNESCO, 2012).

2.2.1 Brief background to Water PNG

To understand the water landscape in PNG it is useful to be clear about Water PNG, the premier water supply entity in the country which tap into conventional water sources such as groundwater like wells and bores and surface water like rivers and a lakes and supply communities with potable water as its primary function, especially urban communities. Water PNG role in the country as a leading water entity would be the most suitable body through which an alternate source (rainwater harvesting) of water should be established. The study throughout the discussions seeks to find out the most suitable approach. However, it is well recognized that most of the rural areas in PNG is not reached by Water PNG. There is no formal water set up, for various reasons, which include difficult terrains, distance of

communities, size of communities, lack of supporting infrastructure such as road etc. The appeal of sustainable rainwater harvesting in these situations is to establish sustainable rainwater harvesting systems within these communities and manage them from within the communities with support from Water PNG and other relevant sectors.

2.2.1.1 Water PNG establishment and mandate

The establishment of Water PNG arose from a strong recommendation from studies undertaken in the seventies and eighties on the provision of Water Supply and Sewerage services in urban and rural areas of PNG. The recommendations to rationalize the planning, operations and management of water supply and sanitation services were based on the following revelations:

- The water sector was highly fragmented resulting in lack of national planning, poor management and coordination.
- The urban water supply and sewerage services poorly managed resulting gross inefficiencies and poor service delivery to consumers.
- Compliance in meeting specified Drinking Water Quality Standards under Public Health Regulations was poor.
- Cost recovery was non-existent with operation and maintenance funded from the National Budget.
- There was no authority to regulate Service Standards provided by operators of private Water Supply and Sewerage services.

The first National Water Supply and Sewerage Acts were passed in the National Parliament in December 1982 culminating actions by successive governments in the rationalization of management of urban water supply and sewerage services in PNG.

In the framework arrangement of Water PNG as it relates to cost recovery a tariff arrangement was built in the process. Where, a regulated sum was applied for water charges to define the responsibilities of the public to pay for a good and to set a platform for the continuity of the entity. In a way that it can maintain water infrastructure and install new ones. By so doing it builds a viable business organization that is relevant and viable at all times. This arrangement is done with the customer being equipped with a meter system on premises that is read on a monthly basis and through an existing account at the water

company. It is updated each month and the company reads the meter and the subject pays the sum calculated based on water consumption. Each water entity establishes its own model to fit the circumstances of that country for example water rates are calculated in line with the inflation levels of the country at the moment in time and the regulatory arm within the organization ensures that these arrangements are maintained at all times, through internal enforcement strategies. The regulatory policies within Water PNG are operated and enforced in two directions the company is expected to meet a guaranteed standard in terms supply good quality water to the public in a timely manner. Failing which the regulating arm of the state within the overall water sector of the country will act on behalf of the community to make sure those standards are met. If they are not, to ensure that individual customers are compensated after the requisite processes are followed. On the part of the customer his responsibility is to ensure that his bills are paid as calculated on a timely basis for the volume of water consumed. If this is not done the water company reserves the right to enforce the regulation accordingly following step by step processes set out in the enforcement policy. At this stage the company will send a reminder through the swiftest means of the day with a minimum timeline of compliance for example being 7 working days. If the customer does not comply then the company follow up with the first stage of water denial, whereby the valve forward of the meter from the public water line is locked, pending compliance. If within the prescribed time line set out in the procedure for the first stage of action and if compliance is not forthcoming, then the second stage of enforcement is activated. The meter is taken out at the customers expense upon payment, the supply disconnected and bunged, until payment compliance are achieved and this enforcement procedures are applicable to all customers engaged to the water company. As long as the state maintains its oversight and the water sector remains vigilant corrupt practices will be kept at a minimum and all involve shall be treated the water sector fairly.

The Act created the National Water Supply and Sewerage Board which operated under the Department of Works and Supply from 1982 to 1986. In 1985 a review of the Board

- Operation was undertaken recommending amendments to the 1982 Act to establish a commercial statutory authority with independent Board of Directors.

- The successful passage of the (NWSS-Act 1986) **National Water Supply and Sewerage Act 1986** in the National Parliament saw establishment of Water PNG as an independent water authority.
- Board of Directors and is self-financing. Membership and appointment of Directors are provided for in the Act.
- Water PNG commenced operations on 1 January 1987 managing water supply and sewerage systems in Lae, Madang, Mt. Hagen, Wewak, Kundiawa, Kimbe and Arawa.
- The Head Office is located in Port Moresby.

2.2.1.2 Water Use Regulations in PNG

Owing to the complexities of water harnessing, quality and distribution to a wide population, the responsibilities with the water sector is huge and far reaching. As a result, it requires very specific and stringent regulations. Therefore, sustainable rainwater harvesting as an imminent water source in PNG, will require guidance through those regulatory structures of Water PNG. For the wider benefit of the local communities, that is most vulnerable to water scarcity in this country.

Water PNG is the sole regulating arm of water source and supply in Papua New Guinea. In view of that, any new or evolving water source such as sustainable rainwater harvesting throughout PNG must be the subject of Water PNG's regulatory framework under which it currently operates to supply water to the public, as water source it is not practical for SRHS to invent a new policy within which to operate as this will be counterproductive to the thrust of Water PNG over the years to eliminate fragmentation. So that SRHS water should be incorporated in the Water PNG water sources structure as an alternative source. This is to facilitate a clear understanding that a regulatory philosophy is vital to the success and acceptance of a SRHS at any level.

2.2.1.3 Water PNG Roles

Water PNG is the principal advisory arm of the national government of Papua New Guinea that advises the government on water resources development in the country. Water PNG coordinates the planning, design and construction of water supply as well as sewerage infrastructure; and manages them and is also charged with the provision of water supply to

the country. Water PNG was established to rationalize the provision of water supply and sanitation in the urban areas of PNG. Prior to its establishment the water sector was seriously fragmented resulting poor service delivery and no cost recovery. The corporate governance framework and policy is formulated by the Board of Directors and Management Team in accordance with the functions stipulated in the National Water Supply and Sewerage Act 1986 (NWSS Act) and Government.

Goals

- To perform in accordance with industry benchmarks.
 - To ensure provision of safe and sustainable water and sanitation services on equitable basis.
 - To work and deliver services in line with national development priorities and objectives.
 - To ensure financial and commercial sustainability and meeting community service objectives.
 - To promote excellence in customer service always.
 - To be environmental conscious in all aspects of planning, construction and operations.
 - To promote a clean, safe, secure, peaceful and decent work environment.
 - To cultivate and promote a dynamic, healthy, competent, professional and progressive workforce.
 - PNG First: In all we do, we will put our people and country interest first.
 - Think Globally, Act Locally: We will strive to adopt relevant international best practice, where practical to achieve our Corporate Goals.
 - Strength and Diversity: We will value diversity as our source of strength to forming a committed, cohesive and dynamic team.
- Ownership: We will take ownership of our actions and decisions and will make it happen.
- Kina Wise: We will value money as a limited resource that needs to be spent wisely at all times.

The ideology of Papua New Guinea water sector synchronizes with the idea to have an alternative water source. In that the goals and objectives are supportive of the thought of new and innovative sources of water (WaterPNG, 2015). Thus, Sustainable Rainwater Harvesting in Lae City – A Model for Papua New Guinea will be a welcome concept and will get the support envisage in this policy framework, formal rainwater harvesting may seem to

be a far away from taking root in PNG but the lessons from countries with similar characteristics are saying otherwise.

Other lessons learned from analysing the countries with scenario and other similar countries is relevant to other small Island States like Papua New Guinea, and especially those expected to experience similar decreases in precipitation due to anthropogenic climate change. For example, a recent study shows that the dry season will become drier and the wet season will become wetter in the Seychelles; the increase in dry spells that resulted in drought conditions in 1999 is likely to occur under future climate change (Payet and Agricole, 2006). This trend in the Seychelles may call for more RWH to store water for later use during the dry spells. The Pacific and even Papua New Guinea likely to experience the same erratic climate variation according to the South Pacific Applied Geoscience Community (SOPAC, 2004) El Niño events have the potential to cause catastrophic droughts in the Pacific region such as in Papua New Guinea and other Melanesian islands as well as the Federated States of Micronesia and the Marshall Islands.

In light of those climate change dynamism that threaten small Island and developing state like PNG the introduction of achieving the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) remains a daunting challenge for many countries in the face of small state budgets and limited donor support. This Policy Research Brief highlights the contribution of a low-cost water supply strategy to a number of MDGs. It also discusses innovative financing schemes to scale up the implementation of such strategies. The relationship between Rainwater Harvesting and the MDGs in which many of halving the proportion of the population without sustainable access to safe drinking water by 2015 is challenging in several respects. The geography of developing countries low population density, low degree of urbanization, long periods of drought and so on imposes economic barriers to the traditional water-grid provision and calls for alternative solutions for water supply. Half way to the deadline for meeting the MDGs, in countries such as Mozambique, Papua New Guinea, Somalia and Afghanistan, only 42, 40, 29 and 20 per cent of the population, respectively, has access to water from an improved source. In many areas, rainwater harvesting (RWH) has been a successful coping strategy against water scarcity, especially in periods of drought. Cisterns are the most popular RWH storage technology. Runoff rainwater is diverted from the rooftops of houses via gutters (made of bamboo, plastic or metal) and stored in a closed ferrocement tank or jar with a capacity of 5–50m³. In Brazil's semi-arid region, a rooftop area of

40m² can capture and store 16,000 litres of clean water for a single household. This is enough to satisfy the drinking water demand of a family of five during the long months of drought. In that area it costs about US\$800 to build a cistern. Besides its direct contribution to attaining sustainable access to safe drinking water, RWH also makes some significant contributions to achieving other MDG's. International Policy research brief February 2010 No.12 (Lehmann *et al.*, 2010).

Therefore, the International Policy research brief 2010 No. 12 have applied significant to the predictions relating to drought and water source to serve the population effectively. As such this study on sustainable rainwater harvesting is fitting and can be applied in the ways proposed in the research for propagation throughout PNG in a systematic way and contribute significantly to the achievement of the MDGs as described above. To achieve success in this regard requires some international capacity and as such PNG like other similar countries such as Barbados has embraced international protocols in going about this as listed below.

- PNG ratified the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change UNFCCC in 1993 and further ratified the Kyoto Protocol in 2002.
- The Office of Climate Change and Development are the national focal point for the UNFCCC and the Kyoto Protocol.
- The OCCD is the coordinating body for all climate change related policies and actions in Papua New Guinea.
- The OCCD is tasked with ensuring Papua New Guinea follows a path of climate-compatible growth: that its economy develops while simultaneously mitigating greenhouse gas emissions and reducing vulnerability to climate change related risk.
- To this end the Office works closely with a range of stakeholders from Government, NGOs, development agencies and the private sector entities, local communities and the wider public.

2.3 Rainwater Harvesting and Climate Change in PNG

In Papua New Guinea encouraging rainwater harvesting requires empowering the practice through policies and providing incentives through partnership and capacity building, environmental management and sound policy driven operational strategies. This can be accomplished by examining and adapting best practices from countries with a track record of achievement in policy driven sustainable rainwater harvesting like Bermuda, Barbados and

other state with similar characteristics. Local government and water sector agencies need to address cultural and social concerns example, land and public education relating to public health issues in the current unsustainable ways of harvesting rainwater, by stipulating water quality and contamination relating to the existing practices. This study is initiating that in the proposed, implementation of SRHS in PNG specific and related sustainable rainwater harvesting policies must be developed to address these on an ongoing basis, the framework from this study can form the bases. Policies should establish acceptable uses for rainwater as a supplemental source to the Water PNG, especially in areas where the terrain or other inhibiting factors prevent Water PNG from supplying. The corresponding treatment requirements such as disinfection of rainwater for use must be standardized, also research and policies should serve as a workable tool to encourage the simplification of sustainable rainwater harvesting process flow and associated cost savings that could broaden the use of rainwater harvesting throughout Papua New Guinea safely.

The chart below (**Figure 2.1**) shows the mean historical temperature and rainfall for Papua New Guinea during the period 1990 to 2012 (World et al., 2015). The image was set out using an average of 22-year mean rainfall data for Papua New Guinea (from 1990 to 2012) to illustrate the changes of precipitation over years. The assumption was made that the fluctuation is due to climate change. This assumption can be more accurately verified to show the link to the impact of climate change. However, such verification is beyond this study due to the lack of requisite modelling software to simulate such. This study seeks to further the discussion concerning climate-change impacts for small island developing states like Papua New Guinea. Climate-change adaptation and mitigation strategies must be developed to cope with changes such as ever-changing precipitation patterns, increasing evapotranspiration, and expanding saline intrusion into coastal aquifers and wells. While it is necessary to study all climate-change mitigation measures, this study focuses on Papua New Guinea to examine the utility of rainwater harvesting (SRHS).

**AVERAGE MONTHLY TEMPERATURE AND RAINFALL
FOR PAPUA NEW GUINEA FROM 1990-2012**

Figure 2.1 1990 to 2012 Mean 22 years monthly rainfall for Papua New Guinea
Source: (Worldbank and Group, 2016)

Through various water demand and deficit scenarios, questions are answered regarding (a) how much rainwater can be harvested on the island given present and future precipitation patterns and (b) how much can RWH realistically curb water-supply deficits now and in the future. Water resources are directly linked to many other considerations, including infrastructure, energy, agriculture, and the overall economy. Exploring the above-mentioned questions can help to facilitate more effective policy decisions for water resources given predictions for rainfall. It is hoped that this study spurs a broader thinking on what concrete actions PNG should take to prepare for the water-resource impacts of climate change (Cohen and Forrester, 2013).

Rainwater harvesting in response to climate extremes enhances the resilience of human society. There is global evidence showing the utility of constructing RWH systems to mitigate aridity and drought conditions. For example, in the Negev Desert, decentralized RWH in micro catchments yields 95,000 L of water per hectare per year (Pandey, 2003). Climate change presents great challenges for PNG. As a Pacific Island State it is one of the generally low-lying and coastal nations, it is the largest Island State in the Pacific (more than 450,000 km²). This nation is among the world most vulnerable nations to climate change. Ninety percent of small island states are in the tropics and many are members of the Alliance of Small Island States. The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) has labelled small islands and developing states as the nation's most vulnerable to climate

change. The United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change lists the following characteristics of SIDS that render them particularly at risk (UNFCCC, 2005):

- Limited natural resources, with many heavily stressed from human activities.
- Coastal concentration of population, socioeconomic activities, and infrastructure
- High susceptibility to frequent and increasingly intense tropical cyclones and associated storm surges, and droughts, tsunamis, and volcanic eruptions
- Dependence on freshwater resources that are highly sensitive to sea-level changes
- Relative isolation and significant distance to major markets
- High sensitivity to external shocks
- High population densities (and in some cases high population growth rates)
- Inadequate infrastructure
- Limited physical size, which eliminates some adaptation options to climate change
- Insufficient financial, technical, and institutional capacities.

These factors challenge the developmental prospects of small island states by serving as a barrier to accessing foreign markets and developing domestic products and services. The susceptibility to cyclones and droughts prevents some industries such as agriculture and water-dependent manufacturing from operating at optimum levels. Limited size creates intense competition for land use (residential, agricultural, industrial, institutional, and conservational uses), which makes land-intensive adaptive measures to climate change difficult. This study focuses on PNG to highlight the problems encountered by small island states and devotes particular attention to a broad outlook of climate change and water resources in this Pacific nation. Included is an overview of climate and precipitation in Papua New Guinea, threats to water resources due to climate change, and rainwater harvesting as a possible response. The objective is to answer key questions regarding the potential of rainwater harvesting as a strategy to mitigate water shortages due to climate change.

The carbon reductions associated with rainwater harvesting are admittedly not on the order of magnitude required to significantly impact climate change adversely at the moment. However, the connection between potable water use and water demand is important to recognize in the broader context of sustainable water management. It is critical to assess

water use not only from a resource availability and environmental protection standpoint, but also with the aim of creating policies to improve the overall sustainability which is a critical component.

As local government and water sector groups are faced with the anticipated CO₂ reductions that will be required over the coming decades, decreased potable water demand and good environmental practices, represent a valuable treasure, the conventional water supply mechanism and the quickest and easiest way to address this demand on the conventional system is through sustainable rainwater harvesting. Rainwater harvesting represent an integrated water management approach that can not only limit contributions to climate change, but also protect and conserve limited water resources, in addition, developing resiliency in Papua New Guinea to the uncertain effects of climate change. Critical to achieving this reduction in contribution to climate change is a well-developed policy driven sustainable rainwater harvesting system (Kloss and Robb, 2008).

Rainwater harvesting has always been collected as a low volume high quality source of water throughout the ages, but since the nineteenth century its use in industrialized countries has received less attention than more technically oriented centralized water sources. However, in recent times, the prohibitive increased cost and other climate change and environmental issues relevant, to supplying treated water, to especially remote and rural areas. This has proven to be quite challenging for small islands and developing states like PNG from a centralized source. Pumping from deep wells has meant that serious consideration to rainwater collection in a sustainable way. Sustainability though not a new occurrence, but will require guiding principles to achieve continuous water supply while at the same time, being mindful of the effect of climate change and the preservation of the environment. As a water source the major advantage of sustainable rainwater harvesting systems are:

- In most areas, rainfall water quality is excellent.
- The concept is simple and thus they are easily built and maintained.
- The ability to operate independently of outside systems is useful in hard to reach areas.

2.4 Ground water recharged potential of rainwater in Lae City

Water PNG collects 30 million liters daily to support the needs of Lae city and its surrounding community's sources from groundwater located at the grounds of The Papua New Guinea University of Technology (UNITECH) with seven (7) pumping stations (Betasolo et al., 2014) in a study found that the long term effect of water withdrawal may cause a gradual settling of land that may in its worst case creates the underlying soil supports to be vulnerable that may cause a sinking called subsidence. The continuous drawdown of groundwater without proper recharge will be detrimental to the health of groundwater as well as sustainable supply of drinking water to the city. UNITECH runs a recharge to the groundwater supply by rainwater harvesting in small quantities such as plastic tanks that are connected to the gutters in most of the UNITECH residential houses. A more comprehensive measure is necessary to protect the depletion of groundwater in the long run. With this scenario alternative supply such as rainwater harvesting in larger scale other than tanks from gutters needs to be explored throughout the areas of PNG where groundwater is extracted and rainfall pattern is optimum and this study has alluded groundwater recharge in a cursorily as it is not the main focus of the study.

2.5 Rainfall in Papua New Guinea (PNG)

According to McAlpine et al., (1983), Papua New Guinea is one of the wettest regions of the earth. Over most of its surface mean annual rainfall lies between 2000 and 4000 mm and is most reliable. No rainfall station record has a mean of less than 950 mm and areas having annual falls lower than 1 500 mm are quite small and isolated. The national capital, Port Moresby, lies in the driest part of the country. In contrast, significant areas have mean annual falls above 4000 mm, and the highest mean annual point precipitation reaches nearly 10 000 mm. Most rainfall regimes exhibit some seasonality in their monthly distributions, although the variation is not so much between dry and wet as between wet and very wet. Such consistently high rainfall patterns directly or indirectly controls much of Papua New Guinea's physical form, its biological resources and human activities. Heavy rainfall regimes are reflected in a physiographical manner in the dense stream and river network that dissects much of the country and in the occurrence of many large seasonally flooded plains such as those that abut the Sepik, Fly and Ramu rivers (McAlpine et al., 1983).

2.5.1 Rainfall in Lae City

Lae City is situated 7° south of the Equator and 147° east. It is a coastal town hence it is close to sea level in altitude. Annual rainfall is typical around 4000 mm to 6000 mm per annum although there are wide fluctuations from year to year. The national rainfall conditions are a result of effect of east trade North West monsoon airflow together with the strong influence of processes due to local geographical conditions. Hence, most of the country annual rainfall distribution has a very wet summer and a less wet winter season. However, in Lae the location of nearby high mountain ranges and the prevailing wind direction result in greater rainfall during May to September period, with typical 400 mm per month. This reverse seasonality of rainfall distribution is the case for many of the highest rainfall areas of Papua New Guinea. Rainstorm can be very severe with peaks of sustained and very high intensity over periods of many minutes (Harris and Milner, 2007)

Figure 2.2 Map of mean rainfall in Lae

Source: (McAlpine et al., 1983)

2.5.2 Reserve Vegetation for sustainable rainwater supply in Lae City

Reserve vegetation are a real asset to Lae City to maintain the good quality rainfall it now produces, providing covering for watershed, shade, habitat for fauna, and purification of the air. Such reserve vegetation have a significant positive impact on the environment through the enhancement of, seasonal colour to plants and trees and contribute positively to the environment; they aid climatic control, and are part of ecological processes. As result, it will require careful management to maintain the integrity of reserve untouched vegetation in

Lae City. In the study this will be exemplified using the rainforest habitat that is located on the Papua New Guinea University of Technology campus which is part of the study area. In developing sustainable rainwater harvesting policy framework it is of essence to incorporate clear approaches to the management of reserve vegetation.

Much of the rain falling on a forest landscape will first impact the canopy vegetation. Some will eventually drip to the ground and some will be evaporated from the vegetation back to the atmosphere as shown in **Figure 2.3**. This evaporative loss is referred to as interception loss. The process is illustrated within **Figure 2.4**. The percentage of rainfall intercepted and evaporated by the forest canopy varies but in countries like the United States of America it ranges from about 12%-48% of rainfall depending on the climate, tree type, and canopy structure(Korhnak, 2012).

Figure 2.3 How water is collected and evaporated from vegetation canopy
 Source:(Korhnak, 2012)

Figure 2.4The cycle of transpiration (Korhnak, 2012)

2.5.3 Sustainable Rainwater Harvesting and the Hydrologic Cycle

2.5.3.1 Hydrologic Cycle

The Hydrologic Cycle recycles the earth's valuable water supply. The sun is the energy that powers this remarkable process. Its energy in the form of light, and heat causes water to evaporate from oceans, rivers, lakes and even puddles. Warm air currents rise from the earth's surface and lift this water vapour into the atmosphere (Prentice, 1998).

Many processes work together to keep Earth's water moving in a cycle. There are five processes at work in the hydrologic cycle: condensation, precipitation, infiltration, runoff, and evapotranspiration. These occur simultaneously and, except for precipitation, continuously. Water vapour condenses to form clouds, which result in precipitation when the conditions are suitable. Precipitation falls to the surface and infiltrates the soil or flows to the ocean as runoff. Surface water (e.g., lakes, streams, oceans, etc.), evaporates, returning moisture to the atmosphere, while vegetation return water to the atmosphere by transpiration.

The distribution of precipitation falling on the ground surface can be modified by the presence of vegetation. Vegetation in general, changes this distribution because of the fact that it intercepts some the falling rain. How much is intercepted is a function of the branching structure and leaf density of the vegetation. Some of the water that is intercepted never makes it to the ground surface. Instead, through transpiration and evaporation from the vegetation surface it goes directly back to the atmosphere. A portion of the intercepted water can travel from the leaves to the branches and then flow down to the ground via the plant's stem. This phenomenon is called stem flow (Prentice, 1998). The study looked at as an alternative to the depletion of other naturally occurring water resources. Such as groundwater, springs etc. To contextualize SRHS and its relevance to the location proposed a clear understanding of the hydrologic cycle will help. The hydrologic cycle provides a pattern of how rainfall is created through evaporation, transpiration, condensation and precipitation as shown below in **Figure 2.5** (Encyclopedia, 2012).

Figure 2.5 Many different processes that leads to the movement and phase changes in water(Encyclopedia, 2016c).

The hydrologic cycle begins when the sun heats water in the oceans, lakes, or streams. The heated water evaporates and turns into water vapour and enters the air. Water can also enter the air when plants breathe in a process known as transpiration. An average tree can transpire hundreds of gallons of water into the air every day. Condensation is the process through which water vapor in the air turns into a liquid and forms clouds. Rain drops often form when water vapor comes in contact with dust in the air. The particle of dust moves through the air, slowly gathering more water vapor molecules around it. Eventually, a raindrop will have formed around the dust particle. The next step in the hydrologic cycle is precipitation in which water from clouds falls back to the earth as rain. Water precipitates out of clouds when the air temperature drops. The drop in air temperature may occur when air moves up the side of a mountain or when a mass of cold air comes in contact with the mass of warm air. Once the rain hits the earth's surface, rainwater harvesting is possible. The rain can either become surface water or groundwater, or it can evaporate back into the air. Surface water is any water found on the surface of the earth, including creeks, rivers, lakes, and oceans. Groundwater is water which sinks down into the earth and forms underground reservoirs known as aquifers. Eventually, the rain water evaporates back into the air and the hydrologic cycle continues. (Encyclopedia, 2012).

2.6 Principle of a sustainable rainwater harvesting system design model

Rooftop model rainwater harvesting system is the most common in countries that are engaged in the practice and it is encouraged along the vein that individual homes take responsibilities for its installation and operation. However, it requires some amount of technical know-how and guidance to guarantee the out of its operation and the safeguarding of household and community health. In this context it seeks to provide a source of water for all purpose such as toilet flushing, cooking, washing, hygiene and rainwater is treated well for drinking purpose.

The amount of rainwater collected is contingent on the rooftop area, the size of the tank and the rainfall at that place. The existing roof is used of to collect rainwater. Since rainwater is pure as it falls from the sky it is necessary that the roof be kept clean for it to remain pure when it is collected. This means the roof will need to be cleared and cleaned daily during the rainy season in the area. This ought to be done carefully using an appropriate length ladder set at the correct angle when mounting, and sweep with a broom. Leaves falling from the roof will cause blockage in the gutters and pipes. The leaves can also cause discoloration of roof and bad odour if allowed to decompose. Thus, roofs must be regularly cleaned of all leaves, dust, bird stools using a broom. Water should only be used if necessary as most times a dry sweeping with a broom will be enough. On washing any droppings from roof the first flush apparatus shall be open prevent filth going into the filter and storage.

Gutters are crucial to the collection of rainwater from a sloping roof and transferring it to a storage tank and the same level of care to roof must be applied to gutters, gutters should also be inspected for leaks and any visible defect that will affect the flow of water in the rainy season. The gutters are strapped to the soffit edge of the roof ,the straps hold the gutter to the wall tightly fixed in place and a slope not exceeding 1:20 to permit water to flow in one direction towards the downpipe that allow water to go in the storage tank. Down pipes are vertically arranged to bring water from the rainwater gutters down to tank. Downpipes should be securely fixed to the wall to prevent sagging due buoyancy from gushing water.

The first flush has a control valve to allow the first little quantity of rainwater to be collected separately. This first water has greater amount of the impurities collected on the roof in dry time. A necessary thing to remember with the first flush system is that it must always be kept in the close position and never left open. It will only be open when the rain is

done and flow out all dirty water after which the clean out adaptor will be closed. A filter can basically be made from gravel, sand and mesh it should be designed in configuration to the tank inlet and fixed in place to filter water entering storage. The main purpose of this filter is to keep rainwater in the storage tank clean, by removing impurities and any organic material such as leaves.

The rainwater storage tank collects rainwater and stores it for future usage whether for potable such as drinking purposes or non-potable such as flushing of toilets etc. The storage tank can be made of various materials such as plastic, concrete or metal, the type of material used depends on the circumstances within the local for example in an area near the sea or in a toxic environment a metal tank would not be ideal but a plastic would be more lasting as its rate of deterioration in that environment is at a slower rate. The tank can be made above the ground and it can also be made underground however, it is more expensive to make underground tanks because of the extensive earthworks that has to be done and there is no certainty of the ground condition in most cases and if the ground is rocky that can also add to the cost making it even more costly, it is best to build storage tank above ground in light of those factors. A storage tank must be fully covered and sealed by covering the tank prevent mosquitos, dust and the growth of algae on the walls of the storage tank. During dry season thorough checks must be carried out and any defects found on the tank must be corrected before the rainy season.

Generally, rainwater harvesting (RWH) is a simple technique that offers many benefits. It can be done very low-tech, cost effective and is applicable at large scale and small -scale with general and available expertise or knowledge; The most common technique in urban areas (besides storm water management) is rooftop rainwater harvesting however, for sustainability large scale communal systems are utilized in many parts of the world: rainwater is collected on the roof and transported with gutters to a storage reservoir and in large scale communal systems through pipes or purpose designed inlet canal, where it provides water at the point of consumption, distribution or is used for groundwater recharge (Betasolo et al., 2014). Collected rainwater can supplement other water sources when they become scarce, low quality or water charges become prohibitive. It also provides a good alternative and replacement in times of drought or when the water table drops and wells go dry. The

technology is flexible and adaptable to a very wide variety of conditions. It is used in the richest and the poorest societies, as well as in the wettest and the driest regions.

2.6.1 Basic Design model of a sustainable rainwater harvesting system

The basic design models of a sustainable rainwater harvesting system include 6 different components and are:

1. Rainfall
2. A catchment area or roof surface to collect rainwater.
3. Delivery systems to transport the water from the collection surface to the storage reservoir.
4. Storage reservoirs or tanks to store the water until it are used.
5. An extraction device or distribution methods (depending on the location of the
6. Tank and filtration or disinfectant device in the case the collected water is used for drinking purposes but does not require purification for groundwater recharge.

The diagram below in **Figure 2.6** illustrates the process flow model showing components of a sustainable rainwater harvesting system, as designed for treating rainwater captured for drinking purposes.

Figure 2.6 Process diagram of a drinking water sustainable rainwater harvesting system

Source: (Thomas and Martinson, 2007)

2.6.1.1 Rainfall

The rainfall pattern over the year plays a key role in determining whether RWH is a viable water supply system. Tropical climate with short (one to four months) dry seasons and

multiple high intensity rainstorms provide the most suitable conditions for water harvesting. In addition, rainwater harvesting may also be valuable in wet tropical climates, where the water quantity of surface water may vary greatly throughout the year. As a general rule, rainfall should be over 50 mm/month for at least half a year or 300 mm/year (unless other sources are extremely scarce) to make RWH environmentally feasible (Thomas and Martinson, 2007).

2.6.1.2 Catchment Area

To be suitable the catchment surface should be made of some hard material that does not absorb the rain or pollute the run-off. Thus, tiles, metal sheets and most plastics are suitable, while grass and palm- leaf roofs are generally not suitable (Thomas and Martinson, 2007).

2.6.1.3 Conveyance System- Filter/Separation

The delivery system from catchment usually consists of a conveyance surface sloping towards an inlet canal and into the storage tank. The inlet canal is used to transport rainwater from the sloping surface to the storage container. The sloping surface can be constructed from a wide variety of materials (e.g. fiber glass, concrete, metal sheets) and the shape can vary depending the location (rectangular or circular). The conveyance surface is usually integrated into an existing sloping site, modified sloping site or a man-made sloping site. This integrated sloping surface catches the water as it falls from the rain and the water sheet flows into the inlet canal and into the storage vessel.

Debris, dirt, dust and droppings from birds will be collected on the surface of the catchment or other collection area. This will cause contamination of the water and the quality will be reduced. Communal RWH systems therefore incorporate a slow sand filter system as part of the treatment process before distribution of the water, so that pathogenic bacteria laden water does not enter the distribution system to the community. The sanitization process is also complimented by an integrated chlorine device which helps the water to reach potable standard for public consumption.

2.6.1.4 Storage tanks

There are almost unlimited options for storing rainwater. Common receptacles used for very small scale water storage in developing countries include plastic bowls and buckets, jerry cans, clay or ceramic jars, cement jars, old oil drums, empty food containers, etc. For storing larger quantities of water, the system will usually require a tank above or below ground. These can vary in size from a cubic metre (1000 litres) up to hundreds of cubic metres for large projects. Domestic systems volumes are typically up to a maximum of 20 or 30 cubic metres. Surface tanks are most common for roof collection.

Sustainable rainwater harvesting system storage tanks represent the biggest capital investment element of a communal sustainable rainwater harvesting system. It therefore usually requires the most careful design – to provide optimal storage capacity base on demand verification and proportionate structural strength, while keeping it cost effective. A communal system or school tank, of course very much dependent on the local pattern of rain throughout the year. SRHS storage tank will be square-shaped or rectangular for ease and simplicity in construction and cost effectiveness.

There are basically two ways locating storage tanks: surface and subsurface, Surface tanks are most common for catchment collection as it provides a more workable arrangement in day to day operation maintenance and access to the water for use. Materials for surface tanks include metal, wood, plastic; fiberglass, brick, inter-locking blocks, rubble-stone blocks, Ferro cement and reinforced concrete, the standard design for SRHS tanks will be from reinforced concrete for durability, structural integrity and sustainability especially in natural disasters such as hurricanes and earthquakes phenomena to which PNG are susceptible.

The material and design for the walls of sub-surface tanks must be able to resist the sub soil that is weighty and cohesive and have great water retention characteristics, and will exert fracturing pressures and soil water pressures from outside when the tank is empty. Tree roots can damage the structure below ground. Careful location of the tank is therefore important. Keeping it partly above the ground level and largely above the groundwater table will prevent problems with rising groundwater tables and passing trucks, which may damage the construction below the surface. A sub-surface tank requires a water-lifting device which adds to all aspect of the cost, hence, not cost effective for a SRHS principle. Some of the devices are pump or bucket-rope system. To prevent contamination of the stored water, safe water lifting device and regular maintenance and cleaning are important.

2.6.1.5 Sizing Storage Tank

There are a number of different methods used for sizing the storage tank. These methods vary in complexity and sophistication depends on the vastness of the community to be supplied. Some are readily carried out by relatively inexperienced, first-time practitioners, while others require computer software and trained engineers who understand how to use this software. The storage requirement will also be determined by a number of interrelated factors, which include: local rainfall data and weather patterns, size of catchment surface, run off coefficient (depending on catchment surface material and slope) and user numbers and consumption demand pattern.

2.6.1.6 Filtering

The best water source is one that doesn't need treatment. Proper care on rainwater collection can produce a relatively clean water supply. Keeping animals away from catchment surface, ensuring that rubbish is not thrown on components of SRHS, will guarantee limited treatment requirements.

In addition, attention to risk of bacteriological pollution from the faeces of flying and crawling animals such as birds, lizards, etc. can minimize the contamination of the water. A Sustainable Rainwater Harvesting Surface must be kept as clean as possible. However, the impact of flying and crawling animals' defecation is inevitable on a SRHS catchment surface that is exposed to such element. Therefore, a slow sand filtration process is necessary as a part of treatment of rainwater harvested on the SRHS catchment.

SRHS treatment process using Slow Sand Filters

Slow sand filtration provides a simple but highly effective and considerably cheap tool that can contribute to a sustainable water management system. Slow sand filters have an advantage over rapid sand filters in that they produce micro-biologically "clean" water which should not require disinfection to inactivate any bacteria, although the addition of a disinfectant to provide a residual for the distribution system is still advisable. (WHO, 2009)

A slow sand filter is classified in the category of gravity filters. In slow filtration fine sand is used, and the designed rate of downward flow of water under treatment that normally lies between 0.1 and 0.4 m³/h per square meter of surface. Unless the water to be treated is of

exceptional turbidity, a filter of this type may run for weeks or even months without cleaning. In rainwater harvesting the potential for turbidity condition of the water is remote and the need for a filter system that requires aggressive maintenance would not be cost effective. As such, rainwater will need a system that can capture suspended solids and colloidal matter that are deposited on the very top of the slow sand filter bed, from which they can be removed by scraping off the surface layer to a depth of one to two centimetres. This infrequent operation may be carried out by unskilled labourers using hand tools (Hisman and Wood, 1974)

2.6.1.7 Disinfecting

All water supplies should be disinfected. This is aimed both at inactivating remaining bacteria before distribution and providing a residual disinfectant to inactivate bacteria introduced by any subsequent entry of contaminated water during storage or distribution. At present, the principal disinfectant used worldwide is chlorine; although alternatives are being increasingly investigated and process such as ozonation are becoming more common.

Chlorine is generally the disinfectant of choice as it is reasonably efficient, cheap and easy to handle. In all but the smallest water treatment plants, chlorine is added to water as either in aqueous solution (calcium hypochlorite or sodium hypochlorite) or chlorine gas. Smaller supplies may use tablets of hypochlorite.

The time taken for different types of microbes to be killed varies widely. In general, amoebic cysts are very resistant and require most exposure. Bacteria, including free-living *Vibrio cholerae* are rapidly inactivated by free chlorine under normal conditions. For example, a chlorine residual of 2mg/l after 30 minutes is required to kill harmful pathogens including amoebic cysts *chistosomiasiscercariae*. Thus, it is important to ensure that adequate contact time is available before water enters a distribution system or is collected for use (WHO, 1978).

2.6.1.8 Treatment

Rainwater itself is of excellent quality, only surpassed by distilled water – it has very little contamination, even in urban or industrial areas, so it is clear and soft. Contaminants can however be introduced into the system after the water has fallen onto a surface (Thomas and Martinson, 2007). Firstly, there is the issue of bacteriological water quality. Rainwater can become contaminated by pathogenic bacteria (e.g. from animal or human faeces) entering the

tank from the catchment area. It is advised that the catchment surface always be kept very clean. Rainwater tanks should be designed to protect the water from contamination by leaves, dust, insects, vermin, and other industrial or agricultural pollutants. Tanks should be sited away from trees, with good fitting lids and kept in good condition. Incoming water should be filtered or screened, or allowed to settle to take out foreign matter. In addition, in large scale communal rainwater harvesting a more comprehensive and thorough treatment process is required which will require the integration of a slow sand filter and a chlorination device along with a standard pattern of quality testing(Gur and Spuhler, 2015).

Common sources of rainwater contamination

- Dirt and faeces (mainly from birds and small animals) on the catchment surface.
- Leaf debris and organic material washed into the tank.
- Animals, insects and birds that have drowned in the water.
- Breeding mosquitoes.
- Dirty storage containers when tank is not adequately covered etc.

A certain degree of microbiological and chemical contamination of catchment run-off is inevitable. It will, however, generally not cause any health problems if the catchment and conveyance system and storage are properly maintained and regularly cleaned and inspected. To prevent breeding mosquitoes it is important that any openings in the tank are fully screened. In addition, proper coarse filter devices are a must prior to water entering storage. Also the positioning of the distribution outlet device is important. Since particles in the tank settle at the bottom, the distribution outlet device should be positioned at least 15 cm above the floor level of the tank. For drinking water it is advisable to place the distribution outlet device about 50 cm above the tank bottom. Concrete and galvanized iron sheet function best as a catchment surface, due to their relative smoothness and the sterilizing effect of the concrete and metal when they are heated by the sun. The poor performance of organic material catchment would seem to preclude them from use for rainwater harvesting systems; however, organic catchments have been employed with varying levels of success (See Figure 4.6). The water is usually used for secondary purposes but can be used as drinking water(Worm and Hattum, 2006).

2.6.19 Distribution

The distribution of rainwater from a sustainable rainwater harvesting system can be a very tricky exercise in Papua New Guinea because of the construction characteristics of the housing stock. That makes it difficult to develop a conventionally designed network system with lateral to individual properties. Base on the general experiences in the local communities and settlements, the delivery of water services to individual household indeed will be a challenging exercise. This is due to the inadequacy of the housing stock where most houses are constructed from untreated and unprocessed forest materials such trees and leaves and are constructed using traditional techniques such as weaves, plaits and fixing with ropes and twigs and cannot accommodate a modern plumbing outfit and potable water infrastructure . As certified with studies done by(Habitat for Humanity International, 2009) That the majority of PNG's population lives in rural communities and settlements based on traditional village housing structures and is dependent on subsistence farming, supplemented by cash cropping. Less than 15% of the population lives in urban areas. In urban areas, housing in squatter settlements is overcrowded and makeshift — generally not places in which families can live in peace and dignity, with women and children protected from domestic violence. In the squatter settlements it is reported to be common to find between 5 and 11 people sharing a single small rented room without even basic facilities.

Standpipe: To mitigate this problem of people not having proper access to potable water because of their living circumstances and ensure that sustainable rainwater harvesting systems benefits all equitably. The installation of public standpipe is the answer, where the housing stock is inadequate for in unit water supply systems. Public standpipes can have one or more taps. Single-tap and double-tap standpipes are the most common types in rural areas and settlements. They are made of brickwork, masonry or concrete, or use wooden poles and similar materials. The design should be done in close consultation with the users (especially women) in order to arrive at an ergonomically optimal solution. Standpipes may have platforms at different levels, making it easy for adults and children to use them with containers of different sizes. A cross sectional view of the basic design of a community standpipe unit is shown below in **Figure 2.7**. The standpipes can also be used for cattle watering and/or washing and/or bathing facilities may be constructed nearby. The design and often also the construction are best done in consultation and with participation of the user households, i.e. both men and women. Public taps drawing from a sustainable rainwater harvesting system represent an alternative method of water distribution.

Figure 2.7 Cross sectional view of the basic design of a community standpipe unit.

Source:(Smet and Wijk, 2002).

Each standpipe should be situated at a suitable point within the community area in order to limit the distance the water users have to go to collect their water. The walking distance for the most distant user of a standpipe should, whenever possible, be limited to 200 m; in sparsely populated rural areas 500 m may be acceptable. The required discharge capacity of a standpipe normally is about 14-18 litres/minute at each outlet. A single-tap standpipe should preferably be used by not more than 40-70 people; a multiple-tap standpipe may provide a reasonable service for up to 250-300 persons; in no case should the number of users' dependent on one standpipe exceed 500. Public standpipes can operate at a low pressure. Distribution systems that serve only standpipes may therefore use low pressure piping, whereas the pipes for distribution systems with house connections generally have to be of a higher pressure class.

Water collected at a public standpipe will have to be carried home in a container (bucket, jerry can, vessel, pot, etc.). This means that the water that was safe at the moment of drawing may no longer be so at the moment it is used in the house. Water consumption from standpipes generally is not higher than 20-30 litres per person per day. This consumption

increases when other facilities (e.g. for washing/bathing) are added to reduce the amount of water women and children have to carry home. Water use for other purposes than drinking and cooking is likely to be curtailed when the water has to be fetched from a standpipe. Yard and house connections will usually encourage a more generous water use for personal hygiene and cleaning purposes.

Wastage of standpipe water: Wastage of water from standpipes can be a serious problem, especially when users' fail to turn off the taps. Furthermore, poor drainage of spilled water may cause stagnant pools of dirty water with the associated health hazards. It is also not uncommon for the taps to be damaged by the users and pilferage sometimes occurs. These problems occur particularly when designs do not meet the user requirements, i.e. there has not been adequate consultation with the users (women and men) and/or there are no clear management arrangements. One way to cope with these problems is through payment for water consumed, which is a fair and effective way of water demand management. Often, those selling water are women, as they are chosen for their reliability and trustworthiness, their need to be present for work within their own neighbourhood and their suitability as hygiene promoters with other women and children.

In spite of their shortcomings, group connections and public standpipes are really the only practical options for water distribution at minimum cost to a large number of people who cannot afford the much higher costs of house or yard connections. In fact, housing is frequently not suitably constructed to allow the installation of internal plumbing. It would often be impossible for a small community to obtain the substantial capital for a water distribution system with house connections. Also, the costs of adequate disposal of the considerable amounts of wastewater generated by a house connected water supply service would place an additional heavy financial burden on the community. Consequently, public standpipes have to be provided and the principal concern should be to lessen their inherent shortcomings as much as possible. To achieve sustainability of this type of service, the management at the public standpipe level needs special attention in terms of organization, operation and maintenance cost recovery (Trifunovic, 2012).

The overall objective of the proposed policy framework for sustainable rainwater harvesting Program for the country is to: Contribute to the utilization of a more achievable approach to the continuous supply of water to the wider PNG population in a sustainable way. Also, conservation of water resources of Papua New Guinea through adoption of

sustainable water management and conservation technologies due to the potential for debilitating consequences because of climate change and the effect of human conduct towards the environment.

The anticipated outcome of the policy framework is: Capacity for implementation of rainwater harvesting for household and commercial purposes, strengthened and support existing water strategies and develop incentive that can eventually mainstreamed into national development strategies and policies. The Policy will focused on creating the framework in such a way that the national government will invest in SRHS across the country, with emphasis on communities that are significantly water-stressed communities; where investment in conventional water augmentation measures are not practical for widespread adoption in the short to medium-term. Water-stressed communities that already have deeply rooted rainwater harvesting traditions will also be targeted to strengthen those traditional techniques and improve the potential for harvesting better quality and greater quantity of water in a sustainable way , but with emphasis on adoption of best practices.

2.7 SRSH Prototype

Integrating the various components graphically of the sustainable rainwater harvesting system to formulate into one composite and functioning mechanism will constitute the SRHS prototype. This study represents a 3D model of the SRHS as a simulation synopsis of the great potential of a “Sustainable Rainwater Harvesting System (SRHS) in Lae City: a Model for Papua New Guinea”.

2.7.1 Structures of the SRHS Components

The specific design will feature a 15° sloping catchment surface that will capture rainwater and serve as a conveyance to sheet flow rainwater to the inlet canal to the storage tank. The first storage tank which is connected to the slow sand filter unit that will filter water through to the second storage tank and then through pipe travel to utility room which house the chlorination device for final sanitization of water then to distribution network.

The collection of rainwater and its subsequent processing and distribution in a sustainable way as a water source has a bright future. This paper has reviewed previous study of its application in a sustainable way. However, many research work done on sustainable rainwater harvesting has suffered because most work has been done in isolation from others,

often similar endeavours. Nevertheless, recently renewed emphasis is being put on the topic by researchers. The attributes of this study is to articulate an integrated approach to a policy driven sustainable rainwater harvesting systems in: Lae City – a model for Papua New Guinea, where all stakeholders at all levels have an input with the end product being action and continuous quality water supply in sufficient quantity(Latham, 1987).

CHAPTER 3

3. METHODOLOGY AND MATERIALS

3.1 Introduction

Based on the conceptual framework for this study a definition of the methodologies involved in this study was established, the methodologies to achieve this paper were primarily investigations to delve into the sample community with a view of finding out what are the water needs, deficiencies and to highlight how rainwater harvesting can fix some of these deficits as a model. Data analysis using rainwater harvesting and climate software were also utilized to determine rainfall pattern using realistic and accurate rain data to confirm the practicality of the proposed idea.

The idea was to locate an area that presented the ideal set of scenarios for a sustainable rainwater harvesting systems (SRHS) in Lae City: a model for Papua New Guinea. Such scenarios would set the stage to develop the requisite data for this research, and at the same time, within proximity to a community to help with an understanding of the community aspect of rainwater harvesting as it is linked to rainwater harvesting site, reserved vegetation in this scenario the rainforest habitat and how these different components can be managed successfully, in an integrated process to ensure continuous supply of water to the designated population. These include the overall study site that is the Papua New Guinea University of Technology (UNITECH).

3.2 Social Assessment

The research approach for this assignment was greatly dependent upon resources available in Lae, Papua New Guinea that can be utilized for the provision of sustainable rainwater harvesting. Online data and few other literature types were employed to understand and review the global methodologies and materials used elsewhere for the development of sustainability in rainwater harvesting. In this study professionals were consulted for advice on various social construct within communities in PNG, areas of rainwater harvesting, archival data, field research, and of great value were the random interviews with the residents around Lae and PNG to get a feel of the surroundings and what will be the potential reception to rainwater harvesting. These interactions created an opportunity to understand the context of the study more clearly from a community perspective and the dynamics that would influence

the effort of this project. A strategy that would eventually fine tune the design of the methodologies in line with the framework of the study, deliberating aspects on of this study with many people who live in Lae helped to direct the research work as, well as enhancing an understanding of the issues involved in the work. The most significant part of the research was interrelating with the citizens of Lae and surrounding communities and ascertaining their needs. This aspect was done in the preliminary stage of developing the concept of sustainable rainwater harvesting system in Lae to model for PNG, and the idea was to see what traction such an introduction gathers. In addition to be clear on the wants and capabilities of the people, prior to creating the method for constructing a rainwater collection system that was feasible for PNG communities. This venture was only able to get ahead by embracing a participatory method thereby actively involving residents in all stages of the work, from initially describing the project, to developing an appropriate solution to implementing the fabrication and construction of a model.

3.3 Reconnaissance

The concept of the Sustainable Rainwater Harvesting System study area being on the University campus is to propose a strategy to harvest rainwater on the compound and infuse in the existing distribution network at UNITECH to augment the current water supplied by Water PNG, by augmenting water supply to the university by 30%. As well as to simulate a model rainwater harvesting system that can be propagated throughout the country. The site selection for SRHS will simulate three characteristics of the effort of this study and they are system location, benefitting population (Papua New Guinea University of Technology), and excess water for groundwater recharged.

Data was collected on the area known as The Garden using basic surveying techniques to establish boundary points and define measurements. The collection of data relative to the formation of rainforest habitat which served as reserve vegetation was included. However, since its inception there has not been any chronicled documentation of the occurrences throughout the 23 years of its existence. Vital data was also gathered by going into a sample community. The admin department and the estate department which together supplied data on water consumption pattern, campus population and how the water system work on campus, were vital in the study.

3.3.1 Site Coordinates

Establishment of the site coordinates was done using an instrument called Explorist 510 GPS as shown in Figure 3.1. The Explorist 510 is used also in establishing the coordinates as in the use of Google maps.

Figure 3.1eXplorist 510 GPS.
Source:(eXplorist, 2016)

3.3.2 SRHS Site Plan

Identification of the site was done by carrying out a reconnaissance, where the site was mapped to set location points using the eXplorist 510 GPS units to accurately map the location points for SRHS. This edition allows mapping for 2D or 3D viewing angles and elevations. It includes and provides cartographic orientation and topographic measurements in almost any location for the catchment surface, storage tanks and utilities room.

3.4 Rainfall Assessment

The rainforest habitat forms a key reference point in the development of the idea, with its rich and almost virgin and dense vegetation; it serves to simulate reservation to induce continuous rainfall to support the SRHS. Therefore, the site for sustainable rainwater harvesting system was deliberately and strategically aligned

with the vegetation reservation to primarily simulate the transpiration and precipitation elements of the hydrologic cycle.

3.4.1 Benefiting population

The concept of the Sustainable Rainwater Harvesting System study area being on the University campus is to propose a strategy to harvest rainwater on the compound and infuse in the existing distribution network at UNITECH to augment the current water supplied by Water PNG, thereby offsetting in part water supply to the university by 30%. As well as to simulate a model rainwater harvesting system that can be propagated throughout the country.

The site selection for SRHS will simulate three characteristics of the effort of this study:

3.4.1.1 Excess water from SRHS for groundwater recharged

A study was carried out by (Betasolo *et al.*, 2014) on the use and management of groundwater in Marobe Province found that the seven pumping stations of the Water PNG supplying Lae City's needs on water including UNITECH were drawing down significant volume. Those seven pumping stations were just outside the fence of the Papua New Guinea University of Technology. The study also confirms that the continuous drawdown without proper recharge will be detrimental to the health of the groundwater.

The location of the SRHS is within proximity to Water PNG extraction bores along the Papua New Guinea University of Technology (UNITECH) and there are no recharge facilities to replenish water extracted from the aquifer at these points. Therefore, part of the proposal base on the predicted rainfall quantity is that there will be excess water after the 30% infusion in the UNITECH system. This excess water will be used to recharge groundwater through designed percolation pits as shown below (**Figure 3.2**).

Figure 3.2 Percolation pit for groundwater recharged

Source: (Slidshare, 2016).

3.5 UNITECH Rainforest Habitat (RFH)

In 1993 a United Nation (UN) International Convention on, Environmental Protection and the Conservation of the Forest or Biodiversity, was held in Rio de Generio Brazil. It was out this convention that the national government of Papua New Guinea called for national institutions and citizen to respond to this most urgent call as it was the era ushering in the dawn of climate change. It was also this call that gave rise to the original idea and timings for the Papua New Guinea University of Technology to get involved and embraced in aspects of environmental issues and programs as behooved by the government. At the same time there were rationalizations of tertiary institutions status in the country. As a result, UNITECH, Vudal based Agriculture Faculty who are former UNITECH staff was taken to form a new University. UNITECH and University of Papua New Guinea (UPNG) took over scientific institutions and government colleges to increase their portfolio and prevent the university from increasing its base.

Following the events that unfolded around issues relating to the environment, in June 1993 UNITECH Pro. Vice in charge of Planning & Development Dr. James Kaiulo put together a paper outlining the concept of the Rainforest Habitat. The nature and scope of the Rainforest Habitat and the Environmental Research & Management Center (ERMC) was outlined in the same paper. When the University Council approved the paper, funders were sought, and UNITECH approach the Department of Environment and Conservation (DEC) to put together a submission to United Nation Development Program (UNDP) to fund it under the country's Institutional Capacity Building component of the Biodiversity Conservation initiative. The development of a rainforest habitat within the context of the UNITECH campus had three major thrust: environmental awareness especially for urban dwellers in PNG and particularly school children to learn about the importance of conservation of plants and animals in their country, tourism and restoration land.

The man who led the operation team for the execution of the various aspect of the development phase of the rainforest habitat was Mr Peter Clark who was an employee at the Insect Farming and Trading Agency (IFTA) at Bulolo and had built up a sizable animal collection of insect and animals at his residence. During his tenure at the IFTA he got to know Mosley Moramora (then Vice Chancellor) and Roger Dixon (Chairman of the Board) at UNITECH who were interested in taking on ownership of IFTA (it was then owned by the government owned Livestock Development Corporation) - as they felt that it would help connect UNITECH more to the average villager (there were 2,000 villagers working there at the time) and also because it offered a sustainable forest based business as an alternative to logging. In that encounter there were discussions to try and establish a zoo in Lae to help with the need for environmental education, originally the suggested area in Lae was out somewhere near 8 mile where a bit of land was available the suggestion did not gain traction along that vein. Discussions was also held with the Lae Botanical Gardens with a view of developing the project there which didn't go anywhere either and they suggested 10ha of land at UNITECH which was then being used as a dump site, which contained old army equipment. It was situated on an old water course so it was light on soil and heavy on gravel. Although it turned out to be the ideal location but it was indeed a gigantic challenge to pull off the project successfully. However, with the hope to bring a better understanding of the forest and its inhabitants to the average city dwelling Papua New Guinean and encourage their respect of the environment is worth the hard, tedious and laborious undertaking.

The site was a challenge on the surface but it had the life blood to support all the intended features of the rainforest habitat, it had water very close to the surface it did supply a very good source of well filtered water which was exploited with the installation of a bore and which supplied constant water to the RFH lake.

As was mentioned earlier the existing soil condition was very heavy on gravel which presented a poor soil type for plant growth. Therefore, high volumes of top soil were trucked with support from various groups in the country, the Prime Minister's office, the security force and private sector. Support from the Office of the Prime Minister because they knew of the work at the IFTA and knew they appreciated the value of the project to the country as such they were influential in organizing the purchasing, construction of the main covering and its erection. Help also came from many other businesses in the town, for example PNG Forest Products built the entrance building, office and training centre, and a staff house. Assurances came from the Defence Force at Igam Barracks in the form of heavy equipment and trucks to level the site and removed the spoils to other areas and Boinamo Enterprises sourced and brought in selected top soil along with other landscaping materials such as manure and mulch.

The elegance of the RFA and the great role it is playing in enhancing the biodiversity within UNITECH, Lae and PNG is very valuable to the environment and the people. Hence, the concept is a great success for the University and the country at large. One of the main purposes of the RFH concept is educational support and this purpose serves this study very well in many ways. The RFH as forest serve to simulate in a practical way, the detail of its stages of development represent the kind of vision that this research wishes to encourage in the development of a sustainable rainwater harvesting systems (SRHS) in Lae City: A model for Papua New Guinea. It shows that during the replication throughout the country in addition to installing the system it is not farfetched to juxtapose a forest akin to the system if a forest does not naturally exist to induce rainfall and provide water supply continuously as reserve vegetation. In light of the experiences on various informal visits unrelated and related to the study it was noted that a number of water scarce communities in PNG has had their forest denuded and depleted and in discussion with residents of these communities they revealed that it is usually done in search food and fuel for cooking purposes. So that the lessons from

the rainforest habitat development in conjunction with SRHS from this research is very valuable to fix some of these issues that have gotten out of control over many years.

Finally, the inauguration of the RFH initiated the development of a partnership with the Wildlife Conservation Society of New York, the Morobe Education Department and British Petroleum Papua New Guinea (BP PNG) instigated a Primary School environmental education in Morobe Province, to do this they brought in teacher trainers from New York who assisted in the training and seminar presentations, teachers from all over Morobe, were supplied with educational materials and had the Education Department make it part of the curriculum. The photographs in figure 3.4 show the vegetation and biodiversity of the rainforest habit and site layout plan of the habitat.

Figure 3.3 Site layout plan of the habitat

Figure 3.4 Vegetation and biodiversity of the rainforest habit

3.6 A SRHS Model Assembling

The study culminates with the development of a model of a rainwater harvesting system that represent a scaled 3D view of the proposed system. The purpose of this model is to simulate the operation in a practical way. Showing how rainfall on the SRHS would be collected from different intensities, thus creating a record for future reference, when the proposed replication is implemented. This model is a rectangular shaped structure showing salient features to harvest rainwater. These includes a catchment surface, an inlet canal, a filter compartment, circulation ports within the water process section, storage tank, distribution outlet, tank overflow and cleanout outlet. A feature of this model that might be unique is the rain simulation tray which is also rectangular and is fixed atop the catchment surface and is completed with a water support contraption that releases water using a

controlled valve to produce different gauges of rainfall. As a model it required to be constructed from a material that offers flexible maneuverings and the ability to be shaped easily, light weight to permit portability and to be able to bring out as much intricate details as possible, to the furtherance of greater clarity of how the system work. The type of material used to construct the prototype are Poly methyl methacrylate (PMMA) also known as acrylic or acrylic glass as well as by trade names plexiglass, acrylite, lucite and perspex among many others. It is a transparent thermoplastic often used in sheet form as a lightweight or shatter resistant alternative to glass(Encyclopedia, 2016b). Aluminum frames were used to formulate a support into which the system was fixed for structural support. Aluminum is a lightweight, silvery-white metallic element that is ductile and is found chiefly in bauxite, and is a good conductor of electricity. It is the most abundant metal in the earth's crust and is used to make a wide variety of products from can to airplane components(Encyclopedia, 2016a).

3.6.1 SRHS Model Construction Process

Design of the sustainable rainwater harvesting system is a very crucial part of this study. The field trips showed that the locals struggle greatly in making rainwater harvesting system that are durable and efficient. This is both in regards to installation, the catchment itself, the treatment and the storage.

3.6.2 Concepts

Within the delivery system there are four main functions: Catchment surface, filter unit, storage tanks and distribution outlet, which are to a large extent reliant on each other. The concept of the unit specification here gives an overview of the purpose and briefly presents explanations of its construction.

3.6.3 Evaluation

Evaluating the concepts in the lab give an indication on what may be useful to further bring out the effectiveness and functionality through testing the model. Thereby, ascertaining a bird's eye view of how it will work on a larger scale and in real life situations.

Based on the evaluation exercise, intuition and pros and cons, the most promising concept for a sustainable rainwater harvesting structure is the SRHS model which demonstrates that given the weaknesses within the rainwater collection in PNG. This concept of a composite operating as a central water supply unit to a community will mitigate many of the water challenges faced by the PNG communities. The concept was chosen primarily because of good durability and less operation demands, and will be taken further into modeling and testing to improve its viability as it develops.

CHAPTER 4

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Introduction

This chapter discusses the results and gives details of the analysis of the sustainability of rainwater harvesting systems in Lae City: a model for Papua New Guinea. An investigation of rainwater harvesting potential showed that the amount of water harvested by a rainwater harvesting systems could considerably support the municipal water usage. The study considers the UNITECH campus as the study area and from there the simulation demonstrates sequence of activities leading up to the implementation of SRHS. Using the community on campus highlighted the needs to be looked at and determine how harvested water would be used for the people. Based on rainwater harvesting potential and community needs, a determination of what types of materials and approaches were required for the construction of a sustainable rainwater harvesting systems for this community.

The amount of water harvested by a rainwater harvesting system can meaningfully compensate for inevitable shortfall within the community, given that the harvesting system has enough storage. In order to determine this, an examination of rainfall statistics and earlier the water consumption pattern of the sample area has been done.

In order to define the amount of rain that could be harvested from a SRHS we examined the climatic conditions in terms of average precipitations in the specific local, monthly rainfall pattern, and annual water demand and water storage level throughout the year. We then calculated average catchment size base on the design parameters, taking into account the average runoff coefficient; to estimate the amount of water that could be collected during each month the data such as catchment size, runoff coefficient etc. were imputed in the software Samsamwater- Rainwater harvesting tool that outputted the results obtained for this study.

4.2 Policy Review

Harvesting rainwater has overtime been accounted for as a water conservation measure, particularly in regions where other water resources are scarce or difficult to access. In recent years, researchers and policy makers have shown renewed interest in water use

strategies due to rising water demand, increased interest in conservation (both water and energy), and an increased in policy development and regulatory emphasis on reducing storm water runoff volumes, associated pollutant loads and other harmful water issues and health concerns. In the last decade, as interest in the practice has grown, numerous state, municipal, regional and global agencies have adopted or amended polices, codes and guidelines to encourage responsible and effective rainwater harvesting practices. In addition, researchers from technical tertiary institutions and nongovernment organizations, as well as commercial sector and professionals, have circulated documents and articles which speak to a broad collection of matters related to the installation, upkeep, prices, and presentation of harvested rainwater and the use of systems for the most effective outcome. **Table 4.1** show a policy review of some of the countries that are developing states like Papua New Guinea, that are engaged in rain-water harvesting as a part of their water source architecture and have developed Policy Guidelines in that regard.

Table 4.1 Global Rainwater Harvesting Policy Review

Policy Description	Strength
Jamaica	
The Jamaican Government currently allocates 0.1% of its total budget to water resources (ESL Management Solutions Limited, 2009).	The water scarcity in the island which makes Government stakeholders aware of the need to improve water management and funding for RWH.
Policy initiatives such as RWH mandates for all new construction and tax incentives to incorporate RWH into existing structures are necessary to mitigate and adapt to the impacts of climate change on water resources.	The integration of rainwater resource and reuse in the water resources and environmental management.
Given the economic importance of the tourism industry and the large quantities of water associated with it, policies could target hotels and buildings in the tourism sector for rainwater collection (i.e., rainwater can be used for laundry, flushing toilets).	The alternative water resources: rainwater, surface runoff combined with the use of new technologies to reduce the need for excessive use of conventional resources.
Barbados	
Obtaining and analyzing information and maintaining up-to-date records of the total available fresh water resources of Barbados.	Foster an environment of deep knowledge of integrated water management
Establishment of a system whereby data related to water resources including rainfall collection, extraction, rainfall levels etc., is collected, collated and stored effectively. This information should then contribute to the development of future water use and management policies and programs.	Foster an environment of deep knowledge of integrated water management
Continued support for the policy requiring new dwellings of a particular size to construct rainwater catchment and storage tanks, including the possible revision of the policy to include existing dwellings and new dwellings of smaller sizes.	The integration of rainwater resource and reuse in the water resources and environmental management.
Bermuda	
Most systems use rainwater storage tanks under buildings with electric pumps to supply piped indoor water. Storage tanks have reinforced concrete floors and roofs, and the walls are constructed of mortar filled concrete blocks with an interior mortar application approximately 1.5 cm thick.	The old tradition to use alternative water resources; rainwater, combined with the use of new technologies: such as pumps and concrete technology
Rainwater utilization systems in Bermuda are regulated by a Public Health Act which requires that all catchments be whitewashed by white latex paint; the paint must be free from metals that might leach into water supplies.	Presence of public health sector in water quality preservation, will help to prevent the out of water borne diseases etc.
Owners must also keep catchments, tanks, gutters, pipes, vents and screens in good repair. Roofs are commonly repainted every two to three years and storage tanks must be cleared at least once every six years.	Improved rainwater techniques for household harvesting and use

Policy Description	Strength
In Papua New Guinea rainwater must be harvested in different ways such as roof catchments, rock catchments, ground catchments, earth dams etc. because cultural diversity dramatic terrain variation.	These guidelines focus on various technical options for improving domestic water supply provision, namely the collection and storage of rainwater runoff from different modalities.
In general, household rainwater tanks are one of the most appropriate solutions to improving potable water supplies in the PNG with an increased level of community involvement and self-reliance in rural water supply schemes but they can also be of value in urban situations.	Currently the knowledge about storage of water and appropriate storage is not well developed as such this policy will bring about a welcome change in the way storage is done.
The vital importance of rainwater is evident in the island and may in fact be the primary, and in some cases only, source of freshwater. Therefore, the preservation of environmental inducements for rainfall is mandatory and must be enforced in all communities.	Only the preservation of the environment can guarantee sustainability in rainfall which is primary source of freshwater water in the most rural and low income communities in PNG. So that promoting good environmental practices among residents and communities is paramount.

Table 4.2 Local Rainwater Harvesting Policy Review

4.2.1 Proposed framework for sustainable rainwater harvesting systems in Lae City: a model for Papua New Guinea.

Sustainable rainwater harvesting is currently not a feature of the water regime in Papua New Guinea (PNG). However as the demand for water for human and industrial use has escalated, so has the need for viable alternative sources. Consequently, new challenges call for a new approach. Hence, the proposal for a sustainable rainwater harvesting system for Lae City that can be replicated throughout PNG in the future and is driven by clear policies. For this to be effective it will require a coherent set of guiding principles which will be set out in this framework. At the moment the approach to rainwater harvesting in PNG is haddock and is not inviting to any form of investment whether from government, NGO'S or private investors. To manage the utilization of rainwater resources more sustainably and effectively, a balanced set of policies and institutional involvement is required starting with the global outlook on rainwater harvesting. The idea is to harness the support of private sector and strengthen the capacity of governments to carry out their essential roles in the harvesting of rainwater for the benefit of the wider community.

Establishing a communal rainwater harvesting system in a community will require support from various groups and government agencies, primary among these are the local government division of government and water sector who are the first line of contact on water infrastructure and water operation funding at a community level. The local government and water sector are the main medium through which government expend budgeted funds on the community. These agencies are also the structures through which private sector and NGO's channel funds to be expended in the community. The local government fosters leadership representative from the community who accounts for money being spent in the community and report to them. This kind of representation and feedback system is vital to the establishment of a communal Sustainable rainwater harvesting system in any community throughout PNG.

The synergies from this arrangement will be beneficial to the implementation and operation of the rainwater harvesting communal systems, management of the environment, water reserved management, rain data management, water quality and quantity control, distribution management and ultimately the continuous delivery of water supply to the user community.

4.2.1.1 The conceptual framework for operation and management of SRHS

The scope of the water needs in PNG cannot be met by government alone, if the development of sustainable water system implementation must be timely and meet the major areas of need. Then, the solicitation of support from private sector and non-government organizations in this regard is vital. At the center of this framework is the community action group/steering committee for Sustainable Rainwater Harvesting, which will be the driving force behind environmental protection, watershed management, rain data management, water quantity and quality control and distribution management to the benefit of SRHS host community.

Figure 4.1 A Policy Conceptual Framework for operation and management for SRHS

4.2.1.1.1 Community action group/steering committee for SRHS

The framework will seek to tap into the synergies of traditional and customary social construct, to produce a structure for a community/village base action group. That will be incorporated as a community base organization with support from all levels of government and even external sources when possible. The idea will drive the implementation of sustainable rainwater harvesting systems throughout these communities and villages, which are without sustainable means of water.

4.2.1.1.1.1 Land Tenure

One of the traditional and customary social construct within PNG is the whole issue of land tenure. In respect of this attachment to land resources, SRHS must integrate the acquisition of property and a workable guideline to sustainable reserve vegetation preservation. This can be done through a community action group/committee since they are conversant with the nuances and encumbrances at a community level. Where, the land acquisition and legitimacy is beyond traditional authority then legal government land acquisition processes will take precedence. If the offer is refused, then it should be handed over to the government land authorities, who will continue further negotiation until a compromise is reached. This will be manoeuvred through the water sector and the local government that has the capacity to execute as state entities acting on the behalf of the community.

Land is of central importance to people in cultural and economic terms in Papua New Guinea, especially in rural areas. Land rights and resource ownership are thus fundamental issues underpinning natural use and resource management, and are central to resource-based forms of development, like water infrastructure. Approximately 97 per cent of Papua New Guinea's total land area is held under customary forms of land tenure by the traditional landowners – communities and clans – a right guaranteed by the National Constitution. The diversity of belief systems and forms of local social organization, as well as local environments, produces often complex sets of connections to land and livelihood strategies (UNDP, 2014). Thus, it is imperative that the SRHS does not stand alone in its implementation, but all stakeholders (Community, local government, water sector etc.) must form part of the processes, to allow for smooth implementation of the system and favourable acceptance from the communities of Papua New Guinea. Although the land issues are real

and seem so difficult to penetrate, but an approach that highlight the current methods of rainwater harvesting in PNG (**Figure 4.2**) and the associated health risk with the poor storage, such as mosquito breeding and other water borne diseases such as cholera. By presenting sustainable rainwater harvesting system and explaining the good benefits will help to break through the cultural barriers that may during the circulation of the system throughout the country.

Figure 4.2 Rainwater harvesting contraption at a settlement in Lae (Madang Compound)

4.2.1.1.2 Global and Regional support, capacity building and funding

There are several approaches to engage global and regional support for the funding, implementation, and operation of rainwater harvesting systems. These supports can take several forms technical training; grant funding, loan access, exchange program, institutional strengthening and so on. However, to channel these support require properly established state agencies like local government and Water PNG in Papua New Guinea. These agencies through the mainstream national government can make representation on behalf of the communities in PNG to access funding for the implementation of sustainable rainwater

harvesting systems. As described earlier in the literature review the provision of drinking water is priority for major global multinational agencies.

4.2.1.1.3 Regional

Cross-regional connections are facilitated by means of exchange visits, regional workshops and annual learning events between all implementing partners. Exchanges also take place with networks such as SEARNET (Southern and Eastern Africa Rainwater Network), IRHA (International Rainwater Harvesting Alliance), GHARP (Greater Horn of Africa Rainwater Partnership), the MUS Group (Multiple Use Water Services) and CGIAR (Consultative Group on International Agricultural Research), and during annual events such as the Stockholm Water Week and the SEARNET International Conference (Nijhof et al., 2010). It should be noted however, that such activities will also require external funding as it would be unlikely that resources would be supplied by either provincial or the national government.

4.2.1.1.4 National Government

The style of this framework is to encourage partnership at all levels and in all phases of the rainwater harvesting strategy. Where a framework for collaboration among the national government, private sector and NGO's is understood from the very outset of a rainwater harvesting program proposal and where practical with support from external agencies, for technical support and transfer of sustainable rainwater harvesting technologies etc. The central emphasis of this collaboration is to create a plan like the skeleton created in this study for Sustainable Rainwater Harvesting Programme in PNG and on capacity building in the country at a national level, with a view to prepare the environment for investments in sustainable rainwater harvesting as an Alternative water source for all (UN-HABITAT, 2011).

In Papua New Guinea encouraging rainwater harvesting requires assisting the practice to develop a careful approach to rainwater harvesting that protect the healthy distribution of potable water that has gone through standard water management process for quality assurance and providing encouragements through partnership and capacity building, environmental management and sound policy driven operational strategies. This can be accomplished by examining and adapting best practices from countries with a track record of achievement in

policy driven sustainable rainwater harvesting. In addition, government through the various arms of the state needs to address cultural and social concerns that will inhibit tapping into this important water resource. Example, land tenure and public education are matters that must be initiated at that level, if satisfactory result must be achieved. This is paramount in order to create a climate that motivates communities to welcome rainwater harvesting. This study is initiating that in the proposed implementation of SRHS in PNG. Specific and related sustainable rainwater harvesting policies must be developed to address these concerns on an ongoing basis. Policies should establish acceptable uses for rainwater as an alternative source to Water PNG, especially in areas where the terrain or other inhibiting factors prevent Water PNG from supplying.

In the national government system there are built in procedures for lower government entities such as local government to access funding to undertake effort to establish a sustainable rainwater harvesting system. For example the evidence based requisition for funding is the best approach where by officers within the entity that is aware of an infrastructural or water scarcity concern in a community, can investigate these concerns in depth and scope a project to resolve the problem. In this scope a report on the genesis of the project is presented in technical details and preliminary cost estimate, for approval by the head of the agency and the procurement committee to proceed further with the development of the project. The further development of such projects would incorporate working drawings, bills of quantities, schedule and a complete contract document ready for perusal and processing and approval by the government procurement department. If all the related procurement procedures are followed then a contractor is selected through a standard tender process and preparation for implementation and project commencement, that will see all authorized government agent signing off and submitted to be process for funding arrangement, finally, disbursement certificates are processed and release at the different phases of the works through to complete, occupation and defects liability stages where final payment is made based on satisfactory snag list is signed off and a maintenance program for the structure is enacted.

4.2.1.1.5 Local Government Support

Local government is the arm of government that has direct link to the community and has direct responsibilities for the implementation and operation of community infrastructure

such as road and water. This authority at community level makes it the ideal entity through which a sustainable rainwater harvesting system can be implemented and operated within a community. The local government agency as the middle agency will see the smooth flow of project implementation and prevent any corrupt practices from fracturing the success of such project. As a government agency there are already standing orders the guide the action of the officers and these standing orders are enforceable by law and serves to protect the government expenditure at that level, with these structures enforced and adhered to then corruption can be kept out of the arrangements.

Sustainable rainwater harvesting system requires multiple interventions, which jointly enhance the resource base and water harvesting potential of a community. To this end the local government will act as the middle agents between stakeholders and the community as this relationship is vital to the smooth flow of the whole process of implementing a SRHS. The local governments facilitate, budgetary and policy enforcement and support the community to own operate and participate in representation at community level on water resources preservation. They will also be charged to give technical and other support to the active community group/ committees on rainwater harvesting for continuity and vigorous sustainability of the guiding principles for SRHS. This facilitation is capacity building at a community level, the process to reinforce the abilities of people to make well-organized use of resources in order to realize their own objectives in a sustained way.

4.2.1.1.6 Water Sector in Papua New Guinea

To understand how the water sector work in Papua New Guinea and how it will impact the concept of “sustainable rainwater harvesting in Lae City – A model for Papua New Guinea” requires an insight into the operations and the mandate of Water PNG. It is essential to understand how it was established? Why it was established? And how it has evolved over the years? Details of the background and Water PNG model is detailed in the literature review of this paper. However, vast concept of sustainable rainwater harvesting to operate throughout PNG as proposed, would not get off the ground any time soon if it should establish a structure within which to carry out its own operations. A venture like the proposal of this research require in depth familiarization with the communities and water aspects, with the experience of Water PNG the proposal is to incorporate SRHS operations within the current operations and utilize the water collected as an alternative or additional water that can

help the company in many respect including being able to continue supply even more efficiently. The size of PNG and the diversity of the country and terrain each area that will be proposed to establish SRHS will have to be dealt with as a case by case basis for best result.

4.2.1.1.7 Environment Management

The impacts of climate change on the environment- the care of the environment is not high on the agenda of the communities. For example a policy that prohibits cutting trees for fuel would solve much of the problems since this is one of the main areas of environmental destruction in PNG. By so doing the government would be required to provide a more environmentally friendly way of doing domestic cooking. Changes in temperature, precipitation and sea levels - are expected to have varying consequences for the availability of freshwater around the world. The main impacts of climate change on humans and the environment occur through water. Efficient management and an integrated policy on water resources need to be reconciled with society's desire for equity and environmental sustainability. Increased loss of functioning infrastructure as a result of climate change would set back progress in drinking water supply and, indirectly, towards other Millennium Development Gold (MDG) targets. There is a wide range of potential climate change impacts on water supply technologies, including changeable rainfall patterns, flood damage to infrastructure, increased contamination, deteriorating water quality, increased treatment requirements and reduced availability.

All drinking water technologies will be vulnerable to climate change, but all have some adaptive potential. A policy framework setting out a unifying set of principles for adaptation and sustainability and investment in this adaptive potential, will make systems and services more resilient, in the face of extreme climatic conditions that can adversely affect sustainable rainwater harvesting systems (SRHS).The intervention of this study to develop a SRHS, the aim of which is to mitigate the full impact of climate change on sustainable rainwater harvesting potential in the face of the unpredictability of climate pattern, and on the infrastructure involve in this process. The current environmental situation in PNG regarding Sustainable Rainwater Harvesting is not reflected generally throughout the country's landscape or even at a community level (Unicef., 2011). Papua New Guinea is very susceptible to natural disasters that occurs naturally or man-made. One of the area that is most vulnerable in a natural disaster like hurricane is the water supply. So that the concept of

the SRHS is have a policy that allow details the type of material to construct storage for example concrete has been very resilient when constructed properly. Another area has to do with reserve vegetation which will induce rainfall in another type of disaster drought conditions a policy to ensure that areas designated for reserved vegetation is not violated for any reason and are maintained at the highest standard always.

Local communities throughout the world have developed a variety of rainwater harvesting systems but its sustainability is threatened by disregarding conformity to environmental principles. A number of factors in addition to cost should be considered when choosing appropriate water sources or a specific sustainable rainwater harvesting system. Climate (rainfall pattern and rain intensity), vegetation reserve, technology, socio-economic factors, local livelihood, political system, and organizational management all play an important role in the eventual choice. The essential starting point when considering a rainwater catchment system for domestic water supply is to determine its environmental, technological and socio-economic viability.

4.2.1.1.8 Watershed Management

Purpose

The goal of this framework is to develop a methodology which will help source the most fitting answer by the Papua New Guinea environment agency in light the incidents of damage to reserve vegetation in various location of the country especially in areas that can least afford to deal with the climate change backlash that will result. The reason for such destruction of reserves vegetation is justified by communities as a means of survival. However, principally in regard to villages, difficult to reach terrain and other small and vulnerable communities, this practice of denuding forest for food and fuel will have to be discouraged in the most vigorous ways; so that this study will accompany the proposal to develop sustainable rainwater harvesting in the country with this framework for watershed management.

Scope

This framework relates to:

- a) The common practices destroying vegetation on land without control or regulation , including what is described in PNG as customary or traditional lands (whilst damage to

vegetation on privately owned land is often an issue there are alternative measures to address this) for example public education and enforcement of environment laws.

b) Destruction to reserve vegetation means burning, poisoning, pruning, felling and the vast and unmanaged removal of vegetation without notifying the environment agencies to coordinate such activities or disallow the destruction if it is deemed detrimental to the environment in the quantities it is being done.

c) The implementation of a SRHS anywhere in PNG will be guided by this framework and the relevant gazette of the document will be included, to make it enforceable upon implementation of SRHS. This will ensure that vegetation illegally removed from the date of adoption of this framework, will attract the necessary enforcement action.

4.3 Framework content

The framework has been advanced with the following points in mind:

a) To afford alternatives to reserved vegetation damage on lands in PNG as a part of the encouragement towards the direction of sustainable rainwater harvesting as a mitigating strategy to the inevitable effect of climate change.

b) To promote a robust dialogue with the communities throughout PNG that illegally damage to vegetation reserves cannot be tolerated if the country must progress and develop.

c) To promote an instrument to inspire community members to report illegitimate destruction to vegetation.

d) To promote sustainable preventive measures against illicit destruction to vegetation, primarily on areas designated as reserve vegetation for the implementing of SRHS.

4.4 Background

Damage of vegetation unlawfully on public or private land is a frequent problem within PNG, being aware of this, has inspired this study to carefully document the concerns with the hope that one day this framework could be a precursor to the enactment of laws against these destruction; against the background of promoting rainwater harvesting and promoting watershed protection. Particular attention will have to be placed on areas where

people are most unaware of the consequences of such actions. Vegetation quite often is destroyed for several reasons, ranging from sabotage to deliberately planned acts, which may persist, carried out for private benefit such as the enhancement of views in urban areas and fuel and food in rural villages. A challenge that will lead to an ongoing decrease in vegetation and a change in canopy structure. This will cause an increased sunlight intensity intrusion on many forest. Reserve vegetation in PNG is of high value to food security that relies heavily on agriculture, which will not survive without sufficient rainfall. Often is particularly significant in terms of:

Safeguarding valuable flora and fauna interest which can have continuous water supply significance and even economic values in terms of attracting tourists, but equally important as rainwater harvesting is, it is not the only spectrum of benefit from a well-regulated reserve, because it also includes habitat values for the protection of endangered species.

- Topography protection
- Soil stabilization
- Scenery preservation
- Shade facility
- Gale force wind barrier for residential communities
- Historical and cultural
- Cultural and historical importance.
- Existing powers to prosecute for damage to vegetation

Provisions exist for the potential prosecution and subsequent penalizing of persons unlawfully destroying vegetation within Papua New Guinea under: Conservation & Environmental Protection Act (2014). “to provide for the conservation and protection of the environment in accordance with the Fourth National Goal and Directive Principle (National Resources and Environment) of the Constitution”. Though seemingly wide-ranging the requirements in terms of proof to reach a successful action, given the nature of the offence, are such that it is unsuitable and ineffective as the sole means of answering to such cases. Particular restrictions are: Although the environmental laws are mentioned in extreme circumstances but limited enforcement is done often time because of the lack of resources

which makes it very discouraging. Therefore, prosecution is rarely pursued due to the fact that it is very difficult and rare to gain satisfactory proof to identify the individual liable.

4.4.1 Framework statement

Principles

The following principles will guide the framework statement:

- i. Destruction to reserve vegetation in PNG, without the approval from the steering committee associated with the SRHS is an objectionable conduct by any member of community and is also an environment breach.
- ii. The reserve vegetation is the nucleus of the SRHS concept as it is the means by which continuous water supply is generated, so that the SRHS will erect signage to define the boundaries of reservation. Anywhere vegetation destruction has been done for reason of a direct profit to individual person or a neighboring property-owner and adequate proof has been found, prosecution will be pursued with the payment of restoration of damage vegetation in addition to applicable penalties, as will be dealt with outside the ambit of the SRHS framework on watershed management by the police.
- iii. Wherever possible and when insufficient evidence for prosecution has been obtained, re destruction of vegetation, regeneration of damaged areas should be carried out by the SRHS infrastructure team until the offender is brought through due process and the necessary penalty applies.
- iv. On locations wherever illicit reserved destruction has transpired an evaluation on the extent of vegetation damaged, and whatever benefit resulting from the lost and the destruction of the site will determine whether more signs will be placed to inform the community of the SRHS response and to motivate eyewitnesses to come forward to provide proof for action; where there are occurrences of SRHS reserved loss has ensured that openly profits neighbouring landowner (eg. for food, fuel or view enhancement) and where there is high community exposure, big signage will be erected in the lines of sight to make sure that there is no continuation of benefit from illegitimate vegetation damage or removal, and to inform the community of the

seriousness of the offences and how it will hurt them in the long run, and that such activities are not acceptable.

- v. The leadership of the local government, conservation and environment authority of PNG and the water sector should guide leadership groups in communities as to the legal procedures that must be followed to initiate prosecution proceedings for vegetation removal and destruction under this policy; and

Unlawful destruction where the witness acknowledged and a landowner has admitted to vegetation damage, or a witness is prepared to attest against the purported offender, and action taken under the PNG Conservation & Environmental Law, or the Local Government Act then the following response shall proceed:

- i. Get in touch with the property owner who has admitted or is alleged to have undertaken the damage and provide an opportunity for them to explain their actions and any mitigating circumstances. Where the damage is significant and has been undertaken for the purpose of a personal benefit and there are no valid mitigating circumstances prosecution shall begin.
- ii. The action should include recovering the cost of re-vegetation and additional signage shall be sought in addition to the financial penalty as part of any successful prosecution.
- iii. When the penalty is followed through but is unsuccessful or the cost of re-vegetation not achieved, signage and re-vegetation should be undertaken at the expense of the SRHS operating expenses within 28 days to ensure that the integrity of the watershed is highlighted and people learn that it should not be taken lightly.
- iv. Action taken must be fair and in keeping with the Conservation & Environment act Prosecutions Policy. The community group responsible officer must determine the significance of the damage and the personal benefit that has been derived from the action.
- v. In conditions where the act is minor the SRHS should engaged the offender and take action to seek remedy by replacement of the vegetation, whereas if the damage is significant prosecution is appropriate.
- vi. Substantial destruction will include the use of felling equipment to kill vegetation, or removal of any tree by other means. Minor damage may include pruning of a tree or

cutting of any vegetation where the vegetation would recoverable and would not be killed.

- vii. Unlawful destruction with no evidence or admittance of guilt where the SRHS community officer inquiries fail to find an appropriate witness or admission of guilt, the SRHS should determine what action is required to remedy the damage which may include re-vegetation or allowing the vegetation to regenerate, and erect more signs at or around the reservation.
- viii. Enticement for evidence leading to action on occasions where the damage to vegetation is particularly substantial, or cannot be supplanted by re-vegetation within a realistic time (e.g. abstraction of mature trees/ vegetation) and a successful action would lead to a major fine, the head of the Conservation & Environment department and the Local government shall offer a monetary inducement up to a value of PGK 1000 in order to encourage witnesses to come forward. Payment of the inducement would only occur following an effective action.

4.4.2 Signs

Subject to the nature of the community in which the vegetation is located, two types of signage are appropriate. Style 1 signage will be mounted at all locations where signals that vegetation has been unlawfully destroyed and there is no strong evidence of a direct benefit to adjoining properties. Style 1 sign shall comprise of a fairly small signage about 0.9m by 0.6m worded as follows:

- SRHS reserve vegetation in this site and the plants in this area is being monitored trespassers will be prosecuted.
- Style 2 signs will be erected at all locations where vegetation has been unlawfully damaged and there is strong proof of a personal benefit to connecting lands, such as enhanced line of sight, fuel etc. The decision for style 2 is to remove the advantage that may have been resulting from unlawful vegetation destruction, and to inform the community that this behavior is unacceptable.
- Style 2 signs will comprise of a big signage about 1.8m by 1.2m installed in clear and visible locations along the site of the vegetation as follows worded:

SRHS reserve vegetation at this site and damaged plants regeneration in progress no trespassing. Sign SRHS management.

A funding provision shall be requested from the Conservation & Environmental Planning budget each year to cover signs and other costs. More funding may be needed if there are many offences in a particular year, nonetheless, it is expected these will decrease with the introduction of this framework.

4.4.3 Inspections

SRHS community team will have designated inspecting rangers who will monitor the sites where signs has been placed once a year. Monitoring will be done including matching photos with marked locations of the site from the time sign was erected, to ensure that surrounding vegetation are compared with documentation of first inspection, looking keenly for density and height difference of vegetation.

4.4.4 Public Awareness

When SRHS has been implemented and has adopted this policy and at consistent intervals of subsequent positive outcome, the policy will be the subject of a media publication and reporting in the SRHS community, to reinforce and highlight the achievement of this policy and encourage residents to continue to support the effort.

4.4.5 Framework evaluation

Appraisal and assessment of this framework for watershed management is crucial in the continual improvement in the achievement of the objective to ensure continuous in support of the effort to establish sustainable rainwater harvesting systems throughout Papua New Guinea Communities .The framework shall be subject to formal review periodically. This will generally be every 5 years and will involve a review of the cases handled under the framework throughout each successive period and evaluate the usefulness of the rules in dealing with the specific cases that have risen. Community responses received throughout the years and the number of cases of unlawful clearing would form part of this evaluation in order to monitor the framework's efficiency in discouraging illicit clearance and achieving

effective restoration. This assessment shall climax in sanctions for improving the functioning processes or framework measures.

4.4.6 Rain data management

The protection and continuation of water supply in Papua New Guinea through sustainable rainwater harvesting reflects the essence of this policy framework. Hence, the policy framework being developed by this study is the foundation for future and continuous revision on sustainable rainwater harvesting potential and the study of rainfall pattern in PNG. This is so because the environment in which we harvest rainwater is very unpredictable due to climate change and the ever changing human conduct towards the environment (UNESCO, 2012).

The actual task to the implementation of a sustainable rain water harvesting solution is to resolve to understand the amount of storage required during the wet season so as to meet the demand for water during the annual low rainfall period (dry season) of approximately five months. It is therefore necessary to have reliable rainfall data over a period of at least 25 to 30 years alongside current validating data, to support a prediction model and pattern on which to base design parameters for specific community. The data collection process is an ongoing process for the operation and management of communal rainwater harvesting system. This records administration process together with weather predictions from credible weather sources, also supports in the distribution controls, in that one can determine the volume of water to be distributed.

The sustainability of rainwater harvesting relies heavily on the quantity of rainfall and patterns of rain storm in the area, the length of dry periods and other water sources. The rainfall pattern based on rain statistics collection and ensuing calculation exercise plays a central role in determining whether sustainable rainwater harvesting is possible. The common rule is that, the rainfall characteristics should be over 50 mm/month for 6 months or 300 mm/annually to make rainwater harvesting viable.

4.4.7 Rain data management proposal SRHS

Rain data is the most essential element to planning of any sustainable rainwater harvesting system anywhere in the world or even conventional water resources administration

arrangement. In Papua New Guinea, rainfall data is collected by the Papua New Guinea National Weather Service, through a network of stations located especially in renowned organizations and other strategic location around the Island. Climatic data are normally kept in tabular forms but digital versions have also been created. The PNG national weather service should be contacted to obtain these data where available. Climate region records can also be accessed to help in assessing the preliminary evaluation of the weather pattern of the designated zone. It is of paramount importance that in depth understanding of rainfall pattern in the target area is important from the start of planning. Therefore, the available data from the national weather station will often require to be accompanied by more intense measurements in the target zone and usually now a days climate software are quite accurate to do this. It is recommended that this should be done for a period of 3 – 5 years at locations within proximity 2 km apart. It has been noted in several rainfall scenarios that rain gauge data represent only a small area surrounding the gauge, the radius of a rainfall event is very difficult to predict accurately. Special efforts should be made to obtain full weather information from the national weather service data where possible. If this is not possible then the most important basic parameters can be obtained from climate software like SamSamwater – climate tool: daily rainfall amount, Rainfall intensity Average, minimum and maximum, monthly and annual rainfall amount. Climate modelling software is useful but quite often very expensive and prohibitive, but if available it can accurately generate long-term data series from the short term measurements using statistical correlations and satellite data.

4.4.8 Water quality and quantity

Background

Rainwater is generally good quality water source. However, the proliferation of conventional water sources has reduced its uses overtime. Recently the idea of rainwater usage has taken on new tractions for various environmental reasons and climate change. The huge cost to supplying treated water to especially remote and rural areas from a centralized source, and of pumping from deep wells has meant that serious consideration to rainwater collection in a sustainable way. Sustainability though not a new event, will require guiding principles to achieve continuous water supply and an environmentally friendly process of sanitizing water for drinking. The treatment needed for water such as sanitization of

rainwater for use must be standardized, also research and policies should serve to encourage and simplify sustainable rainwater harvesting process.

Hence, the strategies in the policy framework are laid out a process flow that will incorporate an ideal site synergy to ensure the smooth implementation of a SRHS. Adequate water supply systems are not just dependent on the quantity of water collected, but also depend on the quality of this water. Rainwater quality may be affected by air pollution, animal or bird droppings, insects, dirt and organic matter. So regular maintenance as well as treatment before water consumption, must be accounted for in this framework to guarantee ultimate sustainability of quality and sustainability of rainwater harvesting.

In rural areas rainwater is generally unpolluted and pure before reaching the ground. It is also in these areas that rainwater from catchments is most commonly used for drinking. Rainwater from well-maintained catchments is generally safe to drink without treatment. Except in heavily urbanized and industrialized areas or regions adjacent to active volcanoes, atmospheric rainwater is very pure and any contamination of the water usually occurs after contact with the catchment system. Regular cleaning and inspection of the catchment area and conveyance systems are important to ensure good water quality. The first rains should be used to flush away the dust, bird droppings, leaves etc. that lie on the catchment surface. In practice, preparation and cleaning of the catchment surface before the first rains hardly ever happens. To prevent these pollutants and contaminants from getting into the storage tank, the first rainwater containing the debris must therefore be diverted or flushed away. Many RWH systems therefore incorporate a system to divert this 'first-flush' water so that it does not enter the tank and for large communal systems a slow sand filter forms part of the design component of the rainwater harvesting unit. A coarse filter, preferably made of nylon or a fine mesh, can also be used to remove dirt and debris before the water enters the storage tank.

The quality of rainwater, which has been properly collected and stored, is expected to be substantially free from minerals and most of the common pollutants that are present in surface and groundwater sources.

To ensure that the rainwater satisfies health requirements for consumption all the harvested rainwater should be given some level of treatment in terms of pH (Potential for Hydrogen), total hardness, chloride concentration and bacterial contamination. From the health point of view it is also important to clean the conveyance from time to time and ensure

that water does not stagnate inside the conveyance unit which can lead to mosquito breeding. Trees hanging in the vicinity definitely enhance the possibility of contamination

Due to increased access of the catchment surface to birds and animals, Leaves and animal droppings contribute to organic loading of the rainwater samples, which in turn act as nutrient for bacterial growth. It is also recommended that the rainwater should be carefully examined if the harvested rainwater is being considered for domestic use especially if it is to be consumed, it should be boiled at least 100 degrees C before consumption and Chlorine (dosage to be determined by a water quality specialist) can be used for disinfection (Olaoye and Olaniyan, 2012).

4.4.9 Framework for SRHS drinking water management adopted from the World Health Organization guidelines for drinking-water quality volume 1 recommendation 2008.

The proposal for sustainable rainwater harvesting system (SRHS) in Lae City is a model for Papua New Guinea designed with a view of serving vast number of people. As a result such system require the best quality control for the water to be distributed, for that reason adopting guidelines set out in the World Health Organization (WHO) guidelines for drinking water quality will set the stage for the communal rainwater harvesting approach proposed by SRHS Rainwater harvesting in whatever quantity is naturally of great quality, once the surrounding environment is not toxic. Unlike other water sources that require extensive and rigorous treatment processes, rainwater does not require that level of treatment. However, the testing parameters remain the same as standard water safety practice. Therefore, it is not necessary to adopt the entire guidelines, only the aspects relevant to water collected from rainwater source in nontoxic zoning will be adopted. The World Health Organization guidelines for drinking water quality relevant to SRHS are set out as follows:

Slow sand filters

Slow sand filters usually consist of tanks containing sand (effective size range 0.15– 0.3 mm) to a depth of between 0.5 and 1.5 m. The raw water flows downwards, and turbidity and microorganisms are removed primarily in the top few centimetres of the sand. A biological layer, known as the “schmutzdecke,” develops on the surface of the filter and can be effective in removing microorganisms. Treated water is collected in underdrains or pipework at the bottom of the filter. The top few centimetres of sand containing the

accumulated solids are removed and replaced periodically. Slow sand filters are operated at a water flow rate of between 0.1 and 0.3 m³/m² · h. Slow sand filters are suitable only for low-turbidity water or water that has been pre-filtered. They are used to remove algae and microorganisms, including protozoa, and, if preceded by micro straining or coarse filtration, to reduce turbidity (including adsorbed chemicals). Slow sand filtration is effective for the removal of organics, including certain pesticides and ammonia (WHO, 2008).

Disinfection

The microbiological quality of drinking-water can be substantially enhanced by protecting the source and by treating the raw water, especially if slow sand filtration is employed. However, where raw waters are not of a consistently high quality, some form of disinfection is essential to ensure that the supply is microbiologically safe. Provided that the physical and chemical quality of the water is acceptable, disinfection provides the most effective means of reducing the numbers of microorganisms in drinking-water. Disinfection methods may be either physical or chemical. Physical methods include boiling and ultraviolet (UV) irradiation; chemical methods include the addition of ozone, or, most commonly, chlorine and its derivatives. Only chlorination has been widely applied in treating community water supplies, although UV irradiation is also sometimes appropriate, as is on-site generation of disinfectant gases. Chlorine is an oxidizing agent that reacts rapidly with organic and inorganic matter present in water. If adequate disinfection is to be achieved, due allowance must be made for the chlorine consumed in these reactions in addition to that needed for disinfection. The amount of chlorine required to react with other compounds (mainly ammonia, some metal ions, and organic compounds) is termed the chlorine demand of the water. Thus, the chlorine dose must be sufficient both to satisfy the chlorine demand and to produce an unreacted excess known as the free residual. A minimum free residual of 0.5mg/litre is recommended, together with a minimum contact time of 30 minutes and a water turbidity of less than 5 NTU (ideally less than 1 NTU). The chlorine demand of some waters (particularly river waters) can increase dramatically at times of heavy pollution, particularly after rain. It may therefore be necessary to increase the dose to allow for this. The residual chlorine level should be determined in samples taken from various points throughout the distribution system; to ensure that a free residual exists in the water supplied to the public. Chlorination usually requires the addition of one of the following three substances to the water:

- Chlorine gas, Cl₂, liquefied under a pressure of 505kPa (5atm). This requires careful handling because it is highly toxic: the gas supplier should provide clear operational guidelines and the surveillance officer should check that these are being strictly observed.
- Sodium hypochlorite solution for water disinfection, containing up to 14% available chlorine, or liquid bleach (about 1% available chlorine). Solutions are unstable at warm temperatures and should be stored in brown or green glass bottles or opaque plastic bottles in a cool, dark place. They should be checked regularly to ensure that the chlorine content is adequate since the concentration may fall if the container has been opened or stored for a long time.
- Solid calcium hypochlorite, commonly available as bleaching powder or chlorinated lime, containing about 30% available chlorine when fresh. The compound is unstable at warm temperatures and should be carefully stored. High-test hypochlorite (HTH) can also be used; it normally contains 50–70% available chlorine. Simple devices for use in chlorination include the constant-head drip and double-pot chlorinators (WHO, 2008).

4.4.10 Distribution Management

Water distribution systems convey water drawn from the water source or treatment facility, to the point where it is delivered to the users. Unlike the transmission systems these systems deal with water demand that varies considerably in the course of a day. Water consumption is highest during the hours that water is used for personal hygiene and cleaning, and when food preparation and clothes washing are done. Water use is lowest during the night. Generally, the distribution system of a community water supply is designed to cater for the domestic and other household water requirements. Stock watering and garden plot irrigation water may also be provided. Storage tanks accumulate and store water during the night so that it can be supplied during the daytime hours of high water-demand. It is necessary to maintain sufficient pressure in the distribution system to protect it against contamination by the ingress of polluted seepage water. For small community supplies a minimum pressure of 5-10 mwc (metres of water column) should be adequate in most instances (Smet and Wijk, 2002).

4.4.11 Site consideration for SRHS water distribution

Sustainable rainwater harvesting and distribution infrastructure are important elements of a well-designed site. Sustainable rainwater harvesting strategies are most effective when fully integrated with the site's other elements including watershed/ vegetation reserve, topography, soils, water flow, and structures, such that the elements work synergistically to create a productive, self-sustaining site. Generally, the less integration that exists between site elements, the lower the site's productivity and the lower the water yield will be for distribution. In contrast, a higher degree of integration of site elements results in a more efficient, productive, and self-sustaining site with higher water yield (Accetturo and Ann Audrey, 2012).

By carrying out a reconnaissance, where the site was mapped to set location points using the eXplorist 510 GPS (Magellan, North America) to accurately map the location points for SRHS. Four sites or stations were selected and their coordinates are shown below on the table.

Table 4.3 Coordinates of the four selected SRHS boundary stations.

Station #	Latitude	Longitude
1	6° 39'48.38"S	146° 59'42.02"E
2	6° 39'59.0"S	146°59'41.36"E
3	6°39'48.80"S	146° 59'41.36"E
4	6° 39'47.45"S	146°59'39.21"E

The design of a distribution system will depend on the demand and the cultural practices related to the use of water in a particular community, for example a heavy farming community will demand greater quantity of water for farming purposes in addition to domestic use. So that pipe sizing, method of distribution (gravity flow or pumping) will also influence the design and the cost. Given the subsistent nature of most PNG communities most of the cost for SRHS distribution will be borne by government, private sector and NGO'S in the short to medium term. This cost will only be recoverable in the long term after the community has evolved through an integrated process of training and development. The avenues for cost recovery overtime will be through development of the human resources, who

will have the capacity to work meaningful jobs, which allows them to contribute directly and indirectly to the financial development of the country. This is bound to see improvement in the wealth of the society and the spin offs will be pay back.

Hence, the accurately demarcated points for future reference and simulation purposes with the potential to implement the proposal, if funding becomes available within the timeframe of the study. **Figure 4.3** below shows demarcated segment of a plot of land adjacent to the rainforest habitat known as The Garden.

Figure 4.3 SRHS site identification report

Site Mapping, Setting Ground Profile and Pegging Out SRHS Site

After locating the four stations, the sites were cleared with machete and the points were manually ID, points were double checked using the GPS reading. Every reading taken from the GPS instrument was recorded as a double check for accuracy. After measurement was correctly done, precise location of the points was identified and the pegs were placed. The pegs were established to easily identify points using stout robust pegs fixed and secured in soil and painted with a bright coloured permanent paint. Following the setting of the pegs in place a taping checks was done to verify accuracy from the coordinates of the GPS, the

demarcated segment of a plot of land adjacent to the rainforest habitat known as The Garden was created. This can be seen in **Figure 4.4**, where established easily identifiable points using stout robust pegs fix and secure in soil and painted with a bright coloured permanent paint.

Figure 4.4 Identification pegs fixed in position.

Topography in relation to gravity feed distribution system

When designing a SRHS system the type of survey needed for planning the pipeline depends on the route's topography. If the route's topography (see SRHS prototype site topography in **figure 4.5**) is noticeably downward, then a survey could be performed with reasonable accuracy for a gravity distribution system.

This concept is in sync with proposal for the SRHS system in that, it is this gravity fed method that will be employed to eliminate the need for electric power to operate the system. Where the terrain does not present a sloping site the water towers which are essentially elevated tanks will be used to aid in the gravity distribution to communities.

A distinctive choice of velocities in distribution pipes is between 0.5 and 1.0 m/s, occasionally up to 2 m/s. The hydraulic gradients usually range between 1 and 5 m/km,

occasionally up to 10 m/km. In case of smaller pipes, $D < 50$ mm, the hydraulic gradient can even be higher due to the relative higher proportion of head loss that occurs in a smaller pipe. The pressure criterion is dependent on topographic (See typical topography map in **figure 4.6**) conditions, availability of water at the source and overall condition of the pipes. The minimum pressures should not drop below 5-10 mean water column (mwc). In larger distribution areas where water scarcity is not an issue, the minimum pressures can range between 20 and 30 mwc above street level, where there are house connections. This is sufficient for supply of 2-3 storey buildings. (Trifunovic, 2012)

Figure 4.5. SRHS Site Topography

Figure 4.6 Typical Topographic map of Papua New Guinea University of Technology

Source: Commonly used by student and staff at UNITECH (Estate management department UNITECH)

4.4.12 Strategic framework for implementation of SRHS benefitting communities

The policy framework for SRHS is conceptualized as an action plan to be implemented at the national level, within a common harmonized framework to ensure that the overall coordination of the policy framework is in agreement with the country's water resources management sector. The overall approach of the policy framework will include: community awareness, capacity building at community level, infrastructural development, administration, monitoring and evaluation. The monitoring and evaluation section is purposely being built into the policy framework given the typical human and financial constraints in many of the lead national and local government agencies that are envisaged to carry out the monitoring and evaluation requirements of the framework.

The interventions within each constituency are predicted to lead to the creation of a facilitating environment which will nurture greater investment in sustainable rainwater harvesting as a viable water supply supplemental mechanism to the existing national water supply regime. The extent to which national governments, and by extension the communities, re-adopts what is a traditional practice in most areas to harvest rainwater with proper guidance, will depend greatly on how much support is provided at the institutional level. It is proposed that the national agency with lead responsibility for water will be charged with the responsibility of advocating the national components of the Policy framework.

Each concern in the policy approach is defined, along with the key actions, verifiable gauges that need to be checked, and the projected results. It is proposed that with the ratification of the national government, the local government and the water sector will be the country's principal team to coordinate the accomplishment of establishing SRHS in a coherent and principled way with the guidelines set out in this document as continuous capacity building. These local government agencies will seek to create global rainwater harvesting partnership with countries with similar characteristics and other non-government agencies such as UNESCO for rainwater harvesting technology transfer and training aids for communities where possible. Through this framework, the idea is to seek placement within the highest-level of political agenda to ensure commitment and translation to national development agendas. This policy initiative is framed against the background of promoting adaptation measures and building resilience in communities in the context of water security; in consideration of the potential effects of climate change and climate variability; as evidenced by the impacts of several destructive forces of nature in Papua New Guinea and the region. The intent of this framework is to ultimately provoke a National action plan for a policy driven sustainable rainwater harvesting network.

Public awareness to sustainable rainwater harvesting systems: Rainwater harvesting is one of the commonly practiced methods of water supply throughout the Pacific Region even before the introduction of potable supply and distribution networks; and it is still practiced widely as many areas still don't have access to conventional distribution networks. However, little is known about sustainable rainwater harvesting, and the idea of a policy driven sustainable rainwater harvesting system anywhere in the region is new. As a result, the traditional approach still applies and in most cases is woefully unsustainable. Therefore, the focus is on crafting a new image for SRHS on the premise of building resilience in the

community especially in an environment where there is increasing pressure on scarce water resources and increase the awareness of the communities to the potential of SRHS as an alternate water source. This will be framed against the backdrop of ensuring some measure of security of supply in a post-disaster circumstance and during prolonged drought conditions when demand surpasses supply. The experiences noted in the study area are reflected throughout PNG and will no doubt help galvanize favourable public perception. The threats posed by climate change are of concern and will be an issue that will need to be confronted over the coming decades and the public need to be alerted to these facts upon the awareness program built in the policy to be done prior to the implementation of SRHS.

Improve on investment in sustainable rainwater harvesting systems: Investing in rainwater harvesting systems has been constrained to some degree by the cost associated with construction of catchment, storage and utilities systems. Although there are general awareness among government and private sector that this approach could remedy some of the water trouble that are now experienced by residents especially in inaccessible areas. Notwithstanding, they are typically unwilling to invest in appropriate measures to capture rainwater, on account of cost.

The public education strategy must focus on consideration of the long-term advantages of SRHS. While the initial investment cost may be relatively frontloaded, foregoing investment can outweigh the investment in the long-term. The policy framework is gear towards the wider communities especially those in difficult terrains who can least afford it. To support better health conditions, better quality water, and continuous supply in sufficient quantity. This framework noted that the question of the end user contribution to the investment and how the invested sum will be recouped. While it is a fact that government have a fundamental function to supply the basics to the populous, this study promulgate an action to a participatory approach by the community. Meaning, at the onset given the menial income of most of these communities they may not be able to contribute financially.

In which case a voluntary labour equivalent must be incorporated at project development stage and accounted for at project implementation stage. The action plan of participation will be continuously enforced through community action groups and committee monitored by local government agencies and water sector groups. The end of which is expected to achieve full participation through purpose design tariff arrangement. Whereby, operators can realize significant cost savings overtime and a greater attitude of accountability

and acceptance of social responsibilities. The new attitude of accountability is projected to translate into other positives for example; water conservation particularly when the supply is under stress at peak demand during the dry season. New interest by other in a policy driven sustainable rainwater harvesting systems, which will mean new investment and the replication in new communities will see new attitude to SRHS, thus direct cost saving to the user and other stakeholders. Ultimately, contributes to continued service provision which is of direct economic interest to service providers and developers of the SRHS.

Support SRHS as a sustainable alternative measure for conventional potable water

Conventional water sources in water-stressed areas quite often fails at the onset of drought. Consequently, the situation becomes a matter to be remediated by the water agency at which time it requires immediate and significant resources. In addition, water resources, resources such as vehicle, fuel, pumps and manpower. This will typically result in water utilities also rationing the volume of water supplies to particular communities during the dry season with resultant interruptions for portions of the day, and in extreme cases, for several days. The situation is worse for communities that are situated at the most difficult areas of the water distribution network. Residents and business operators in these areas are familiar with the difficulties associated with water shortages and will tend to be those who will readily accept the implementation of a policy driven SRHS. The Program will use such water-stressed areas as prime demonstrations, drawing on the added dimension of implementing a sustainable rainwater harvesting system as an alternative or support to the regular water system. Emphasis will be placed on general water conservation as part of on-going education with all partners in the water sector but the implementation of a SRHS will have a welcoming impact on the water situation in those communities in general.

Best practices, health and sanitation of Sustainable rainwater harvesting systems

Generally, there is a lack of a coordinated framework for administration of community catchment systems operated in many areas. It is the common perception that the systems are the responsibility of the State and that the State should take full responsibility for their operation and maintenance. The issue of sanitation needs to be addressed in two areas: (1) proper management of community SRHS through regulated regimes. (2) Encouragement of good practices by community constituents' in areas where the communal SRHS lack state resources and low level of involvement of communities in management. It will lead to a

situation of poor maintenance with potentially serious health consequences. The community action group and SRHS committee reporting to the local government and water sector will take charge in the best interest of all. This group will take the necessary measures to safeguard the communities' water as it passes through the various components of the SRHS process, thereby averting the introduction of possible contaminants, in the tank. These action groups will see that simple techniques to treat the water to ensure reduction in bacterial counts are carried out at all times as set out in the water quality procedure manual. The awareness strategy among these groups will therefore, need to address all aspects of management and maintenance of the SRHS with technical support from local government and the water agency. The setup of the action group/committee with technical representation from the various agencies will be equipped with a clear understanding on the roles of the various stakeholders in provision of quality water from SRHS communal systems. This outline seeks to define and synthesize, so that all involved recognize the integration of social and economic dimensions associated with management of common-property resources, as is the case with operation and management of the SRHS.

SRHS public and stakeholders' workshops and seminars supported by water agency and local government

In the first year monthly seminar and workshop must be conducted as a part of sensitization strategy of the SRHS. Thereafter, quarterly SRHS workshop will be organized, which will operate for the lifecycle of the system. These workshops and seminars will target community members, the private and commercial sectors, with involvement of policy makers who will assist in promotion of the SRHS and create the environment necessary to further investment. These seminars and workshops will need to be tailored to ensure maximum receptivity depending on the audience. It is anticipated that relevant educational materials developed by various government and non-government agencies will form core resources for facilitators.

Propagation of technical materials

During the Project reconnaissance and site investigation for the implementation of the SRHS it is mandatory that in addition to public awareness that a SRHS is proposed for the community. Technical material should be made available to the general public for consultation where specific information on the design and construction of the SRHS

concluded with the community's expectation of the facility; social and cultural harmony which will encourage better acceptance of the system. A Handbook and technical brochures should be developed local government and water sector. This handbook must be written in basic format and easy to read. The exercise will be based on information gleaned from pilot prior. This will be designed to furnish users with appropriate information for various types of applications. The Handbook is regarded a work in progress; as new lessons are learnt and new technologies introduced, it will be updated. The Handbook and brochures are being made available in limited copies but will be available in Adobe portable document format (pdf) on local government and water agency websites at no cost.

Stakeholder evaluation on level of awareness pre - and post-implementation of SRHS seminars

Pre-evaluation must be carried out, twenty eight days prior to commencement of project construction to facilitate last minute adjustment highlighted by community or any other stakeholder. Post evaluation at the end of the first quarter after the commissioning into operation. An essential feature of the SRHS program is the system in the first instance as a public outreach campaign, in which case a systematic assessment of impact on benefiting communities will shape the path for the future. Targeted communities should be polled periodically to determine the extent to which they may have adopted to SRHS practices as a result of the public education initiatives. The local government, water agency, arm of government for health, along with environment agency should partner in this regard.

Advance and augment national capabilities in developing, design, build and operate SRHS

Sustainable rainwater harvesting systems are not a common practice in Papua New Guinea and there is generally low capacity in the area of proper design and construction of SRHS systems due to the deficiency in skill artisan trades personnel. This finding emerged out of a recent study that involved interviewing various industries in PNG and the institutions indicated that several industries are dissatisfied with the level of knowledge and skills possessed by contemporary Technical Vocation Education and Training (TVET) graduates, who seriously lacks the requisite artisans' skills. (Maino, 2013).

This is compounded by the lack of long histories of using communal rainwater systems and is familiar with their construction. Therefore, in the absence of a well-constructed SRHS, then a range of problems will arise, and in extreme cases compromising the integrity of building foundations. Capacity needs to be developed in application of SRHS technologies for communal uses particularly in large scale distribution network, with emphasis on enhancing efficiencies in skill craftsmanship. This plan proposes to train specialists in the technical craftsmanship involved in the implementation of the SRHS. Training will also be necessary for public service professionals in local government and water sector departments and other technical sections of relevant agencies to equip them with the necessary advisory and technical support tools for transfer to communities' stakeholders. It is anticipated that associations of professional engineers in Papua New Guinea will be key partners in support of coordinated capacity development.

Train communities in management and operation of Sustainable rainwater harvesting systems

The SRHS mandate advocates to train residents of the communities to carry out key management and operation functions of the sustainable rainwater harvesting communal system. Notwithstanding, the community is not excused from the collective responsibility of the general upkeep and security of the SRHS. Residents should protect the system from intrusion of livestock to stray on the catchment surfaces and not allow vegetation to grow on the catchment surfaces that will cause serious damage and affect the quality of the water. The community will not pay for water obtained from these communal systems in the first 5 years of operation, but will meaningfully participate in the non-technical upkeep. This will include: bushing, painting and minor repairs to physical structure. After the 5 years elapse, the SRHS monitoring committee appointed by the local government and water agency will design a manageable flat tariff arrangement to match the income of the community; to foster an attitude of responsibility among community constituents. The strategy will call for awareness-building and strengthen capacity within beneficiary communities to play a collaborative role along with support agencies in management and maintenance of communal water supplies.

Train Technical professions in sustainable rainwater harvesting systems control

The policy framework in this study is crafted on the premise of the proposal within this study. That is “Sustainable Rainwater Harvesting Systems - SRHS – in Lae City – A model for Papua New Guinea” as the system spread throughout the provinces and communities of PNG. Training of professionals in SRHS control is a recurring need in all facets of water resource management of the SRHS program and must always be kept in the forefront of development planning for the program. Training professionals in SRHS control lends significant value to the crafting of additional appropriate policy and incentives. Create the enabling environment to facilitate investment in sustainable rainwater harvesting program in the country by the private sector and civil society. The Program will call for a series of technical exchanges between local, public and private sectors professionals, with other professionals in the region. Some of these exchanges may take the form of in-country technical seminars and workshops while others may involve travel to neighbouring countries and where necessary, outside the region, to gain first-hand insights on best practices that are relevant to specific needs. Given the cost involved in this undertaking, assistance will need to be sought from mainstream government through partners such as the local international non-government organizations; this idea will contribute resources to facilitate some of the envisaged activities.

Seminars: Special seminar series for selected community constituents from the action groups and committee, contractors, local government, water agencies, private sector and senior policy makers should be organized to sensitize them on practical issues related to implementation (operation, maintenance and quality testing/monitoring) of SRHS systems. These seminars can be organized and tailored depending on the target sector. A training-of-trainers program should be considered. Local professional engineer associations should be regarded as playing key roles, particularly in reaching out to the private sector. The policy framework guidelines developed in this study for SRHS should be used as a key tool in structuring these seminars.

Regional exchange: As a part of the capacity building strategy exchanges should be organized where practical, to send professionals to respective countries and have reciprocal visits to regional and other relevant countries to exchange experiences in sustainable rainwater harvesting applications. Notably some of the other South Pacific Islands have made strides in establishing some form of Sustainable rainwater harvesting systems in some areas,

from technical advancements to policy and governance. These countries have similar geography as Papua New Guinea and face similar community and water challenges making them ideal for partnering in exchange program.

Develop capacity to manage and maintain community sustainable rainwater harvesting systems: The sustainable management of SRHS, presents special challenges given the fact that they serve multiple households. Unlike a single-dwelling RWH systems where the owner has sole responsibility for that system, community systems are ‘owned and managed’ either under public sector (state or local municipal) or cooperative arrangements. In a low-investment environment these SRHS systems may not be adequately maintained or operated, on account of loose institutional arrangements, non-adherence to best practices and lack of systems that ensure the value of water is paid for on a long term basis and is returned to management of the system. In that case of responsibility for upkeep of the system, it will entirely be up to the local government, water agency, authority invested in the community action group and committee members who are empowered to manage the SRHS as set out in the policy framework. Additionally, the tenet therefore proposes that the situation with respect to management of the SRHS such as those should be address by building capacity amongst key members in the community action group, who will actively contribute to management in collaboration with the other institutional stakeholders. Emphasis will also be placed on the formulation strategies to ensure that the schedule quantity and quality of water supply is guaranteed on a continuous basis.

SRHS conceptualization for specific location and funding procurement strategies: following development of project concepts, for the specific locale, an action plan will be initiated and developed by the local government in conjunction with the water agency.

The full project process will be already broadly developed based on the needs involve: Site investigation and reconnaissance and consultation with beneficiaries and stakeholders, design modification and construction detail plans, submit budget based on design concept for funding arrangement through finance ministry, or any donor NGO or private sector group. Execute procurement plan and process base on government procurement procedures to select contractor. Arrange ground breaking ceremony, provide technical and financial oversight and management for the life cycle of the project and supervise commissioning into service on completion to begin operations. The relevant technical and

advisory agencies and ministries, political representative should play lead roles in all phase along with potential beneficiaries and supported by ministries of finance.

Operational strategies: Rainwater harvesting have been done in Papua New Guinea with basic roof top collection methods and so managing a communal sustainable rainwater harvesting system will require some specific operational guiding principles relevant to the sustainability of the SRHS. Those areas considered to require coherent guiding principles are: Land uses, watershed management, topography, soil condition, water treatment, maintenance, and storage and water delivery strategies. The flexibility that is anticipated from each community selected for SRHS, will reap tremendous benefit in regard to continuous water supply. Although the concept of sustainable rainwater harvesting maybe new. The local government, water agency, traditional administrative and other bureaucratic and legal structures within government, will be instrumental in pivoting these concerns and working them through with all stakeholders in the most amicable ways.

Land use: In the Pacific a variety of customary land tenure systems have been practiced over decades, often sharing similarities such as communal ownership and spiritual association with the land. More importantly, customary land laws (and therefore customary land tenure) and constitutional land laws are currently being recognized and applied simultaneously, where the latter seldom reflect customary land tenure principles and are often regarded as the ultimate land law. The parallel recognition and application of both land tenure systems, without any facilitative links between them, gives rise to a “grey area” where conflicts often arise. Consequently, the customary land tenure systems in the Pacific have often been criticized for being obstacles to economic development. The way forward is to ensure that the interests and benefits arising from the utilization of land resources are equitably distributed between local communities and entrepreneurs(UNESCO, 2008).

SRHS Land Acquisition strategy

The acquisition of land therefore, for SRHS will follow normal land purchase practices using state apparatus to avert any inequity in the process, however, where customary land is the only alternative a long term lease arrangement negotiation with the community traditional administration, for a minimum lease in tranches of 5 years, renewable or pending sale agreement will apply. The topography of the land should be moderately sloped and soil condition firm enough for artificial sloping infrastructure such as columns if

necessary. In a number of areas throughout PNG where the SRHS is proposed to be promulgated are relative flat land, in which the sloping requirement for the SRHS will have to be achieved using a structural framework of isolated column systems for the catchment support and elevation needs. As a result, a determination of the soil type and soil integrity will have to be carried out using laboratory test and verification to ensure that sound structural design parameters are established before implementation.

Maintenance: The sustainability of rainwater harvesting system will depend heavily on maintenance which is very important and quite often neglected on a communal system, if a maintenance framework is not set out in the procedures. The amount of maintenance required by a basic, community centered SRHS catchment system involves the annual inspection of the catchment, conveyance system, mosquito screening and the removal of any leaves, dirt or other matter, and the cleaning of the storage tank. In seasonal climates, where catchment surface may become dirty and dusty in dry seasons, the cleaning and sweeping of the catchment, conveyance and storage tank before the first major rains is of paramount importance to guarantee quality water supply for the life cycle of the SRHS.

The policy framework requires that the various components of the SRHS systems are regularly cleaned. A simple schedule of maintenance should form an integral part of overall operation of the system. A part from the first step in maintenance should include the day to day cleaning of the components. A half yearly inspection based on a maintenance check list, indicating defects at different stages and a repair sequencing plan in order of severity and all defects identified must be effected in 28 days. If these possible problems are not identified and necessary repairs are not performed, then the system will cease to provide a reliable, good-quality supply of water.

The following timetable of maintenance and management requirements gives a basis for monitoring checks:

Rainy season: the entire SRHS system (catchment, conveyance, pipes, screens, filter and overflow) should be visually checked after each rain, and cleaned after every dry period greater than one month.

Yearly checks: The water tank should regularly be checked annually for leaks and cracks, which need to be repaired. Only small weeping leaks, which may occur on first filling the tank, need not be repaired since they usually seal themselves. If there is any doubt about the

presence of organic contaminants in the water source, the water must be chlorinated. Water must not be allowed to leak from tap fittings. Not only will this waste water, but it may also provide a basis for algae growth in the sink or drainage system and lead to development of bacteria, which form hygiene risk.

4.4.13 Schedule maintenance

The following section provides a schedule of operation and maintenance tasks for storage tanks and associated catchments and conveyance.

- Catchment surfaces and conveyance have to be kept free of bird droppings.
- Inflow screen and filters must be regularly cleared of leaves and other rubbish.
- The mosquito screening on the overflow pipe should be checked regularly during the rainy season and renewed if necessary.
- Unless there is some automatic means of diverting the first flush of water in a storm away from the tank, the inflow screen should be sealed from the tank during dry periods. Then a short period after rain begins and the system has been flushed, it should be so the water flows into the tank.
- The water level in the tank should be measured once a week using a graduated stick. During dry periods, the drop of water level should correspond with water consumption. If not, there might be some leakage.

Sporadic and annual tasks:

The following yearly tasks will require technical support, are important for the maintenance of the SRHS system:

- At the end of the dry season, any leaks that have been noticed should be repaired.
- The catchment surface, conveyance, supporting brackets and inflow/outflow pipes need to be checked and repaired where necessary.
- All filtration systems should be washed with clean water or replaced if defective.
- Removal of deposits from the bottom of the tank is periodically necessary and should be done annually if it is deemed to be bad to affect water quality.
- After repairs have been carried out inside the tank and after deposits have been cleared out, the interior should be scrubbed down with a solution of 1 cup (75 ml) of

5% chlorine bleach to 45 litres of water. After scrubbing, leave the tank for 36 hours and finally flush it out with water before using it again to store water.

4.5 Computation of water catchment

The foundation for all rainwater harvesting computation is the formula rainfall x catchment area x runoff coefficient = water supply, where the most significant variation is identified by the variation in runoff coefficient providing the rainfall quantity is accounted for properly. In SRHS scenario even after taking into account the significant runoff coefficient (0.9), during the rainy season large quantity of water base on the storage analysis would be collected. It was also found that it would be possible to harvests during the dry season would be negligible, however, months of moderate to heavy rainfall could still produce significant amounts of water that could be managed and distributed cautiously to have continuous supply throughout the year. The quality of management depends on how well operators adopt best practices in rainwater distribution of rainwater, policy adoption and enforcement and strategic approach to the ongoing operations of such systems.

4.6 Rainfall analysis for Lae City and UNITECH Campus

The software (SamSamwater – Climate tool) was used to establish an average rainfall pattern for UNITECH campus, which will help to ascertain accurately the potential annual volume of rainwater that can be harvested by the SRHS. In most developing countries records kept of climate activities are difficult to obtain and thus the need for a support data base on climate activities to implement rainwater harvesting systems. Therefore, software accesses satellite data base of climate activities that is made available through the online connection. This tool uses a worldwide data set of monthly climate to provide estimate of climatic conditions for which no observation are available or are limited. The results of required data input in the software are shown below (**Table 4.4**).

Table 4.4 Average precipitations (in mm or liters per m²) for the location Papua New Guinea University of Technology campus Lae.

Month	Rainfall (mm)
January	255
February	218
March	261
April	270
May	243
June	254
July	301
August	309
September	276
October	282
November	229
December	266
Year	3163

Figure 4.7 Average precipitations graphically calculated using Samsamwater – Climate tool on Papua New Guinea University of Technology Lae.

Knowing the specific rainfall pattern at the particular location for the implementation of the SRHS is vital to crafting a design parameter for the system. Pivotal information is derived to develop a storage capacity base on the availability of water in space and time, the table below set out the basic design parameters for a SRHS. The parameters will vary from

location to location due to minor changes in key design parameters. As such aspects of the design parameters will not be employed everywhere in the same manner.

4.7 Analysis of demand and storage design

Accounts of the monthly pattern of water usage data were obtained from UNITECH admin Office. The data collected show the usage pattern from 2012-2015. By analysing this four year pattern an average water consumption level was arrived at. Information from this data assisted in the determination of the volume of water supplied by Water PNG. In order to recommend a reduction in the volume supplied by Water PNG to accommodate the infusion of SRHS water in the system. It is estimated that Water PNG supplies 8.2 Million litres to the campus per year. The SRHS is proposing to reduce that volume by 30% which equates to an estimated 2.5 Million litres annually. When this is translated into kina figures it will show significant savings that can be utilize in other areas of the University's budget to offset other expenses. The water consumption pattern at UNITECH is shown below (**Figure 4.8**).

Figure 4.8 Graph showing Papua New Guinea University of Technology campus water consumption pattern.

The software SamSamwater- Rainwater Harvesting Tool was used to develop the following demand requirement and storage capacity based on the runoff coefficient and the

population to be supplied. The rainwater harvesting tool is very efficient in computing the demand and storage parameters as it bases its calculation on the optimum rain periods to accurately carry out this analysis.

The total population of the UNITECH campus is estimated to be 5,415 and their water consumption pattern is as indicated. The map in **(Figure 4.9)** shows the location of UNITECH as identified in the software to ascertain precise rainfall data using satellite interface.

Figure 4.9 Papua New Guinea University of Technology Lae, location on the rainfall data map.

The **table 4.5** shows the general parameters in the computation and analysis of the SRHS and give details of the sequence of activities involve in the design process including the runoff coefficient also shown in **table 4.6** of the system. Starting with catchment showing details of how it is sized to capture the volume of water required. The storage calculation parameters demonstrate the various areas involve in the development of optimum storage capacity to fit the demand. Another area that is of great importance to the design process of such system is the utility, in the utility room is where the water quality control is administered, the regulation of the quantity of water to be distributed and the general maintenance of the system is done from this point. The distribution outlet to the network is pivoted from this point where it is controlled and all mains and laterals emanates from this distribution point.

Table 4.5 Design parameters for SRHS.

DESIGN	DESCRIPTION REQUIREMENT
CATCHMENT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Open space free from large tree ● Slope minimum 15° ● Sizing catchment using basic equation : $W_s = A \times Q \times C_r$ ($W_s =$ Water Supply) [Equation 1]
STORAGE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The size storage tank using basic equation : ● $Q = R \times A \times C_r$ <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. ($Q =$ quantity of rainfall in m^3), 2. ($R =$ average rainfall in mm), 3. ($A =$ area of catchment in m^2), 4. ($C_r =$runoff coefficient). Rainfall the last10 years. [Equation 2]
UTILITY	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Water quality control (Chlorine treatment) ● Distribution regulation ● Maintenance
DISTRIBUTION	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Distributing will be done by Gravity Supply : (a) Gravity Supply - Residual Pressure : (Darcy-Weisbachformula). $P_{\text{residual}} \text{ (mWG)} = H \text{ (m)} - \Delta P \text{ (m)}$ [Equation 3] (b) Gravity Supply - Maximum Capacity: (Hydraulic calculation of a gravity fed system . $P_{\text{static}} \text{ (mWG)} = H \text{ (m)}$ [Equation 4]

Table 4.6 Runoff coefficient for various catchment types

Source: Caribbean rainwater harvesting handbook 2009

Type of catchment	Coefficients
Roof catchments	
Tiles	0.8 - 0.9
Corrugated metal sheets	0.7 - 0.9
Ground surface coverings	
Concrete	0.6 - 0.8
Brick pavement	0.5 - 0.6
Untreated ground catchments	
Soil on slopes less than 10 percent	0.1 - 0.3
Rocky natural catchments	0.2 - 0.5

To adequately support a population of 5,415 as at UNITECH campus, the computation determined that the total amount of water to meet the demand of the population will not be totally met by rainwater harvesting alone. However, given the rainfall potential of the location it is worthwhile to construct a rainwater harvesting system to support the water demand of the population in part.

Base on the population water demand and the projected rainfall intensity over time in that location a sustainable rainwater harvesting system can support satisfactorily, storage of 364,800 litres (364.8m³) per day, which is an estimated 30% of the total demand of UNITECH campus.

4.8 Rainfall projection

The rainfall graph in **Figure 4.10** shows that the average rainfall at UNITECH campus varies between 217.9 mm in the driest months (February) and 309.3 mm in the wettest month (August). Hence, the total annual rainfall in an average year is 3163 mm.

Figure 4.10 Monthly rainfalls for an average year calculated using Samsamwater – Rainwater harvesting tool for Papua New Guinea University of technology campus Lae.

4.9 Water Availability

A concrete catchment surface has a runoff coefficient of 0.9, which means that 90% of the rains can be harvested. Base on this runoff coefficient and a catchment surface area of 3977.1 m²a volume of 779,949 litres (using the formula: $W_s = A \times Q \times C_r$ [$W_s =$ Water Supply] 217.9 mm x 3977.1 m² x 0.9) of water can be collected in the driest month (February) and 1107105 litres (using the formula: $W_s = A \times Q \times C_r$ [$W_s =$ Water Supply] 309.3 mm x 3977.1 m² x 0.9) in the wettest month (August). As such, the yearly amount of water that can be collected from the concrete catchment surface at SRHS study area UNITECH is 11320500 litre (11321m³) in an average year.

4.10 Water Demand

The water demand is 100300 litres per day, which equals to an estimated 3009000 litres (36609.5 m³) per year. The amount of water that can be collected from the concrete catchment surface (11321m³) is less than the water demand (36609 m³). Thus, only a part of the water demand can be fulfilled using rainwater harvesting system. The graph in (**Figure 4.11**) shows the water availability and water demand throughout the year.

Figure 4.11 Water availability and water demand throughout the year calculated using Samsamwater – Rainwater harvesting tool for Papua New Guinea University of Technology Campus Lae.

4.11 Required Storage

Planning distribution and regulation strategy for a water system small or large, rainwater harvesting or conventional harvesting require a clear knowledge of available water storage at specific times. So that there can be precision planning for the distribution method to be employed. The SRHS for UNITECH employed that same accurate analysis, for that reason in carrying out the analysis it was pivotal to ascertain accurately the required storage.

The total amount of water that can be collected from the concrete catchment surface 11320500 litres which is not enough to fulfill the total yearly water demand of 36609500 litres. However, it is prudent to construct the rainwater harvesting system. With a storage capacity of 364800 litres (364.8 m³) and the sustainable rainwater harvesting infrastructure will provide 31015 litres of water per day which is 30% of the total demand. The graph in **(Figure 4.12)** gives an analysis of the proposed water levels in the storage tank based on the rainfall pattern. The storage reservoir will be full and then slowly drain until it is almost empty at the end of June.

Figure 4.12 Water levels throughout the year in proposed storage reservoir calculated using Samsamwater – Rainwater harvesting tool for Papua New Guinea University of Technology Lae.

Wet and dry years

The design analysis for SRHS in this exercise is based on the average monthly rainfall. The actual rainfall differs from month to month and year to year. The amount of available water and filling of the storage tank might therefore, be different and change from year to year.

Against that background when designing and constructing sustainable rainwater harvesting system it is important that wet and dry years are taken into account and incorporates a marginal factor of safety respectively. This factor of safety will be determined on the ground as each rainfall scenario presents their own unique sets of parameters.

Dry year Scenario : During a dry year, there is less rain to fill the system. The system can provide a smaller amount of water compared to an average year. All rain is stored, so constructing a larger storage capacity wont help.

Wet year Scenario : During the wet year there is more water available and constructing a larger storage will increase the water availability situation and with an increase storage the rainwater harvesting potential can increase significantly and could provide a greater percentage to meet the total water demand.

Rainfall is very dynamic therefore it is of significant value to understand the current climate updates and future forecast, to efficiently manage a sustainable rainwater harvesting system and distribution operations.

Distribution:

Distribution will be done using gravity flow from the storage reservoir to a water tower and infused into the University campus distribution network. See **Figure 4.13** below.

Figure 4.13 Elevation profile from proposed storage reservoir to water tower.

Ground profile

The main transmission line will transport water from the SRHS storage reservoir to the water tower, which will be located east of the storage reservoir within proximity of the Catholic chapel and the eastern entrance to the University campus. The ground profile of the proposed main transmission line was done to develop an accurately elevation along the route of pipe travel and establish a height at both points. After completion of the transmission line elevation profile, the next step was to characterize the gravity parameters to be accounted for. The basic flow parameters are:

- Flow velocity
- Pipe size
- Flow rate
- Pressure loss due to frictional drag

Gravity flow calculation from SRHS storage reservoir to water tower

The Darcy-Weisbach formula:

ΔH = head loss (mwc)

T = Temperature

L = pipe length (m)

D = pipe diameter (m)

γ = friction factor (-)

v = the mean velocity in the pipe (m/s)

Equation [1]

The Reynolds number indicates the flow regime

where: $Re = \frac{vD}{\nu}$

v = the mean velocity in the pipe (m/s)

D = pipe diameter (m)

ν = kinematic viscosity (m^2/s)

Equation [2]

The calculation accounts for the activities from the SRHS reservoir to the water tower. However, infusing new water into the existing water network can be problematic with regards to water quality controls at all times as is required on a distribution system. Therefore, some measures must be implemented to regulate this situation and a mixing chamber with a tablet chlorinator booster unit will fix this problem. This chamber is a simple concrete covered tank fixed on the inline of existing live main transmission line and the new pipeline inlet to the chamber with the requisite one way valves and on the outlet of the chamber, a tablet chlorinator unit to boost water quality entering the network is installed.

4.12 Elements of the SRHS prototype

The harvesting of rainwater in its widest sense can be defined as the collection of runoff rainwater for domestic water supply, municipal use and environmental management. Water harvesting systems, which harvest runoff from catchment, roofs or ground surfaces fall under the technology of rainwater harvesting. This SRHS study primarily focuses on rainwater harvesting from catchment surfaces at municipal level for domestic purposes, such as drinking, cooking, sand washing and so on.

Concrete catchment surface

The concrete catchment of a sustainable rainwater harvesting system is the surface that receives rainfall directly and drains the water to the system through the inlet canal. The water will, however, pass through the filter bed before entering the storage tank and further treatment will be done before distribution. This level of processing will make it suitable for drinking purposes, since the water quality might not be good enough for drinking straight from the catchment surface. The potential for harmful impurities in the water from catchment surface is due to its susceptibility to droppings from birds, toxic dust from the atmosphere that gather during the dry season etc. Therefore, the final product would have been subjected to a series of treatment such as filtration and chlorination to make it safe for community consumption.

Catchment area Design

The catchment surface area of has a significant impact on both the design and water savings potential of the sustainable rainwater harvesting systems. Generally, it is recommended that the size of the catchment area used for a SRHS should be as large as possible to maximize water savings. Although, sometimes it may not be feasible to utilize all the collected rainwater from the entire catchment area due to excess rain storm which will go to waste if a designed groundwater recharge mechanism is not in place, as is the case with the SRHS.

Catchment Material

All catchment surfaces must have sloping impervious surface to maximize the rainwater collection of a catchment system. While many different texture of catchment surface is used depending on the material available in the specific local and the runoff coefficient required, but great care must be taken to maximize rainwater yield because rainfall is seasonal and rainfall pattern is not fixed. The type of catchment material used by a SRHS can affect: The proportion of rainfall collected during a rainfall occasion, defined as the collection efficiency from the catchment surface; the quality of harvested rainwater. Rainfall collection efficiency cannot be monitored with 100% accuracy, although 1 Litre of runoff can theoretically be collected from each millimetre of rainfall contacting a 1m² surface area; some losses take place following contact with the catchment surface. These losses vary depending upon the type of catchment material and the geometry of the catchment surface

and should be carefully considered when estimating the amount of rainwater that can be collected and utilized by the SRHS. The general losses can be characterized by an initial loss factor (in mm of rainfall) due to the absorbency of the catchment material, and continuous losses (in percentage of rainfall) from wind and leaks in the conveyance network. These losses for various catchment type can be calculated based on the design materials choice using the runoff coefficient which is the percentage rainwater collected from the surface after all the losses are accounted for (Catchment plan).

4.12.1 SRHS storage tank

The storage facility is at the core of the SRHS system. In addition to having the appropriate volume capacity in relation to the catchment area, rainfall conditions and needs, it must be functional, durable and cost-effective in its installation and maintenance. An ideal or ‘universal’ storage tank design does not exist; selection of the type of storage facility ultimately depends on purpose of use, affordability, availability of supplies and materials, and know-how in design and installation. The following are key considerations in design and operation of the storage facility:

- Water-tight construction with a secure cover to keep out insects and other vermin, dirt and sunshine (note, exposure to sunlight will cause algal growth in stored water)
- Screened inlet to prevent particles and mosquitoes from entering the tank;
- Screened overflow pipe to prevent mosquito entry and breeding

Figure 4.14 Plan view of sustainable rain water harvesting system

- Inclusion of a manhole (to permit insertion of a ladder) to allow access for cleaning
- An extraction system that does not contaminate the water during operation (related to tap or outlet pipe for distribution)
- Soak away to prevent spilt water forming standing puddles near the tank (minimize mosquito breeding).

4.12.2 Tank location for SRHS

The location of a storage tank is very significant to the efficient life cycle of the tank, sustainability, functionality, maintenance ability and the operational qualities. In that there are areas that affect locating a tank in negative ways for example the propensity to structural failure cause by the intrusion of tree roots on foundations, earthquakes, landslides and other earth movements. The climatic and soil conditions must also form a critical part of the design conditions. A sustainable rainwater harvesting system as a model for Papua New Guinea will invariably be a municipal system therefore, one of the viable selling points for this system is its aesthetics. As such where ever the system is located it should add appearance value to that community.

4.12.3 Tank materials for SRHS

Generally, any water storage tank can be used in a rainwater harvesting system, though there are some prevailing conditions in particular zones that can influence material choice for storage tank. For example in a disaster prone zone it is prudent to build with robust materials like concrete with extensive designed failure limits. Also, in the aftermath of a disaster, water is the most critical utility to restore first. So that robust water storage would suffer limited or no damage and would be of crucial value to recovery effort, health care and environmental management. In this regard the design material for SRHS storage is primarily concrete. Concrete tanks also provide a very prized advantage in water storage over other tank systems because they neutralize the acidity of harvested rainwater.

Figure 4.16 Plan view of SRHS storage tank.

Figure 4.17 Section through storage tank

4.12.4 Slow Sand Filtration

Slow sand filtration may not only be the cheapest and simplest treatment process to operate and maintain but also the most efficient under appropriate circumstances (Collins et al., 1991). Such filtration can be done either horizontally or vertically and is accomplished by passing raw water slowly - driven by gravity through a medium of graded aggregates. On the surface of the sand bed, a thin biological film develops after some time of ripening. This film consists of active microorganisms and is called filter skin. It is responsible for the bacteriological purification effect. The slow sand filter is therefore also called biological filter.

Mechanisms of Filtration

The principal purification processes taking place during slow sand filtration are:

Sedimentation: The water body sitting on top of the filter bed acts as a settling reservoir. Settleable particles sink to the sand surface.

Mechanical straining: The sand acts as a strainer. Particles too big to pass through the interstices between the sand grains are retained.

Adsorption: The suspended particles and colloids that come in contact with the surface of the sand grains by following the passage of the water are retained by: - adhesion to the biological layer - physical mass attraction, and - electrostatic and electro kinetic attractive forces.

On account of these forces, an agglomerate of opposite charged particles forms within the top layer of sand. This process needs some time of ripening to fully develop. Biochemical processes in the biological layer: - partial oxidation and breakdown of organic substances form water, CO₂ and inorganic salts, - conversion of soluble iron and manganese compounds into insoluble hydroxides which attach themselves to the grain surfaces, - killing of *E. Coli* and of pathogens. Organic substances are deposited on the upper layer of sand, where they serve as a breeding ground and food for bacteria and other types of microorganisms (assimilation and dissimilation). These produce a slimy, sticky, gelatinous film which consists of active bacteria, their wastes and dead cells and partly assimilated organic materials.

The dissimilation products are carried away by the water to greater depth. Similar processes occur there. The bacterial activity gradually decreases with depth. Different types of bacteria are normally found at various depths. Algae can contribute to the breakdown of organic material and bacteria. They can improve the formation of the biological layer (filter skin). In uncovered filters, growth of algae is driven by photosynthesis.

The presence of large amounts of algae in the supernatant reservoir of a filter as shown in **table 4.7**, generally impedes the functioning of the filter. Dead cell material may clog the filter. Increased consumption of oxygen due to the presence of dead cell material increases the possibility that anaerobic conditions will occur. There is always a diurnal variation in the oxygen content due to growth and decay of the algae mass. When algae growth is strong, the algae must be either removed regularly or the filter must be covered. The conditions necessary for those biochemical processes are: - sufficient ripening of the biological layers, - uniform and slow flow of water through the filter, approx. 0.1 to 0.3 m/in, - a depth of the filter bed of 1 m (0.5 m is needed solely for the biochemical process) of specific grain sizes, - sufficient oxygen in the raw water (at least 3 mg/l) to induce biological activity (Prentice, 1998).

4.12.6 Range of Application of Slow Sand Filters According to Raw Water Quality

Table 4.7 Water quality parameters (Prentice, 1998).

Water Quality Parameters	Purification Effects
Bacteria	Pathogenic bacteria and <i>E. Coli</i> removed at 99-99 %*; cysts, helminth-egg and Schistosoma- larvae removed completely.
Viruses	Complete removal
Organic substances	Complete removal
Color	Partial removal
Turbidity	Significant reduction; turbidity of raw water should not be greater than 10 NTU. At higher turbidity, pretreatment necessary to prevent clogging filter.
Substances difficult to degrade biologically	e.g., detergents, phenol pesticides. Only minor degradation possible.

Rainwater for municipal distribution should be properly disinfected because the microbiological processes and chemical action of filtration are very sensitive to changes in temperature. Both slow down under conditions of low temperature. A reduction in filtration

rate can compensate for this effect. Under protracted cold environments, the filter should be covered to prevent heat loss, and ensuing disinfection should be provided.

Figure 4.18 Section through slow sand filter

4.12.7 Utilities Room

The design philosophy of sustainable rainwater harvesting system utilities room is to allow for operational effectiveness and functional distribution links between the catchment, storage and distribution network. To be a secure area where basic spare parts are stored, it

also serves to house network appurtenances such as control valves and chlorination equipment.

The utilities area is design with comfortable working space, easy access to equipment in an effort to make regular maintenance encouraging as essential aspect of the operation of the SRHS and its sustainability throughout its life cycle.

Figure 4.19. Plan view of utilities room.

Figure 4.20 Left elevation of utilities room.

4.12.8 Elevation profile

The elevation profile of a sustainable rainwater harvesting system defines the collection potential of a catchment surface. The slope of land or the artificial slope created will be the angle at which the runoff occurs. Normally a slope of not more than 15° for rainwater catchment surface can encourage greater level of splashing and interferes with filtration rate and cause great losses. When the runoff water gushes too quickly on the filter at a rate faster than the filtration process then overflow will occur at the inlet canal of the catchment. Therefore, it is important in site selection and implementation of all ground based or hillside catchment that topographic points are established and fixed as in the case of the SRHS site for this study.

Due to the need for a graphical appreciation a composite profile should be represented at design phase as in figure showing sloping steepness of the catchment and its connection to the other elements of the system, like the storage tank and utilities room. The Slope steepness of the SRHS was determined using a handheld GPS unit and the data used in the design and drawing development showing angles preferable for runoff harvesting from open areas.

4.12.9 Site selection

Determining the slope really begins at the preliminary selection of SRHS site suitable to meet the objectives of the study. This is critical for the success of the study and is dependent upon several factors including soil condition, topography, and also types of facilities that can be accommodated for harvesting rainwater , whether a hillside aptly slope or require minimum cut to fit system, or an artificial sloping catchment is needed to be designed.

At the site selection stage the decision as to potential size that is possible in that particular location should be established, sloping potential and placement of all elements, to ensure that the system can handle the runoff from the catchment surface in severe storms, all sections (drainage and piping) must be appropriately sized and sloped to promote the optimum drainage of rainwater from catchment to storage to distribution. When sizing pipes and other parts of the SRHS, it is important to consider what proportion of the catchment surface a particular section of the network is handling. In the SRHS case, the storage tank is divided into sections for the collection and conveyance of rainwater in one compartment and filtration and storage for distribution in a separate compartment. This will ensure that the design rate of filtration is achieved before chlorination and distribution.

Figure 4.21 Elevation profiles of the SRHS showing composite view catchment, storage and utilities room.

4.12.10 Chlorine

The use of chlorine to protect drinking water is one of the greatest public health advances in history. Chlorine destroys disease-causing organisms in water and is the most commonly-used disinfectant in all regions of the world. Chlorine's critical role in providing safe drinking water around the globe; Potential health and environmental effects of chlorine and disinfection by-products in treated drinking water; and Considerations for selecting disinfection methods Drinking Water, are essential consideration in the whole treatment process potable water(WCC, 2008).

Tablet Chlorinator

A tablet chlorinator is purpose design chlorination system that operates automatically to promote optimum chlorine contact for safe drinking water as stipulate by the World Chlorine Council. For effective disinfection, there should be a residual concentration of free chlorine of 0.5 mg/L after at least 30 min contact time at pH<8.0.The design of a tablet chlorinator allows flexibility in achieving this arrangement for a sustainable rainwater harvesting system.

The tablet chlorinator system is characterized by a municipal profile for drinking water operations, which is based on a 75mm tablet form of calcium hypochlorite used in combination with unique delivery process that work automatically for potable water purpose. The primary purpose of this technology is a self-contained water sanitizing application. The system offers a very safe and cost effective method of treating water.

Advantages of tablet chlorinator for SRHS as a model for Papua New Guinea

Papua New Guinea has a multiplicity of terrain type and to replicate a water system throughout the country will require accessories that have flexibilities and portability for ease and simplicity in implementation.

- Unit does not require special handling and safety training for handlers
- It is not bulky, expensive to transport, and degrades rapidly in hot climates

Portability and Ease of Use:

- Tablet chlorinators are manufactured to work simple chlorinator design

- It can meter accurate amounts of chlorine without electricity
- The tablets are portable, concentrated, and have at least 1-year shelf life

Characteristics of Tablet Chlorinator:

- Tablet Chlorination Systems is designed to preserve the integrity of tablets by maintaining a reserve of dry full strength tablets. A side-stream of the water only contacts the bottom layer of tablets for a controlled tablet/water interface
- Erodes at a predictable rate with controlled release tablets
- Capable of delivering 27kgs/ hour of chlorine or treating up to 15,000 litres per minute (~6 MGD) of process water.
- Control chlorine delivery by controlling water flow rate through the chlorinator

How the Tablet Chlorinator System Works:

The System is easy to install and can be integrated into any existing system. Once in place, the system runs simply and efficiently with little to no maintenance.

- a) Side stream flows to the chlorinator.
- b) Flow to the chlorinator is adjusted to control chlorine delivery.
- c) Seventy Five Millimeter tablets sit on top of a sieve plate inside the chlorinator.
- d) Untreated water rises through holes in the sieve plate eroding the bottom of the tablets. The balance of the tablets remains dry.
- e) Water is returned to the system with the appropriate amount of chlorine.

Figure 4.22 Calcium Hypochlorite Tablet Feed System

Source:acc-tab.com

The elements of the sustainable rainwater harvesting system was presented in this study to give a clear understanding of the intricate details of the components which will be formulated as one composite into the prototype. A detail set of working drawings will form part of the appendices for this document (**Appendix B**).

4.13 Prototype

The prototype model in figure (**Figure 4.23**) signifies the final objective of this study on Sustainable Rainwater Harvesting System in Lae City: A Model for Papua New Guinea. The 3 dimensional model which was developed as a composite appreciation of the proposed design, and to give characteristics and shape to a concept that can be physically simulated in all aspect, in real life if funding becomes available even outside of the ambit of this study.

Figure 4.23 Prototype with basic aesthetic layout (88.6 m x 45.1 m).

This is a demonstration of the use of conventional and readily available, safe and easy to work with material such as concrete to create a robust and sustainable water support system for the Papua New Guinea University of Technology Campus. Based on the analysis carried out in earlier chapters the reliability and sustainability of this rainwater harvesting

system's, life will extend beyond the current generation and overtime the University can improve on the size of the system to produce greater volume of water, much more that the 30 percent of its current usage and possibly at some point become the sole source of water for the campus and prevent the excessive use of local water supply.

The intention of the study in developing a model was to demonstrate a physical infrastructure that would appeal to funding interest to participate in the proposal. By building a scaled model that reflected all the boundaries of what a large infrastructure would be both in appearance and purpose. A prototype would have been more apt but funding constraint prevented developing a prototype. However, with the interest generated by the timeliness and relevance of SRHS, it is predicted that the concept will be sold sooner than later and the capacity to build and replicate the SRHS throughout the country will be realized. In order to provide a better balanced and a healthier environment and no doubt reduce the cost of water on campus significantly overtime. So that by using rainwater harvesting and reuse collected rainwater on campus to infuse in the network, then the potential for a reduction in the University water budget becomes a reality.

4.13.1 Prototype Design Features

The prototype design feature follows the designed process flow of SRHS model (**Figure 4.24**).

Figure 4.24 Process diagram for SRHS model.

Watershed: A watershed is an area of land that captures rainfall and other precipitations and funnels it to rivers, streams, wetland and other depositories; under trees and vegetation to manage and preserve a rainforest. Watershed management envisages a systematic and scientific approach towards conservation; to permit the continuous inducement of rainfall that will even allow for the sustainable harvesting of rainwater. It is in light of this understanding, that the watershed area is central to the concept of the SRHS in aligning this study to the rainforest habitat on UNITECH campus.

Catchment: The section of the sustainable rainwater harvesting system from which rainwater is collected a 15° natural drainage area.

Inlet canal: The inlet canal is the component of the SRHS that is the catchment and the filtration unit which serve as a conveyance system to filter.

Filter: The SRHS use a slow sand filter is very useful water treatment process, this filtration process effectively removes organic matter and pathogenic organisms to produce clean and safe water. Slow sand filtration is the best single treatment process that can increase the physical and biological quality of water as well as sand filtering.

Storage device: The SRHS tank positioned the filter unit and the utilities room that allows for pre-treated water storage and treated water storage.

Utilities Room: The component of the SRHS know as the utilites room is located frontmost of the system and housies the system's control devices ,tools and other cleaning and sanitation apparatus including the security of everyday spare parts. The distribution pipe passes through the utilities room before connecting to the network.

Distribution: SRHS treated water is drained slowly through the distribution pipe into the dispensing network to the user community.

4.13.2 Aesthetics

The hallmark of well-organized and well run water system is that it is aesthetically pleasing especially when it's in a neighbourhood or public places. It adds value to properties and set the stage for community members to show appreciation for the system in the community. When designing rainwater harvesting system careful thought must be given to

what the end product will look as the end product is the selling point for consideration on replication elsewhere.

The system must be incorporated in the landscape of reference at all times; the SRHS should never be designed with cumbersome curves and awkward hard to reach crevices and make cleaning and maintenance difficult. As this will discourage maintenances and encourage rapid deterioration that will quickly make the system unserviceable and unsightly.

4.13.3 Construction and Commissioning SRHS

To construct the sustainable rainwater harvesting system, a typical quantity of preliminary construction works will be necessary such as removal of vegetable soil, cutting and filling, setting out, safety set ups and possibly compaction. Trees may have to be strategically removed in keeping with optimum environmental approach for the removal of trees. The ground will have to be excavated to place foundations and needed pipes. This development, for cost effectiveness must be done during dry season and preferably when the University is on holidays if the dry season coincides with a major holiday this time will be best. In the implementation process proper engineering procedures must be employed, so that the proper interpretation and application and design principles can be achieved. A team of well skilled workers should be engaged with appropriate skillset in the artisan trades and should be well motivated for the duration of the project; the combined crew will create a prototype as set out on plan and in the end implement a sustainable rainwater harvesting system.

The idea of a structured approach to the implementation of a SRHS is to prevent as best as possible re-worked on construction technique items due to misread or misinterpretation of drawings.

On completion of the project a formal application to the requisite authorities must be made, who will carry out the technical quality inspection and approval for commissioning into service. This will be followed by a symbolic ceremony in keeping with the community's tradition and all stakeholders should be present, this ceremony represents a formal hand over of the SRHS to the community.

4.13.4 Cost of SRHS Prototype

The estimated cost to develop the prototype is (United States Dollar) \$220,000.00 and may vary from place to place in PNG as different locations may present different circumstances. The estimated cost here quoted is based on current average materials and labor charges in PNG. The cost does not reflect land acquisition charges which would require country wide land pricing average which is beyond the objective of this study. Based on the population water demand and the projected rainfall intensity over time in that location a sustainable rainwater harvesting system can support satisfactorily, storage of 364,800 litres (364.8m³) per day, which is an estimated 30% of the total demand of UNITECH campus.

4.13.5 The SRSH Model

The SRHS model is a proposal that was conceived to be used on the Papua New Guinea University Technology student and staffing community. This parameter of use was employed to facilitate this research project. However, due to financial and time constraint, at the time of study the physically implementation was not practical. Therefore, to ensure that the research paper is properly executed a theoretical model exercise was carried out, which was confirmed using rigorous lab experimental processes. Details are as follows:

The formulae for calculating rainwater harvesting as set out in table 4.5 design parameters for SRHS, includes: (1) Catchment surface - $W_s = A \times Q \times C_r$; (2) Storage - $Q = R \times A \times C_r$. A rainwater catchment system design has five (5) primary parameters such as 1) rainfall pattern, 2) water demand pattern, 3) collection area, 4) storage capacity, and 5) system reliability. What influences the rainfall amount is the design of the rain catchment area. The stored rainwater depends on the size of the tank. The model prototype includes the rainfall simulator, the catchment surface, an inlet canal, a filter compartment, circulation ports, storage tank and a cleanout outlet. It has an aluminium frame to support in carrying the model prototype for ease of mobility. The sizing for catchment area helps the designer the provision of the needed supply of drinking water to the public. The slope of the catchment is designed in such a way it will not affect the quickness of the water runoff during rainfall. The minimum slope is 15 degrees. The model used 30 degrees which are the maximum for the efficient running of water through gravity process. The slope affects how quickly water runoff during a rain event.

The SRHS model was designed to capture designated quantities of rainwater using basic computation as that of the prototype. The SRSB model represents the prototype due to fund constraints. The area of the SRHS that was designed to capture rainwater is known as the catchment surface. This surface was measured shaped and fixed at angle of approximately 15° using silicone adhesive sealant. The other areas was the inlet canal, this canal was designed to collect the rainwater that sheet flows from the catchment surface into the canal. The water from the inlet canal is channeled into the purpose built slow sand filter in to the storage tank then to distribution outlet. The primary materials used in this process are: Perspex, aluminum angle strips, rivets and silicone adhesive sealant. The tools used in this exercise were small power tools and marking and fabricating devices. Each panel of the model was marked out and fabricated separately and fixed together with silicone adhesive and rivets.

Figure 4.25 Plan View of SRHS model

Figure 4.26 Right elevation SRHS model

Figure 4.27 Sustainable rainwater harvesting model.

Figure 4.28 Sustainable rainwater harvesting model.

Source: Betasolo et al. Axiomatic design process in developing a model prototype Rainwater Harvesting Infrastructure 2016.

Chapter 5

CONCLUSION

Considerable theoretical and practical research effort was focused on examining the global perspective of sustainable rainwater harvesting systems and the associated policy framework and principles that supports the sustainability to the benefit of the needs of communities. The aim was to develop a model sustainable rainwater harvesting system in Lae City which is one of the wettest communities in Papua New Guinea which can be replicated throughout PNG.

To achieve this proposed model a thorough examination of the rainfall availability and pattern using computer software aided climate tool and rainwater harvesting tools. These investigations aided in determining the potential for achieving optimum quantities of water with sustainability to supply a designed demand population and at the same time preserving the integrity of the environment. The average rainfall at UNITECH campus varies between 217.9 mm in the driest months (February) and 309.3 mm in the wettest month (August). Hence, the total annual rainfall in an average year is 3163 mm, which shows a consistent pattern to support a SRHS.

In order to carry out this study a specific study site was mandatory with ample space and suitable topography and authorization to prevent disturbance during the course of the study and the area known as the Garden on Papua New Guinea University of Technology Campus was selected. To harvest rainwater efficiently requires an area where the hydrologic cycle function at peak calibration with good environmental management, therefore, the study site was located adjacent to the rainforest habitat to simulate a vegetation reserve that will support on rainfall inducement, that would be ideal to simulate a prototype for modelling in environmentally safe manner and a SRHS that would have the potential for replication throughout the water scarce communities without proper water infrastructure. A SRHS concrete catchment surface has a runoff coefficient of 0.9, which means that 90% of the rains can be harvested. Base on this runoff coefficient and a catchment surface area of 3977.1 m² a volume of 779,949 litres.

At the end of the study a workable concept will be provided representing a design prototype (in plan) of a sustainable rainwater harvesting system (SRSH) as an alternative water supply infrastructure that is not mechanical/electrically driven in harvesting rainwater.

- a) Catchment area
- b) Rainwater Collection Tank
- c) Utilities
- d) Network Distribution

A scaled model will amalgamate the elements of the prototype as described in the study for modelling and simulation physical outlay of SRHS, for potential a successful replication throughout the country.

This research has already achieved success on two levels (1) Papua New Guinea University of Technology now have a framework to implement a sustainable system on the University campus once funding becomes available. Thereby, becoming part of the global thrust for positive environmental change by using alternative water support, and play its part in influencing climate change in a positive direction in PNG. (2) The research sparks a conversation in the society about the utilization of alternative water support especially in difficult to reach communities. This conversation will inevitably bear positive fruits both by supplying people's water need throughout the country and the preservation of the environment.

Chapter 6

RECOMMENDATION AND FUTURE RESEARCH

Currently the Papua New Guinea University of Technology does not have a rainwater harvesting culture and the awareness of rainwater harvesting generally is limited. As the only Technology University in the South Pacific, several islands including the home country Papua New Guinea look to the institution for innovative technology output. Rainwater harvesting systems development through research is one such output that UNITECH should engage. The University could start by having rainwater harvesting awareness seminars and seek funding to propagate these seminars throughout the country at set intervals annually or coinciding with World Water Day which is March 22 (UN, 1992) each year. This exercise could build an awareness setting in the country that could encourage the use of rainwater harvesting as an alternative throughout and possibly extend regionally.

Another recommendation for the University campus is roof top rainwater harvesting. It is estimated that Papua New Guinea University of Technology campus has 500 housing units which are adequately constructed with appropriate zinc roofs. The institution should consider equipping all housing units with rainwater harvesting furniture and converting units to a dual piping system to potable for drinking and non-potable for flushing and washing. Non-potable would utilize rainwater collected from rainwater harvesting.

Finally, a rainwater harvesting curriculum should be developed in the University for the Civil Engineering and Mechanical Engineering Departments, starting at the undergraduate to the post graduate level. The Civil Engineers will emphasize infrastructural design and implementation while the Mechanical Engineers will emphasize the technological aspect such as conveyance and distribution using alternative energy sources.

Future research is recommended for the development of a rainwater harvesting network in Papua New Guinea that will form part of Water PNG's system of operation. By developing a database of the rainwater harvesting potential of each community, which will include rainfall availability and pattern to allow for quick access to rainfall information that will make it easier to implement a rainwater harvesting system in a community. It will also assist in further developing and standardizing model prototypes both in sizes and material types to fit various community profiles. The suggested approach requires considerable

financial manoeuvrings which will require specialized competences in conjunction with technical efforts.

Chapter 7

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Accetturo, A.&Ann Audrey 2012. Rainwater Harvesting Guidance toward a sustainable water future. <https://www.cob.org/documents/.../water-conservation/rainwater-harvesting-booklet> pp16-18 [Accessed September 10, 2016].

Barbados, G. O. 2000. National sustainable development policy and action plan. Barbados Sustainable Development Policy-part2 pp 1-27 [Accessed September 10, 2016].

Betasolo, M., Samson , G. & Anthony, B. 2014. Design of Sustainable use and Management of Groundwater in Marobe Province. Engineering Journal Proceedings of the 3rd International Workshop on Design in Civil and Engineering. DTU, Denmark, pp 27 - 34.

Cashman, A., Nurse, L. & Charley, J. 2010. Climate change in the Caribbean : The water management implication.

Climate, W. W. 2015. Weather and Climate: Papua New Guinea, average monthly Rainfall, Sunshine, Temperature, wind speed [Online]. Available: <https://weather-and-climate.com/average-monthly-Rainfall-Temperature-Sunshine-in-Papua-New-Guinea>. [Accessed April 27, 2015].

Cohen, M.&Forrester, A.2013. Special Issue Sustainable Food Consumption: Current Trends, Policy Approaches, and Future Scenarios. 1-3.

Collins, M. R., Eighmy, T. T.& JR, J. P. M. 1991. Evaluating modifications to slow sand filters1-9.

Conservancy, T. N. 2015. Explore water conservation in Papua New Guinea/ Papua New Guinea Water for Conservation [Online]. Available: [http:// www.nature.org](http://www.nature.org) > ... > Regions > Asia and the Pacific > Papua New Guinea [Accessed March 18, 2015].

Emmanuel, K.& Spence, B.2009. Climate change implications for water resource management in Caribbean tourism.,252-268.

Encyclopedia. 2016a. Aluminium [Online]. Available: <https://www.en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Aluminium> [Accessed March 13, 2016].

Encyclopedia. 2016b. Poly methyl methacrylate [Online]. Available: [https://www.en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Poly\(methyl_methacrylate\)](https://www.en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Poly(methyl_methacrylate)) [Accessed March 13, 2016].

Encyclopedia. 2016c. Water Cycle [Online]. Available: https://www.wikipedia.org/wiki/Water_cycle [Accessed March 12, 2016].

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Papua_New_Guinea [Online]. [Accessed November 20, 2015].

Encyclopedia. 2012. Water cycle[Online]. Available: <http://www.cyclewater.me.vccs.edu/courses/young/hydrologiccycle.htm> [Accessed June 2, 2015].

Environment, C.&2009. Department of Environment and Conservation in Papua New Guinea[Online]. Available: <http://www.egs.apec.org/morearticles/> [Accessed March 18, 2015].

ESL 2009. Management Solutions Limited Development of a national water sector adaptation strategy to address climate change in Jamaica.

- Eplorist, N. A. 2016. eXplorist 510 [Online]. Available: <http://www.magellangps.com/Store/eXploristSeries/eXplorist-510> [Accessed September 9, 2016].
- Fao, A. 2015. Papua New Guinea [Online]. Available: <http://www.fao.org/nr/water/.../print1.stm> [Accessed April 27, 2015].
- Fricano, R. J. & Grass, A. K. 2014. Evaluating American Rainwater Harvesting Policy: A Case Study of Three U.S. Cities. *Journal of Sustainable Development*, 7, 133-149.
- Gur, E.&Spuhler, D. 2015. Rainwater harvesting (Rural) SSWM[Online]. Available: <http://www.sswm.info> > ... > Hardware > Precipitation Harvesting [Accessed October 30, 2015].
- GWP. 2014. Global Water Partnership: Integrated water resources management in the Caribbean: The challenges facing Small Island Developing States. pp1-52.
- HABITAT FOR HUMANITY INTERNATIONAL, A.-P. O.2009. Poverty Housing in the Developing Nations of the Pacific Islands.
- Harris, D. J.& Milner, E.2007. The measurement of rainfall in Papua New Guinea, and its effect on microwave propagation. [Online]. Available: <http://www.onlinelibrary.wiley.com> > ... > Vol 8 Issue 3 > Abstract [Accessed October 18,2015].
- Hutchinson, A. P. 2010. Rain Water Harvesting – Case Studies from the Barbados Experience pp1-11. A_Hutchinson_RWH_barbados
- Jim, K. 2008. Water profile of Papua New guinea. The encyclopedia of earth,pp1-5.
- JØNCH-CLAUSEN, T. 2004. "...Integrated Water Resources Management (IWRM) and Water Efficiency Plans by 2005" Why, What and How? pp1-10 <http://www.gwp.org2004/2005> [Accessed September 9,2016].
- Kloss, C.& Robb, L. 2008. Managing Wet Weather with Green Infrastructure Municipal Handbook pp1-19. <http://www.dep.wv.gov/.../handbooks/.../Green> [Accessed September 9, 2016] .
- Korhnaak, L. V.2012. Restoring the Hydrological Cycle in the Urban Forest Ecosystem. pp1-6, http://www.agraria.unipd.it/materiale/.../URBAN_FORESTRY/ECOSYSTEM.../fr07000 [Accessed September 10, 2016].
- Latham, B.1987. Rainwater collection system : A Literature review , <http://www.ircwash.org/sites/default/files/Latham-1987-Rainwater.pdf> [Accessed September 10, 2016].
- Lehmann, C., Tsukada, R. &Lourete, A. 2010. Low-Cost Technologies Towards Achieving the Millennium Development Goals:The Case of Rainwater Harvesting. 1-4.
- Maino, P. 2013. Efforts in reorienting technical vocational education & training (TVET) system in Papua New Guinea (PNG) to the global economy: A case study. pp.290-295, http://www.unitech.ac.pg/Upload_Pdf/HS7-2013-46.pdf [Accessed September 10, 2016].
- Marilyn, W.2012. Climate-change mitigation and adaptation in small island developing states: the case of rainwater harvesting in Jamaica[Online]. Available: <http://www.sspp.proquest.com/archives/vol8iss2/communityessay.waite.html>, [Accessed September 9, 2016].
- McAlpine, J. R., Keig, G.& Falls, R.1983. Climate of Papua New Guinea pp.61-70,

http://www.pacificdisaster.net/pdnadmin/data/original/JP_DM594_PNG_1983_Climate.pdf
[Accessed September 10, 2016].

Morelock, J. 2015. Climate in Papua New Guinea. <https://www.pacificclimatechange.net/node/58>
[Accessed September 10, 2016].

Nijhof, S., Jantowski, B., Meerman, R. & Schoemaker, A. 2010. Rainwater harvesting in challenging environments: Towards institutional frameworks for sustainable domestic water supply, pp 210-212, <http://www.ircwash.org/sites/default/files/Nijhof-2010-Rainwater.pdf> [Accessed September 10, 2016].

Olaoye, R. A. & Olaniyan, O. S. 2012. Quality of Rainwater from Different Roof Material. pp 1-9, http://www.harvesth2o.com/adobe_files/Assessment%20of%20RWH%20Viability.pdf, [Accessed September 10, 2016].

Pandey, D., Gupta, A., & Anderson, D. 2003. Rainwater harvesting as an adaptation to climate change. pp 46–59, <http://www.nidm.gov.in/PDF/TrgReports/2011/September/temp/reading4.pdf>, [Accessed September 10, 2016].

Payet, R. & Agricole, W. 2006. Climate change in the Seychelles: implications for water and coral reefs, pp 182–189 <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/16944643>, [Accessed September 10, 2016].

Prentice, H. 1998. Hydrological Cycle, [buc.edu.in/sde_book/msc_water.pdf](http://www.buc.edu.in/sde_book/msc_water.pdf), [Online] [Accessed September 10, 2016].

Rogers, S. 2009. Access to clean water. The Guardian, <http://www.theguardian.com › Environment › Water>, [Accessed September 9, 2016].

Simple methods of the treatment drinking water Gabriele Heber 1985.

SLIDESHARE. 2016. Rainwater harvesting percolation pit [Online]. Available: <http://www.slideshare.net/pjicvinitb/rain-water-harvesting> [Accessed March 12, 2016].

Smet, J. & Wijk, C. V. 2002. Small Community Water Supplies Technology, People and Partnership, pp 466-490, <http://www.theijes.com/papers/v3-i4/Version-1/C03401016021.pdf>, [Accessed September 10, 2016].

Sopac. 2004. Harvesting the Heavens Guidelines for Rainwater Harvesting in Pacific Island Countries, <http://www.pacificwater.org/.../Harvesting>, [Accessed September 10, 2016].

Spooner, E. M. & McAlpine, J. R. 1986. PAPUA NEW GUINEA INVENTORY OF NATURAL RESOURCES, POPULATION DISTRIBUTION AND LAND USE HANDBOOK, http://www.pacificdisaster.net/.../JP_DM604c_PNG_1986_Inventory_natural_resources_sm, [Accessed September 10, 2016].

Thomas, E. N. 1980. The artificial and roof rainwater catches of Bermuda : Bermuda Public Works Department, pp 185 - 193, <http://www.oas.org/dsd/publications/unit/oea59e/ch10.htm> [Accessed September 10, 2016].

Thomas, T. H. & Martinson, D. B. 2007. Roofwater Harvesting: A Handbook for Practitioners, <https://books.google.com.jm/books?isbn=1604976659>, [Accessed September 10, 2016].

Trifunovic N. 2012. Water distribution, pp 470-480 http://www.samsamwater.com/library/TP40_21_Water_distribution.pdf, [Accessed September 10, 2016].

UN-HABITAT 2011. Rainwater Harvesting and Utilisation,

http://www.hpscste.gov.in/rwh/Blue_Drop_Series_02_-_Capacity_Building.pdf [Accessed September 10, 2016].

UN. 1992. World Water Day[Online], <http://www.timeanddate.com/holidays/un/world-water-day> [Accessed September 10, 2016].

UNDP 2014. 2014 National Human Development Report, From Wealth to Wellbeing: Translating Resource Revenue into Sustainable Human Development Papua New Guinea, pp58-60 <http://www.undp.org/.../undp/.../HDR/Asia>, [Accessed September 10, 2016] .

UNEP INTERNATIONAL ENVIRONMENTAL TECHNOLOGY CENTRE -OSAKA/SHIGA, J., IETC. 2001. Rainwater harvesting and utilisation : an environmentally sound approach for sustainable urban water management : an introductory guide for decision-makers. <http://www.unep.org/gc/gc22/Document/k0263456.pdf>, [Accessed September 10, 2016].

UNESCO. 2008. Asia and the Pacific, pp 19-22, UNESCO. 2008. Asia and the Pacific, [Accessed September 10, 2016].

UNESCO. 2012. Case_Studies_AsiaPacific,

www.unep.org/rso/Portals/118/Documents/NESs/ROAP/Indonesia_NES_2012, [Accessed September 10, 2016].

UNFCCC 2005. climate change small island developing States, pp.1-32

unfccc.int/resource/docs/publications/cc_sids.pdf, [Accessed September 11, 2016] .

UNICEF, W. 2014. The Independent State of Papua New Guinea Water, Sanitation and Hygiene Policy Development in Papua New Guinea SYNTHESIS REPORT OF TECHNICAL ASSISTANCE, https://www.wsp.org/sites/wsp.org/files/.../WSP_EAP_SDA_PNG_Report.pdf, [Accessed September 11, 2016] .

UNICEF., W.2011. Drinking Water Equity, safety and sustainability.

Waller. 1982. Rainwater as a supply source in Bermuda[Online]. Available: <http://www.eng.warwick.ac.uk/ircsa/abs/1st/184waller.htm> [Accessed July 23, 2015].

WATER, P. 2015. water sources [Online]. Available: <http://www.waterpng.com.pg/site/index>. [Accessed March 18, 2015].

WATERAID. 2013. Technical brief Rainwater Harvesting, <http://www.wateraid.org/~media/Publications/Rainwater-harvesting.pdf>, [Accessed September 11, 2016].

WATERPNG. 2015. About the company [Online]. Available: <http://www.waterpng.com.pg> [Accessed November 11, 2015].

WCC 2008. Drinking Water Chlorination : World Chlorine Council position paper, pp 1-8, http://www.worldchlorine.org/wp-content/.../WCC_Policy_Paper_Water_Chlorination.pdf, [Accessed September 11, 2016].

WHO 1978. WHO seminar pack for drinking-water quality, http://www.who.int/water_sanitation_health/dwq/S04.pdf, [Accessed September 11, 2016].

WHO 2008. Guidelines for Drinking-water Quality THIRD EDITION INCORPORATING THE FIRST AND SECOND ADDENDA Volume 1 ,pp166 - 180, www.who.int/water_sanitation_health/dwq/fulltext.pdf, [Accessed September 11, 2016].

WHO Chapter 12: Water Treatment. In: WHO (Editor) (2009): WHO Seminar Pack for Drinking Water Quality

http://www.who.int/water_sanitation_health/dwq/S12.pdf [Accessed April 4, 2017].

WORLD, BANK&GROUP. 2015. Climate changed knowledge portal [Online]. Available: <https://www.weather-and-climate.com/average-monthly-Rainfall-Temperature-> [Accessed October 24, 2015].

WORLDBANK 2013. Independent State of Papua New Guinea, pp 1-2,

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Papua_New_Guinea, [Accessed September 11, 2016].

WORLDBANK & GROUP. 2016. Climate changed knowledge portal: Average monthly temperature and rainfall for Papua New Guinea from 1990 - 2012 [Online]. [Accessed March 12, 2016].

Worm, J.&Hattum, T. V. 2006. Rainwater harvesting for domestic use ,pp.58-63,

http://www.journeytoforever.org/farm_library/AD43.pdf, [Accessed September 11, 2016].

WRA. 2011. Water Resources Authority Hydrology of Jamaica:Climate and Precipitation[Online]. Available: <http://www.wra.gov.jm/dynawebdti?dynasection=general&dynapage=hydrology> [Accessed August 22,2015].

8. APPENDICES

Appendix A: Google map of the SRHS site lay out

Map of Proposed SRHS in Lae City- Papua New Guinea (Location Plan)

Site layout plan

Site Plan:
 The Papua New Guinea
 University of Technology

Project Name:
 3D Model (Prototype Layout) of SRHS in Lae City a model
 for Papua New Guinea.

Sheet Title:
 CATCHMENT SITE PLAN

Sheet:
 2

Catchment Plan Layout

Catchment Front Elevation

The Papua New Guinea University of Technology

Project Name:
 3D Model (Prototype Layout) of SRHS in Lae City a model for Papua New Guinea.

Sheet Title:
 FRONT & RIGHT ELEVATION

Sheet No:
 3

Section through filter to storage tank

Section Through Filter

Organization: The Papua New Guinea University of Technology	Project Name: 3D Model (Prototype Layout) of SRHS in Lae City a model for Papua New Guinea.	Sheet Title: FILTER PLANA SECTION	Sheet No.: 4.2
--	--	---	--------------------------

Catchment foundation plan

Utilities room

Catchment Profile

Organization:

 The Papua New Guinea University of Technology

Project Name:
 3D Model (Prototype Layout) of SRHS in Lae City a model for Papua New Guinea

Sheet Title:
 CATCHMENT PROFILE

Sheet #:
 7

Foundation plan

Floor slab plan

Roof plan

Roofs slab plan

Institution: The Papua New Guinea University of Technology

Project Name: 3D Model (Prototype Layout) of SRHS in Lae City a model for Papua New Guinea

Sheet Title: TANK COVER DETAILS

Sheet No: 12

Detail sheet

Detail sheet

Section through storage tank

Section Through Tank

Detail sheet showing section through ladder and elevation of external access ladder

<p>Institution:</p> <p>The Papua New Guinea University of Technology</p>	<p>Project Name:</p> <p>3D Model (Prototype Layout) of SRLHS in Lae City a model for Papua New Guinea.</p>	<p>Sheet Title:</p> <p>LADDERDETAILS</p>	<p>Sheet#</p> <p>16</p>
--	--	--	-------------------------

Appendix C: Gravity Flow Calculations

Gravity flow calculation from SRHS storage reservoir to water tower

The Darcy-Weisbach formula:

ΔH = head loss (mwc)

T = Temperature

L = pipe length (m)

D = pipe diameter (m)

γ = friction factor (-)

v = the mean velocity in the pipe (m/s)

The Reynolds number indicates the flow regime

where: $Re = \frac{vD}{\nu}$

v = the mean velocity in the pipe (m/s)

D = pipe diameter (m)

ν = kinematic viscosity (m²/s)

$$\Delta H = 5 \text{ m}$$

$$L = 1300 \text{ m}$$

$$T = 30 \text{ C}^0$$

$$K = 0.05$$

$$D = 0.1 \text{ m}$$

$$V = 1 \text{ m/s} \quad \text{i.e. Assumed for iteration}$$

$$S = \frac{\Delta H}{L}$$

$$= \frac{5}{1300}$$

$$= 0.003846$$

$$v = \frac{497 \times 10^{-6}}{(T + 42.5)^{1.5}}$$

$$= \frac{497 \times 10^{-6}}{(30 + 42.5)^{1.5}}$$

$$= 8.051 \times 10^{-7} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$$

$$R_e = \frac{VD}{v}$$

$$= \frac{1 \times 0.1}{8.051 \times 10^{-7}}$$

$$= 124208.2$$

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{\gamma}} = -2 \log \left[\frac{5.128}{R_e^{0.89}} + \frac{K}{3.7D} \right]$$

$$= -2 \log \left[\frac{5.128}{124208.2^{0.89}} + \frac{0.05}{3.7 \times 100} \right]$$

$$= 7.0897$$

Therefore:

$$\gamma = 0.19895$$

$$V = \sqrt{\frac{2gDS}{\gamma}}$$

$$= \sqrt{\frac{2 \times 9.81 \times 0.1 \times 0.003646}{0.19895}}$$

$$= 0.195 \text{ m/s}$$

$$Q = VA = 0.195 \times \frac{0.1^2 \times \pi}{4}$$

$$= 0.0015 \text{ m}^3/\text{s} \text{ or } 1.5 \text{ L/s}$$